

USING ONLINE PRACTICES ON FACEBOOK: A STUDY OF MALES AND FEMALES USE OF ONLINE LINGUISTIC AND LEARNING RESOURCES ON A FACEBOOK GROUP, A BOURDIEUSIAN THEORETICAL LENS.

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degree of

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Declaration

I certify the following about the thesis entitled: *Using Online Practices on Facebook: A study of Males and Females Use of Online Linguistic and Learning resources on a Facebook group, a Bourdieusian Theoretical Lens.*

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Abstract

The immense growth of the internet shapes the way people communicate, by creating new forms of communication (Madge, et al 2019; Kahai and Lei, 2009). Social networking sites is a prominent way in which technology impacts individuals' practices. Facebook is one of the dominant and important social network sites nowadays (Naseri, 217), not only used for social purposes, but also for academic ones (Laidfa, 2018; Mokededem, 2021). The digital affordances of Facebook groups provide a bi/multilingual environment for bi/multilingual users to practise their linguistic habitus and perform their online social behaviour. This study is sets out to examine the online linguistic practices, particularly the code-switching practices of 17 Kabyle students, who are multilingual active Facebook users. The Kabyles are the Amazigh ethnic group of indigenous people of North Africa. These students are proficient in at least four languages: Tamazight language with its variety (Kabyle), Arabic language, French, and English in addition to other digital behaviours and semiotic features such as the use of emoji, and internet memes. Nevertheless, the majority of studies tackle code-switching on Facebook, focusing mainly on its types and frequency. More attention is needed to understand the online practices of code switching in terms of the linguistic habitus and gender dynamics. The study of gender dynamics is pivotal as it depicts the way individual construct their online identities, revealing potential benefits in self-representation. The purpose of this study is to explore how these adult participants use their linguistic resources on their social interaction and how these practices differ from males to females. Additionally, the study focuses on participants' perceptions towards their own linguistic practices, while also giving due consideration to how these perceptions are related to their linguistic habitus, social cultural, and sociopsychological perspectives. Furthermore, the study aims at investigating the different online behaviours employed by each gender while commenting/posting on Facebook. For this reason, I conducted a qualitative study focusing on specific students' community on a Facebook group. Using an online ethnography, I explored the research questions by conducting an- in depth interview and online-observation of 17 participants involved in sharing course related materials and linguistic resources. With findings arrived at through thematic analysis and qualitative content analysis. Importantly the findings revealed that Facebook groups that are used for sharing educational resources among students create a sense of belonging and relatedness among students. Crucially too, the findings contends

that the use of the linguistic dynamics vary between males and females' practices in language use. This heterogeneity lies in the code-choice used by each gender, factors deriving these choices, audience, topic, and the use of emoji that each gender employs. It argues that policymakers have a crucial role in fostering an environment that supports diverse linguistic practices. Key recommendations include the development of teacher training programs to better integrate code-switching into teaching strategies, the revision of language policies to reflect the benefits of multilingualism, and the need for further research to evaluate the impact of code-switching on student outcomes. By adopting such frameworks, educators and policymakers can enhance the learning experience and promote a more inclusive, linguistically diverse educational environment.

Key words: Online linguistic practices, online social behaviour, language dynamics, code-switching, Facebook educational groups, gender.

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Chapter One: Framing the Research

1.1 Introduction

The wide growth of technology brought the acceleration to different forms of communication, which in turn shapes both the online learning dispositions and the online linguistic practices among individuals when communicating, sharing, and commenting (Al-Sharqi and Abbasi, 2020; Vlachopoulos and Makri, 2019). One of the significant ways that technology influences the communication is through the proliferation of social networking sites, particularly Facebook. Social networking sites reinforces and nurtures the development of “network capital” (Larsen and Urry, 2006b). According to Larsen, Urry, and Axhausen (2008, p.656) network capital as the “capacity to engender and sustain social relations with people who are not necessarily proximate, and which generates emotion, financial, and practical benefits”. Therefore, I would argue that network capital should be further explained as a form of capital that encompasses the social and relational resources that social actors possess to facilitate through personal relationships. Being a virtual space where individuals build and establish their social connections for different purposes, Facebook can be seen a network capital that facilitates the availability of resources through connection and interaction (Wellman and Frank, 2001).

Considering Facebook, it can be defined as a “social media platform that was started in 2004 with the goal of connecting friends, students, family, building communities and businesses” (Nichols, 2020, p.3). By means of Facebook, users can create Facebook groups, within the Facebook platform. This is due to the multiple affordances, including the social, linguistic, and pedagogical ones that the Facebook groups offer (Wang et al, 2011). That is, members of the Facebook group can post, share learning resources, through text, images, videos, and links. They can also exchange language through the post and comment features. Additionally, Facebook is not only used for communication, but also it used as a source to share the knowledge, perform the social rules, and it allows users to share resources (Kahai and Lei, 2019). This present study deals with an educational Facebook group, which is considered as

a 'sanctuary'¹ for postgraduate students to share knowledge and demonstrate their linguistic repertoires, herein being a network capital.

Therefore, this thesis fits into the fields of sociolinguistics and the sociology of education in Computer Mediated Communication, CMC. It examines an educational Facebook group *Département D'Anglais Officiel*, which is created and managed by students. Importantly, it seeks to explore how this group helps students to share and exchange their learning resources. Critically too, this study explains how the linguistic dynamics, particularly the code-switching dynamics, that are manifested in the group, vary from males to females' practices. Students use this group to construct their knowledge, using their learning dispositions and linguistic resources. Such a construction is achieved when they post, share, and comment to one another. That is, when students share their course-related materials on the group, they develop a mutual and shared understanding of their social and cultural world. Similarly, when students use language to comment or share, they are also constructing their unique perspectives of their social and cultural world.

By doing so, this study hopes to contribute to the existing body of literature in the realm of online learning and linguistic exchanges, among males and females, in the Kabyle context. Moreover, the results of the study contribute to the knowledge by generating interesting insights in relation to sharing the learning resources and practising the linguistic capitals, in social networking sites. Significantly too, in order to attain this goal, a theoretical/ conceptual framework is adopted to understand how users demonstrate their linguistic capital and habitus, their learning resources, including sharing notes, exchanging knowledge, contributing to this knowledge, and gaining skills through the interactions they have on the Facebook group. Their interaction can be shaped by users' habitus and their individual dispositions.

While students engage in online social media, there has been a lack of in-depth qualitative research exploring the ways students use these platforms to enhance their learning experiences and manifest their discourses.

1 The word 'sanctuary' in this thesis is used as a description to the Facebook group where participants share, post, and communicate. The substance of this terms appears in my findings to express the way students perceive the Facebook group, and the way they jointly share their educational and language resources.

The research contributes to knowledge about the use of linguistic and learning resources on digital settings. The findings are of use not only to researchers in digital language dynamics and learning dispositions withing social networking sites, but also it helps teachers and students to understand the process of exclusion and inclusion in a society. Because, based on the research findings, there is a democracy that is excluded. But, again, then students are included; their inclusion is shallower, but they still get educated and get a qualification. The impact on society thus, can be seen through the dilemma of inclusion and exclusion, and these are things for policy to look at. My contribution to the national policy discussion is that creating Facebook group for educational purposes can have several potential benefits. For one, Facebook is widely used social media platforms, so incorporating it into educational policy could provide an opportunity to engage students in a platform that they are already familiar with and comfortable using it. Secondly, Facebook can be a useful tool for collaboration among both students and teachers. It can allow for easier sharing of learning capitals and hence create an online community of learners. However, it is also important to raise that using Facebook in education policy also raises concerns about confidentiality and credibility. Therefore, any implementation of Facebook should be done thoughtfully and with appropriate guidelines in place.

At the level of habitus, it needs to be viewed as they are formed through our socialisation experiences, and cultural backgrounds. Since the Facebook group market includes males and females' users, this research also contributes to knowledge about how gender differences, in terms of language habitus and learning dispositions, can be depicted in social networking sites. During my initial research for this study, I discovered that there was a relatively amount of existing literature on this topic. Furthermore, when I searched for research that explored the intersection of Bourdieu with topics such as online learning, language use, and gender, I found very little that addressed all of these areas, and none that fully answered the questions I had set out to investigate what role does the Facebook group play, what type of learning is there, and how does males sharing differ from females' ones; this is in terms of the linguistic and learning resources. Hence, in the literature review chapter, I consider work that falls into the three separate areas of these study.

Before moving on into the gaps of knowledge that this study brings to the literature, it is necessary to provide a comprehensive overview of its subject and focus. Therefore, the next section discusses the research scope and focus.

1.2 Positionality: Reflections

This section features my reflections through which I view and perceive the world. Providing a reflective account of my personal background traces my motives for choosing this research topic, its theoretical framework, and methodological underpinnings, as well as its participants. This view aligns with what Gary and Holmes (2020) pertains to as a researcher's positionality in relation to his/her world view, background, and "assumptions about human nature and agency", which dictates the way individuals interact with the social world (Sikes, 2004, p.18). Equally too, Sikes (2004) elucidates that understanding the researcher's background and perspective is crucial in understanding the social world.

From a student's perspective, Facebook groups have played a significant role in keeping me updated with the department news, including administrative updates and course-related material resources. I have been active in sharing course-related materials, including my own notes to support fellow students in their exam preparation or when seeking for help. Observing the way collaborative nature of the group, with students harmoniously collaborated and engaged with each other's inquiries inspired me to dig deeply in the online learning habitus of students as well as it makes me wondering about the type of learning that is going on, on the group. Interestingly, it was intriguing to observe how my colleagues' attitudes in the group differed from their actual behaviour in physical classrooms. This has triggered my impetus to study how students use Facebook groups, how their learning practices are demonstrated, and what kind of learning they share. Importantly, too, I have found that the practice of sharing is different in a sense of language usage.

Considering languages and taking the fact that I had the chance to grow up in a multilingual community, Algeria, where each language and each variety is associated within its cultural, social, and political fields (Rouabah, 2022; McDougall, 2006). The diversity of languages leads language users to produce their linguistic habitus that they have in their social and cultural capital, with alternating codes from one language to another and from one variety to another. I was and I am always inspired by the use of languages used by multilingual individuals and the way they alternate and switch between languages. My first impression was that code switching, the use of two or more linguistic varieties, is common only in oral communication, i.e. face to face communication, until I joined the blue space, Facebook where I was

astonished by students' use of language(s) in their comments, posts, and even chats. Despite of other social networking platforms, it remains the most dominant platform among its users and hence gains a huge interest among researchers (Hellamans, 2020). Users, males, and female ones, use different forms of capitals to express their thoughts, and share their resources. Interestingly, their practices differ from males to females. This drives me further to wonder how Facebook educational group could be used as a social capital for learning, what support does it offer, and how students practices differ in online communication. To my surprise, there is a very limited literature tackling that issue, the thing that undoubtedly makes me more curious as it increases my desire to further research.

1.3 Merging the Threads: narrowing the scope and broadening the research focus

The main thrust of this section is to describe the process of developing the scope and focus of this study. In my earliest stage of writing this thesis, my focus was vague and not clear enough; it was true that I wanted to investigate the linguistic behaviour, and its use among the two genders, yet I was a bit unsure about the studies that reflect my focus and motivation per se. My first impression was that the mere way to study the linguistic behaviour is through the spoken communication, offline one; Until I joined Facebook where I was impressed by the users' use of languages. I then decided to study these behaviours in their online occurrence and see how individuals perceive their own practices. Still, my focus was too broad as I need to sharpen a particular setting and target population. More importantly, I was unsure about which theoretical perspective I should follow to reflect my study on and gain deeper insights. Additionally, my focus was on studying the linguistic behaviours of both males and females on their personal account. At this point, I realised this would cause issues regarding ethics and confidentiality. For this reason, I shift my focus to study a Facebook group where students share their learning resources and use language per se. I figured this out when I started the process of collecting my data.

When I was immersed in the field, the research scope appears to be refined. A research scope according to Bryman and Bell (2015) can be inferred and constructed from the data that is gathered from the study. Reflecting on this point, after the process of interviewing and observing participants' practices on the group, there was a stress on the importance of this

Facebook group as a learning institution that helps students to share notes of their course-related materials, exchange ideas and even revise for exams. Additionally, some participants emphasized that accommodation strategies are factors that shape their language use. This indicates that they are aware of the 'rules of the games' (Bourdieu, 1977).

Therefore, it can be argued that exchanging notes and sharing course materials on the Facebook group impacts students' learning dynamics and practices. This way, the group is considered as a core element of the participants' habitus (Reiss and Tsvetkova, 2019). The question that may arise to the reader's mind is how students manifest their linguistic and learning habitus on the group and how these practices differ from males' use to females' ones.

1.3.1 Research Aims and Research Questions

Based on the research aims stated above, I believe that I should be clear about how the central focus and the research questions can be further developed. Hence, this section presents both the research aims and questions that underpin this study. Following the aforementioned theories, I started developing my questions, and hence, I settled in the following research questions: these questions were informed by a process of personal experience, as a multilingual and a Facebook user.

1.3.1.1 RQ1: How does the Facebook group used as a learning resource?

The purpose of this question was to explore the habitus of how students share their course-related materials in the group. The aim was known to be relying on these materials to gain profits, which are in this case, passing their exams. Meanwhile, this question addresses the role of this group in creating a community of practice among students. On the other hand, the question leads to see this group as a means to debate full-time engagement. The Facebook group was initiated based on altruistic values that are set up by students to help other people. That is, they are not doing it for personal gain. However, these altruistic values have led some students to take it in unintended directions, such as using it as a way not to join real classes.

1.3.1.2 RQ2 How do students harness symbolic capital that is conveyed linguistically in their Facebook group?

With respect to the second question, the way students practise their linguistic capital (repertoire) will be described. These practices will be addressed based on what students share, post, and comment on the Facebook group, with a focus of their code-switching practices and language choice. Kabyle students of English have the full access to different linguistic repertoire. The other potential aim, this question seeks to look at the way students use their linguistic capitals, which languages they use and what factors drive their choices, and to offer a sense of their linguistic diverse when posting or commenting to each other. Participants' active use and engagement in the group show that Facebook could be used as a market for language gain and knowledge gain.

1.3.1.3 RQ3 How do students' dynamics in the group differ from males to females?

The main thrust of this question is to understand how males and females use dynamics are practised when they share on the group. Sharing practices differ based on socio-cultural capital differences. This refers to factors such as their social status and cultural background, and gender norms. Differentiation in practices between males and females in terms of approaching, engaging, and contributing to certain practices on the group.

By doing so, this study hopes to contribute to the existing body of literature in the realm of online learning and linguistic exchanges, among males and females, in the Kabyle context. Moreover, the results of the study contribute to the knowledge by generating interesting insights in relation to sharing the learning resources and practising the linguistic capitals, in social networking sites. Participants' active use and engagement in the group show that Facebook could be used as a market of learning and as a linguistic market where students' exchange and harness their linguistic resources. Variation in practice between males and females' dynamics. Hence, I suggest that more attention in future research should be directed at exploring the merits of the Facebook group in learning; exchanging ideas, revising for passing the exams, and as a platform where linguistic capitals are manifested, at the level of gender variations. My argument then is that the social networking site, Facebook provides a dynamic and engaging learning experience among students, as it allows students to practise

their language resources, by engaging in learning-related discussion and even debates. Furthermore, through these social interactions that are manifested in the Facebook group, difference in practice and behaviour between males and females' students is spotted. At this level, I should further argue that by investigating the learning practices and behaviours on Facebook, including how these practices vary between males and females can help to identify further practices for using Facebook group to promote learning outcomes, linguistic practices, and foster a sense of connectedness with others.

Methodology-wise, to achieve the research objectives of this study, and to address the research questions, which are presented in section 1.3., I advocated a qualitative methodology, which seeks to understand a phenomenon in its breadth, rather than in-depth (Blaxter et al, 1996; Dawadi, Shrestha, and Giri, 2021). Understanding in this study is achieved through an online ethnography as a methodology to explore how the selected Facebook group is used as both a linguistic market and an educational platform, where students harness their learning and language dispositions. This was achieved through online observation, and online -semi-structured interviews, as data collection tools.

Having presented a roadmap of the main focus of this thesis, the coming sections are structured as follows: firstly, section 1.1, fuses the rationale for carrying out this research. Section 1.2 presents the main research questions which this study poses, followed by the aims that are portrayed in 1.3. Thirdly, section 1.4 discusses the originality and contribution of the study.

1.4 Critical reflections on the Kabyle Context

The aim of this section is to examine important aspects concerning language dynamics and learning/educational dispositions in the Kabyle context in Algeria. These aspects are discussed in relation to the theoretical and practical shortcomings in the Kabyle region of Algeria. Nonetheless, a thorough description of the wider context within which the study takes place will be discussed in chapter two. Hence, this section reviews the educational system in Algeria, reflecting on educational and gender insight. The use of online social networking sites for the purpose of learning and sharing course materials will be also demonstrated.

1.5 Critical Reflections on Facebook group as a Social Capital

By prioritising multilingualism and offering quality language education, Algeria can equip its citizens, students, and graduates with the necessary linguistic skills to thrive in a globalised world. To enhance the educational system, the TESOL profession organised Athens proposed that multilingualism should be embodied in language education policy as valuable capital language education policies and practices (Cook,2016; TESOL International,2017). However, with the rise of COVID-19, the Algerian education sector, as most of the educational institutions, has been disrupted by shifting to an online remote learning, using different learning platforms and tools (Ghounane, 2022). This being either by relying on asynchronous learning, using the different social networking sites such as Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp, or engaging in different synchronous modes that offer virtual environments, such as educational platforms including Moodle and Microsoft Teams. Drawing on this point, Murphy et al. (2011) maintained that synchronous online learning is student-based, while the asynchronous mode priorities the importance of instructors' involvement. However, it is true that implementing these two modes of learning inevitably influence the process of interaction between teachers and their students as the interaction between both parties is absent, but the idea that categorises asynchronous learning to student-focused and synchronous learning as teacher-based is often misleading as both synchronous and asynchronous modes are guided and controlled by teachers to meet students' needs (Bryson and Andres, 2020).

Nowadays, the rise of technology, particularly with social networking sites has profoundly influenced the way students learn (Ghounane, 2021). Searches within this review assert that students exhibit a greater motivation towards the utilisation of Social Networking Sites (SNSs) in educational settings compared to the use of synchronous, or other Learning Management System (LMS) platforms such as Moodle, Zoom, and Kahoot. In this regard, Muls et al (2019) and Jumaat and Tasir (2016) claim that using SNSs has many merits in providing students with opportunities to interact and exchange course-related ideas with their peers. Not only students, but even teachers have also been 'attracted' to the utilisation of the different SNSs as a platform for sharing and engaging in online courses and academic discussion (Jumaat and Tasir, 2016, p.5). As indicated earlier, there is a harmony among scholars in relation to the merits of Facebook as an online educational platform among students and teachers. In this regard, Saif and Jemni (2017), have asserted that Facebook has become pervasive compared

to the other social sites. This pervasiveness attracted researchers in the field to investigate its educational use. This is because of the affordances it provides among its users. In this regard, Al-Quasi et al (2023) argue that social networking sites are effective tools for fostering collaboration and communication among students. This includes assisting students in their research, sharing information, staying updated, as well as building connections with peers. Interestingly however, given the fact that different affordances are available in SNSs, particularly Facebook, the online practices vary from male to female users. Gender differences occur at the level of the practice of sharing the content itself, the language used to comment or to post (Schwartz et al, 2013), as in how each gender perceives Facebook (Biernatowska, Balcerowska, and Bereznowski, 2017).

1.6 Potential significance of the research

The breadth of this research lies in the connection between language use, learning habitus, gender, society and social media. Its depth lies in the way in which the methodology will allow the researcher to get a deeper understanding of the phenomenon of the learning dispositions and the linguistic habitus that are manifested in the Facebook group. Besides, it looks at how these behaviours vary males and females' students. This multidisciplinary approach offers an original perspective in understanding of the habitus manifestation in relation to gender dynamics in online communication among the multilingual Kabyle students of English. Beginning with the theoretical aspect, this study contributes to the area of learning habitus and language strategies at the level of gender variation. My argument based on this point would be that the use of the Facebook group is the mechanism that students deploy, and they engage with to gain the educational gain, that is exchanging ideas to pass the exams and linguistic gain, that is practicing the language that participants have in their linguistic capitals. However,

Secondly, at the methodological level, considering the dearth of qualitative research, particularly the online ethnographical studies in relation to the online dispositions among males and female students on the social networking sites, Facebook, and how they perceive these practices, this study is underpinned by Bourdieu theory of practice. Taking this idea into account, this study seeks to explore gender variation in social media. Practically, the researcher hopes that this research could be beneficial in sociolinguistic areas in general and

for English students, specifically, for further research about the language and gender variation occurring in the Kabyle context and in the social networking sites. This study also hopes to contribute to the body of knowledge by contributing to computer Mediated Communication, CMC learning, language use and behaviours, and gender variation in Kabyle. This thesis is interdisciplinary in nature as it embraces interrelated aspects of knowledge. It aims at providing a clear insight about students learning dispositions on Facebook education group and the linguistic habitus of males and females to foster cooperative online learning gain as well as a linguistic gain.

1.7 Reflective and concluding Thoughts.

This chapter located the research focus and scope and highlights its research questions and aims. It also offered an overview about my personal background, that motivates me to pursue this study.

To reiterate, the research questions that directed this study were inspired by my introspective experiences as a multilingual speaker and a Facebook group user. Moreover, the study was directed by relevant literature. It aims to contribute to the current body of research regarding how the gender norms shape both the online linguistics and the learning experiences of students when using educational Facebook groups. Furthermore, it looks at the Facebook group as a learning platform where learners work harmoniously and collaboratively. which is, to my best of knowledge, does not really investigated in the Algerian context in general and in Kabyle, in particular.

To conclude this chapter, I provide an overview of the organisation of the remaining sections of the thesis.

Chapter Two: Setting the Scene: The Background Context of the Study

2.1 Introduction

The main thrust behind setting out this chapter is to present a contextual background for the reader, to be able to navigate a map of the study context. The chapter is divided into six sections. It begins with presenting a historical background about the Algerian context. It then moves to discuss how the Colonialism impacted the nation, by focusing on the linguistic impact. The chapter then progresses to narrow its contextual scope and describe the Tamazight and Kabyle language. Discussion of the use Kabyle dialect in Algeria will be critically discussed as a main core of investigation in this study. A panoramic discussion of the education policy in Algeria and the learning scenario is also demonstrated, this encompasses a broad and in-depth analysis of the educational policies and the way in which learning is facilitated and experienced within the Algerian context.

2.2 Education Policy: Linguistic Practices and Challenges

The section attempts to present the educational policy and its challenges in Algeria. Its main aim is to explore the vital role of the Algerian education in shaping the social and cultural landscape. Following the country's independence, education in Algeria witnessed significant reforms, driven by the economic, social, and political shifts (AL-Hamdani, 2022). The local interpretation of the education policy in Algeria in relation to language policy has been updated recently to promote the use of multiple language varieties, including French and English while also recognising Tamazight as an official language. The presence of these languages in the educational settings continues to influence the sociolinguistic and public fields (Rouabah, 2022). In this respect, I would like to draw on my personal experiences, as a former Algerian student who lives in the farthest East of Algeria, Tamazight was not incorporated in schools, as well as in some other regional schools. I would argue that despite being recognised as an official language, Tamazight continues to be marginalised in practice as it is not treated on equal footing with Arabic and French (Bourdieu, 1958). However, during the Berber Cultural Movement that starts in 1988, the Ministry of Higher Education in Algeria responded to this marginalisation by establishing the department of Berber Language and Culture, at Mouloud Mammeri University in Tizi Ouzou (HCA, 2014). The objective behind establishing this department was to provide a research training to set up a master level curriculum in three major areas namely: linguistics, literature, and civilisation (HCA, 2014).

By prioritising multilingualism and offering quality language education, Algeria can equip its citizens, students, and graduates with the necessary linguistic skills to thrive in a globalised world. To expand the educational infrastructure, the TESOL profession organised Athens proposed that multilingualism should be embodied in language education policy as valuable capital language education policies and practices (Cook,2016; TESOL International,2017). However, with the rise of COVID-19, the Algerian education sector, as most of the educational institutions, has been disrupted by shifting to an online remote learning, using different learning platforms and tools (Ghounane, 2022). This being either by relying on asynchronous learning, using the different social networking sites such as Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp, or engaging in different synchronous modes that offer virtual environments, such as educational platforms including Moodle and Microsoft Teams. Drawing on this point, Murphy et al. (2011) maintained that synchronous online learning is a student-based, while the asynchronous mode prioritises the importance of instructors' involvement. However, it is true that implementing these two modes of learning inevitably influence the process of interaction between teachers and their students as the interaction between both parties is absent, but the idea that categorises asynchronous learning to student-focused and synchronous learning as teacher-based is often misleading as both synchronous and asynchronous modes are guided and controlled by teachers to meet students' needs (Bryson and Andres, 2020).

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educational use. This is because of the affordances it provides among its users. In this regard, Al-Quasi et al (2023) argue that social networking sites are effective tools for fostering collaboration and communication among students. This includes assisting students in their research, sharing information, staying updated, as well as building connection with peers. Interestingly however, given the fact that different affordances are available in SNSs, particularly Facebook, the online practices vary from male to female users. Gender differences occur at the level of the practice of sharing the content itself, the language used to comment or to post (Schwartz et al, 2013), as in how each gender perceives Facebook (Biernatowska, Balcerowska, and Bereznowski, 2017). Therefore, this section now turns to discuss how the 987the online practices on Facebook. Education Policy: Linguistic Practices and Challenges

2.3 History of Algeria: A historical and a sociolinguistic background

Discussing the historic background of Algeria is crucial in understanding its linguistic complexity. In this section, I aim to provide a better understanding of the study context and it draws out how the history of Algeria influences language and its practices among agents. When Algeria got its independence on July 1962, the Arabic language became the only official language of the government. However, the Algerian authorities added the Tamazight language as a second national language in April 2002 and latterly, in 2016, it became the second official language. Both languages according to Benrabah indicate “a language family of Afro-Asiatic

2.4 History Matters: the impact of the colonialism in Algeria and Amazigh

In this section, I aim to portray the historical movements Algeria went through. Being the largest country in Africa and due to its coastal plain and Saharan deserts, Algeria has been viewed as a gateway and a targeted object to many conquests. Nevertheless, the history of Algeria was at first marked by the presence of Amazigh (the Imazighen), since this ethnic group was the indigenous people of North Africa, as well as by the Carthaginian civilization which was controlled by the Phoenician traders in North Africa (Maddy-Weeitzman, 2011). The arrival of Phoenicians to North Africa marks the use of the Punic languages among colonies. This has influenced the Berber language, and hence Berbers became bilinguals as Punic; the language of the Carthaginian empire, was their second language after the Amazigh (Berber)

language. After the Carthaginian Empire declined, the Roman Empire took its control and occupied the region. Again, this has led to language contact and subsequently Berbers of North Africa at that time, became multilinguals (Benabou, 1976). However, Latin, the official language of Rome, was not spoken by the majority; it was highly used by the elite. In contrast, Punic and Berbers maintained their domination. Though the vandals and the Byzantes came after the Romans and occupied Algeria, only Berber, Punic, and Latin were the languages used at that time.

The Byzantine invasion was interrupted by the Arabic conquest that resisted for five centuries. The Arabic invasion succeeded in reshaping North African culture in both language and religion. Arabs introduced the Arabic language and the Islamic religion. As a result, most Berbers entered to Islam, without being forced, and it became their religion (Wara, 2015).

Algeria witnessed the Spanish settlement in the coastline cities. It started to seize some parts of Algeria like Mers el Kebir, Oran, Bougie, Tenes, Dellys, and Tlemcen (Gillespie, 2000). However, the Spanish settlement was ceased by the Othman Empire who control of the nation, from 1529 until the coming of French in July 1830. This long period was remarkable enough for both Algeria and the Othman empire as the latter took to put Algeria under the domination of the Turkish protectorate (Benrabah, 2013). Due to the long period-settlement of Turks in Algeria, there was an impact on the language use among Algerians, at that time as multilingualism was predominant. In this vein, Benrabah (2005, p.349) claims that during this long period of time, "multilingualism involving approximately 15 languages prevailed". Turks used the Othman Turkish language, and it was recognized as an official language. Berber language and dialects were preserved as colloquial languages whereas Arabic was conserved as a liturgical language that is mostly used for religious purposes (Şahan Güney, 2018; Benrabah, 2013). The coming of French who invaded Algeria from 1830 to 1962 has put an end to the Turkish domination in Algeria. Algeria has been a subject to many invasion and civilization, this in turn has deep influences on its cultural and linguistic situations and therefore Algeria becomes a multilingual community (Benrabah, 2014). However, due to the numerous and various invasion it faced, only three languages were used namely Berber language with its varieties, Arabic language with its varieties and French. The above section represented the classical history of northern Algeria and the Berbers (Kabyles), in particular. The next section will discuss the history of Algeria during the French revolution and how this long duration period has affected the Algerian's verbal repertoire.

2.5 Colonial Algeria (1830-1962)

The French invasion was one of the most critical movements in Algeria as it lasted for 132 years and has influenced both the social, cultural, and linguistic (During this period, 1830, the total population density was about 3 million, with a Berber population representing 50% of Algeria (Benrabah, 2013). Ethnicity was a major characteristic on which lay people differentiated between Berbers and Arabs. However, linguistics, i.e. language, is the key index that distinguishes the two groups; Berbers speak Tamazight as their first language while Arabs use Arabic with its varieties (El Aissati, 2001; McDougall, 2017). This section discusses the major impact of the French colonialism on Algeria and Amazigh (Kabyles). When the colonizer settled in Algeria, they dispossessed the peasantry, especially those who belong to Amazigh peasants, and provide them to the European settlers (Knauss, 1977; Bennoune, 1976-2002). Algeria was introduced as a French land that was classified, by the Minister of Domestic Affairs into three departments namely: Algiers, Oran, and Constantine (Calvet, 2017). Nevertheless, these departments have been divided into a European zone (civilians), the mixed, that constitutes of two different ethnic groups and the Arabs zone, that was populated by the natives, the thing that makes the community a subject to military rule (Haouam, 1990). French reinforced the idea of dividing Algerians into zones and hence it succeeded in creating a racial division between two ethnic groups, Arabs and Amazigh. The latter group was conservative in terms of religion and language especially before the Arab Muslim conquest. During the French revolution, they were highly accepted by the French coloniser due to their religious heterogeneity (Benrabah, 2005; Benrabah; 2013). Nevertheless, the Arabs embraced the Islam. As far as language is concerned, the Arabic language, with its dialect, was spoken almost in the majority of regions whereas The Tamazight language, including its Kabyle dialect, remains the major language used in the mountain (Benrabah, 2005). During this era, the Arabic language was portrayed as a cosmopolitan language as it was the most used language for commercial purposes. Tamazight language, from the other hand, was mainly used for local communication. Notably, this is because Imazighen were sedentary population whereas Arabs were nomadic (Locrin, 2014).

The language policy and language planning during this era marked the use of French as a powerful language that governs the Algerian society. The long-term period of the French colonisation in Algeria introduced French as an official language in 1848 and it has been seen

as a superior language in their linguistic markets, i.e their linguistic varieties and proficiencies. Benrabah (2005, p. 2008) claims, “In the linguistic market, French has a high value and carries a prestigious image”. This policy caused a great change not only in terms of the linguistic market, field, and habitus, but also in the social organisation, agriculture and social economy of the community (Bourdieu, 1962). In his book, *the Algerians* which was originally published in 1958, and further expanded in 1961, Bourdieu argues that Algerian’s social formation was indissolubly related to the European colonies who gain the social capital in the region. Algerians who belong to the lower classes have their own habitus (perception) in seeing the world around them. Within the French market, Algerians perceive all agents from the dominant society including, teachers, doctors, and administrators tied to the colonial context (Bourdieu, 1961). In terms of agriculture market, Bourdieu claims that individual capital, resources and powers (Bourdieu, 1984), influence the relationship between the farmer, his family, and the tribe in relation to honour and prestige (Bourdieu, 1961). Unlike French that was recognized as the first language by law, Arabic was, at that time, considered as a foreign language and it was banned from use in the educational contexts (Al-Khatib 2008). The Tamazight language with its varieties was also unrecognised. However, that recognition was not symbolic but literal as penetrating the French language in schools aims at obliterating the Algerian identity and culture and spreading the colonial culture and language instead.

2.6 L’Algérie Libre/ Independent Algeria: A linguistic Profile

This section aims at discussing the post- war Algeria period and its linguistic profile. In 1962, Algeria got its independence. However, the remnants of the French colony remain evident. At this exact era- 1962, just after the independence, 90% of Algerians were illiterate and six million of them were capable to use French whereas only one million were able to read it (Benrabah, 2013). Nowadays, Algeria is a multilingual community that represents a multilingual market (Benrabah, 2014; Batibo, 2005). Multilingualism refers to the coexistence of more than one language by individual or by a speech community. According to Stavans and Hoffman (2015), multilingualism refers to the ability of using a range of autonomous languages that suggests the existence of a separate system. Among the linguistic varieties that exist in today’s Algerian verbal repertoire are; standard Arabic which has been formally officialised to be used as a first language in 1963, the Algerian Arabic that is used in informal settings and in daily communication, Tamazight language has been recognised by the Algerian

gouvernement as an official language January 2016. This means that it is taught in schools and used in administrative documents. The next section will discuss further details about each language in the post war Algeria.

2.6.1 Arabic

Arabic is a Semitic language that is considered as a national language of 14 countries. Generally, it is widely used in the Middle East and North Africa. "There are 14 nations where Arabic is the sole official language. Of these, four are in Africa: Tunisia, Egypt, Mauritania, and Libya. The remaining countries where Arabic is the official language are situated in the Middle East: The United Arab Emirates, Yemen, Qatar, Bahrain, Kuwait, Oman, Syria, Saudi Arabia, and Jordan" (Maps of World, 2018). Arabic has various language varieties and it can be represented as the following; Classical Arabic (CA), Modern Standard Arabic (MSA), and the Algerian (Colloquial) Arabic.

2.6.2 Classical Arabic (CA): it is considered as a highly valued and prestigious language because it is regarded as the language of the Holy Quran, in one turn, and in another turn, due to its complex grammar and sophisticated vocabulary. Benrabah (2014, p. 43) describes it as the "liturgical language for all Muslims". Accordingly, this variety of language is rarely used in vernacular interaction, as it is restricted only to the religious domains. Therefore, classical Arabic succeeded in gaining a high status and variety. Classical Arabic has been developed to be a modern and a codified variety that can be used and understood by the majority of Arabs and Maghribs for specific domains (Ennaji, 1991; Fishman, 1972; Versteegh, 2014).

2.6.3 Modern Standard Arabic (MSA)

Unlike the CA, the MSA is less complicated and to a lesser degree, formal. However, it is considered as a high variety just like the standard Arabic (Ferguson, 1959). A standardized language variety that is considerably taught in schools as well as universities. In educational setting, modern standard Arabic is considered as the first language, with a French as a second language, and English as a foreign language. Nevertheless, it is "never used outside the school for any purpose. Pupils are torn between the diglossic reality whereby they "must" use MSA to write and communicate in formal situations" (Kerma, 2018, p.136). He also added that throughout the 19 century, a number of foreign lexicon have been started to be used in the Arabic language and, subsequently, they contributed to the renaissance of this variety of

language. (Kerma, 2018). This has led this variety to be used in several domains such as media, education, and formal speech both in oral and written forms. However, French is still used in some domain, the industrial field for example, as this latter requires a support from France; the thing that necessitates the use of French as language for work purpose (Rouabah, 2020). The adaptation of French I educational as a second and the first foreign in Algeria, particularly in the educational sphere, led speakers/ students to code switch between the two languages

2.6.4 Algerian Arabic (AA)

Another variety of the Algerian languages is the Algerian Arabic. A colloquial language that is used informally in everyday routine communication. It is often used in speaking rather than writing; however, in the Algerian Arabic, we may find some writers include some informal texts (monologue or conversations in their writings). Moreover, colloquial Arabic is used more frequently on social media such as Facebook, twitter, and other social websites. A study conducted by Soumeur et al (2018) shows the use of the Algerian Arabic on Facebook, they claim that Facebookers in their writings/chats use the Algerian Arabic, French, and English. An example of this switch between languages can be seen in this example "**Bonjour, حالك كيف اليوم Brother?**" *Good morning, how are you today brother?* (Soumeur et al., 2018, p.28). This sentence shows a French, Arabic, and English. In fact, the Algerian Arabic is quite miscellaneous than the Arabic language and that is due to the impact of the French, Tamazight (Berber) as well as Turkish languages. . Another study has been conducted by Cotterell et al (2014) on which they investigate the Algerian Arabic-French Code Switching from the comments section in an Algerian newspaper. An example of Algerian Arabic-French code switching was highlighted as follow: "mais les filles ta3na ysedkou n'importe quoi ana hada Facebook jamais cheftou" which means; but our girls believe anything. I have never seen this Facebook before (Cotterell et al., 2014, p.3). Although AA is considered as the mother tongue of the Algerian community, the possibility of integrating more than one language (code switching) is expected as this latter is considered as a natural sociolinguistic phenomenon that occurs in a multilingual speech community, Algeria in this context.

2.6.5 Berber (Tamazight Language)

Consistently with Arabic, Tamazight is both the national and the official language in the Algerian constitution. It is considered as the native language of the local citizens. It is affiliated with the "Hamito-Semitic" languages along with: ancient Egyptian, Semitic, Cushitic, Chadic

and Omotic language. (Grag, 2019). In North Africa, both Morocco and Algeria speak this language. Benrabah (2005) states that the word “Tamazight” refers to the “Berberian language” and the word “Amazigh”, which refers to the Berber culture and means “Freeman or Noble man” were borrowed from “Moroccan Berbophones”.

This Afro-asiatic language consists of four dialects namely: the Kabylean “Takbaylit”, Chaouis and the Tamchek and Mozabites. The Kabylean (Takbylit): it is one of the most Berber dialects that is used much more in the north of the Algerian country by roughly 5 to 7 million people. The number of the speakers may be higher when we count the immigrants of Canada, France, and Europe. It is composed of people speakers living in Boumerdes, Bejaia, Tizi-ouzou, and EL Bouira. “It is a tense-less, head marking language and it is generally presented as a VSO language, with possible VSO variations”. (Mettouchi, A, 2008).

The basic word order in this language variety according is “SVO, which alternates with a SVO order in Topicalized contexts”. (Erhard-Voeltz, 2005).

Shawias (Tachawit): this dialect is mostly spoken in the southeast of Kabylie, more particularly in the Aures region by approximately two million speakers. It is made up of speakers occupying Soukahrass, Batna, and Khenchla.

Mozabites and Tamchek: the former is considered as an important Berber variety due to its linguistic ethnicity The latter dialect encompasses speakers who are from the south of Algeria, mainly Tuareg of the Hoggar and the Tassili regions. It is considered a crucial language variety “because it is considered as the “mother tongue of large group of speakers in Mali and Niger” (Benhattab, 2011, p.37).

2.7 French/ English in Algeria (Frenchification policy)

Gherzouli (2019, p.10) asserted that “French remains a de facto working language in many sectors”. French has influenced Algerians’ speaking and writings more than English does. This is something predicted as the French language was the only compulsory foreign language in primary schools and above all it is the language of the ex-coloniser. According to Benrabah (2018), the outcome of imposing the French language has led to a major proportion of illiteracy among most of the Algerians. Benrabah refers to this policy as a “*Frenchification policy*” that kept Algeria subordinated to France for a while, “L’Algérie Française” had a significant impact on the Algerian official languages, Arabic and Berber. (Daoudi, 2018, P.264). These major impacts have contributed to make French the most used language both in formal

and informal contexts. Moreover, these impacts according to Saadi (2002) has led Algeria to be the second largest francophone country. However, in 1990, there was a trial to eliminate French in administration and replace it with the standard Arabic instead. This idea was encouraged by the ex-president of Algeria, Abdelaziz Bouteflika -1999-2019- who himself supported the idea of bilingualism (Benrabah, 2013). Nevertheless, neglecting French was challenging, as it was not easy to get rid from using it.

2.8 Geographical Context

The chosen context of my study is Kabyle, “the largest homogeneous cultural, linguistic, ethnic community, which is considered the most traditional Berbers in North Africa” (Serier and Kribi, P.5). I chose kabylia students of English because they are engaged in more than two languages, Tamazight, the native language of Kabyle, French, Arabic, Algerian Arabic, and even English. Additionally, I am interested in the linguistic variations in this area, as well as, I have some friends and relatives studying there and I also have a connection with them on Facebook. Each time I was inspired by their use of language and meanwhile I was enthusiastic and eager to know what reasons had lead them to switch codes, is it because due to the social norms, political or politeness ones, do they code switch to maintain symbolic power and why women use of code switching is different than men. Therefore, by way of presenting the chosen context, I will present a brief overview about the Kabylia context.

2.8.1 Geography of Kabylia

Kabylia or, “la Kabylie” in French, is a region situated in the northern of Algeria. Due to its location in Algeria, Kabylia is a part of the Tell Atlas Mountain as well as the edge of the Mediterranean Sea. Roughly, it is located 92km from Algiers, the capital. Kabyle region is considered as the largest ethnic group of the five Berber tribes, approximately with 2 million inhabitants. (Orr, 2013).

Besides, this region encompasses many other administrative provinces such as Tizi-ouzou, which is the capital city of the “Grand Kabyle”, or the Greater Kabylia , Bejaia, some parts of Bouira , Kabylia is a relatively small region with an area of 25257 km² for a population of approximately 7 to 8 million. The map below shows the Kabyle region in Algeria and its main provinces.

Bourdieu describes the Kabyle terrain as an example of “traditional”, “nonliterate” “classless”, and “undifferentiated” society. Bourdieu refers to traditional societies as the personal relations of power in which social practice and agency are both evident and effective in social reproduction. (Danahay, 2003).

Figure 2.1. Geography of Kabylia: The map is taken from Wikimedia Commons

French colonizers were the ones who conserved and coined the term Kabylie to refer mainly to the inhabitants who, at that time, were known as “la kabylie”. Currently, in Algeria, the term “Kabyle” is assigned to the Berber-speaking inhabitants of some specific parts namely: the Tell Atlas, the costal chain that spans from the edge from Mitija plain south-east of Algiers to the Babour mountains, southwest of Jijel. Some other Berber speakers in Algeria are known by other names who used different Berber dialects namely, “Chaouis” and the “Tamchek and Mozabites”. The former this dialect is mostly spoken in the southeast of Kabylie, more particularly in the Aures region by approximately two million speakers, while the latter dialects encompass speakers who are from the south of Algeria.

2.8.2 The region of Tizi Ouzou

As it is mentioned before, the region of Tizi-ouzou referred to the capital city of the great “Grand Kabyle”. It is also called “Thizi Wuzzu”. “Col des genets”, in the French language. Besides, it is considered as one of the densely populated in the Kabyle district. It is noteworthy that the first university in Algeria which opened the department of language and culture is Mouloud Mammeri University in Tizi Ouzou. It is also a multilingual society where the possibility of mixing between languages and varieties may occur. Serier and Kribi (2018) explains that researchers who investigated the languages in this area have acknowledged the fact that speakers in Tizi Ouzou are multilingual in which Tamazight, Arabic, French and English languages are involved.

2.8.3 Language

As far as language is concerned, it is worthwhile to mention that every single language spoken in Algeria, whether it is colloquial or dialectal Arabic, French or Tamazight language with its varieties, has its marked and specific sociocultural position and, subsequently, each position refers back to its historical movements. (Le Roux, 2017). “Taqbaylit” is the first language spoken in Kabyle. In fact Taqbaylit is a dialect that is derived from the Tamazight Berber language. Extensively, the Takbylit, as any Berberian dialect in Algeria, has inserted some of the French and the Arabic languages and dialects in every day conversations. This led the Kabylis to incorporate perpetual code switching. (Maas, 2014).

Kabylia, for instance is considered as one of the Berber region that has “most wholly retained its Berber dialect, Taqbaylit, as mother tongue”. (Mouhleb, 2005, p.7).

2.8.4 Ethnic Relations and Emergence of the Nation

“Les Berbères”, Berbers or the Amazighen, were the earliest inhabitants of the Kabyle region; they were present even before the Arabic in the 7th century. The first conquerors were Phoenicians whose ports established along the Mediterranean. Then, the Romans whose rule lasted six hundred years, made inroads into the North Africa, and thereby they proclaimed a new kingdom, known as Numidia. Concomitant with this was the French control of the nineteenth century who took to besiege the ports built by the Phoenicians, yet their attempts failed. Hence, when they did not succeed in that they invaded Algeria on the 5th of July 1830.

Later on, during the year of 1840-1847, following the French government rules, a large number of French people started to immigrate to Algeria. The main target of the French government at that time was to obliterate the Algerian both culture and identity and replace it with their own. The end of the nineteenth, the French hegemony extended more and more; this is “axiomatic because Algeria occupied an exceptional place in the French empire and that its unique status as a settler colony was the wellspring of its economic and geopolitical strength” (Sessions, 2011, p.8). French started to hold hands and by the end of 1914, French colonialism expanded their operation to the Berber tribes’ lands.

Conclusion

This chapter portrays an overview of the contextual background of the Algerian context, focusing much on the Kabyle region as the main context of this study. The chapter begins by giving an overview of the educational policies in Algeria, emphasising the linguistic practices and challenges. Additionally, it gives a thorough description of the sociolinguistics profile of the languages used in the Algerian context. The chapter then, narrows the scope by discussing the Kabyle context and its history. The next chapter will discuss the literature informed this study.

Chapter Three: Mapping the Literature Review

3.1 Introduction

The previous chapter considered the contextual background of Algeria, focusing on its history, and how it left its linguistic mark on the country. The aim of this chapter is to introduce and explore the literature that pertains to code switching, as a social linguistic phenomenon. I will begin with elucidating the puzzle of code switching by giving different interpretations to it. I will, then, present the history behind code switching and its early foundations. The social contexts, approaches and sociolinguistics dimensions of the code-switching phenomenon will be also discussed. As this study concerns itself in understanding the nature and the policy of this phenomenon, I will present the Bourdieusian lens to critically understand its policy. I close

this chapter by identifying the factors that lead users to switch codes as well as the distinction between code switching from code mixing, and finally I will classify the types of code switching and what characterizes each type because this will help me to point out the use of each type by males and females in chapter 3. Examining the existing body of the related literature supports the main thesis argument that social networking sites, particularly Facebook groups. Section 2.2 reviews the use of Facebook as a learning platform among students. it is argued that the pervasiveness of Facebook as a social networking site contributes positively on students learning outcomes. Being a learning channel where student actively participate and share learning/course related-materials, Facebook is perceived as a symbolic capital for learners. Students can gain access to different learning resources, shared by their peers and/or their institutions. The relationship between Language practices and learning dispositions in relation to gender, in the Facebook group is the focal areas of my study, and the aim is to investigate how these three areas are related using Bourdieu Conceptual Framework. To begin with, a historical overview of the linguistic practices, focusing on the code-switching practices, followed by its definitions and the language practices and learning dispositions of males are different from females in the group.

3.2 Methodology of Searching the Literature

This section sets out to demonstrate the search method that I went through to select my literature. Sources have been retrieved using a set of subsequent key search terms derived from research questions. These include language use in online communication, gender habitus in the online space, online learning in social networking sites. Wider reading and citations help in the identification of the pioneers in this field of study.

The sources I accessed were obtained from sources that are illustrated in the following diagram:

Figure 3.1: Searching Strategies for Literature: Adapted from Davies (2003).

As illustrated in the diagram above, different sources have been used in discussing the literature. For example, the use of databases comprises Taylor and Francis online, Google Scholar, and Sage Online. 'Gray' literature has been also used; this includes previous theses, mainly from Ethos, conference papers, and proceedings. Seminal textbooks have been accessed to identify the theoretical and conceptual framework in relation to Wenger's Community of Practice, Bourdieu's Forms of Capitals, and Entwistle's surface learning approach were accessed.

Particular criteria have been carefully followed to ensure the quality and reliability of papers selected. This includes the selection of high standard related journals, the number of views and citations for each chosen article, and years of publication. To ensure reliability, articles were selected according to their relevance to the subject matter that is of interests, and they were also scrutinised according to the argument(s) they highlighted.

As far as the study design is followed, relevance of the selection of the research design was screened, by looking at how the research design is used to answer the research questions, and how vocabulary and coherence are used to discuss the findings. The reason behind this

was to understand the protocol through which the methodological rigour is established (Hart, 2018).

Sources that were established between the timeframe of 1991 to 2022. The purpose behind selecting this timeframe is that I am integrating some conceptual tools of Bourdieu's (1991) theory. Besides, some of the seminal works on gender and language were written between 1997 and 2003, the thing that leads me to include them in my sources and rely on them in discussing the literature. Furthermore, the search was extended to establish wider perspective, literature have been selected both from the Algerian context, and other Western and Eastern contexts, where studies about language use and practice on Facebook groups have been done.

Since the selection of the literature review focused on specific materials, it therefore considered to be selective. The following figure summarises the three related areas through which the literature has been acknowledged, to answer the research questions.

Figure 3.2 A Synopsis of the Key Topics Covered in the Literature with Influential Authors in the field.

Social Networking Sites, Facebook

Introduction

The immense growth of the internet has shaped the way people communicate and therefore creates a new form of communication. Similarly, by means of communication, social network sites also become exponentially popular, consequently, they create a new digital social network in which people can communicate with others both globally and locally (Orth et al., 2020). Considering the complex nature of the social network sites and the major roles it plays in shaping the digital social interaction, the main aim of this chapter is to introduce several aspects related to social network sites. First, it gives an overview about the social network sites and its definition. Secondly, it discusses how social network site, particularly Facebook is used as a communicative tool and as a social arena platform among its users. Thirdly, this chapter provides an overview about Facebook and then it moves to presents this social network site as a social capital arena by addressing the linguistic practices, with a great emphasis on code switching and politeness strategies used by males and females.

3.2. Definition of the Social Network sites

Social network sites are a recent asynchronous method of communication that allows users to use multiple practices. Some examples of these practices are: interacting with messages and even unsend them at any time when needed, create posts, send them, comments/ reply, edit or delete these replies (Androutsopoulos, 2006; Herring, 2010; Morse, 2003). In like manner, Ellison and Boyd (2013) defined social networking sites as “ a networked communication platform in which users can create profiles, decide who can view their profiles, as it allow them to interact with contents that are shared by their connection. Interestingly, while reading the literature on social networking sites, I found that there is a difference between social network sites and social networking sites. The former relates to what I have illustrated earlier, whereas the latter is concerned with public discourse that are accessed by everyone (Boyd and Ellison, 2008). Although the terms are very often used

interchangeably, I prefer to follow Boyd and Ellison connotation and use the term **network** instead of **networking** because as explained by the two scholars, networking often focuses on initiating relationship among strangers. On the other hand, users in the **network** sites are not aiming to build a networking connection by looking for new other people; instead, they are mainly building a communication with those who belong to their social network. Therefore, in this study, I am using the term social network sites to focus on their scope and features.

3.3. Early foundations of the Social Network Sites

Having defined what is meant by social network site, I will move on to briefly present the historical background behind it. According to Boyd and Ellison (2007), SixDegrees.com was the first social network site, founded by the American entrepreneur Andrew Weinreich in 1997. This site has many features including allowing users to create profiles, establish new acquaintance with others who are available on their social network, send messages and share their thoughts. However, this site does not last long due to its failure in not being able to maintain business. As a result, it turned to be out of service on 2000 (Boyd and Ellison, 2007). Later on, 2001 period marks the beginning of a new social network site known as Ryze.com to facilitate people's business. Yet, as it was the case with the SixDegree site, Ryze.com site was unsuccessful and did not gain that popularity among users either. Subsequently it was followed by other powerful social network sites that such as Friendster in 2002, LinkedIn and my Space 2003, and Facebook in 2004. This is just a brief history of how the social network sites popped out. The next section will discuss its main features.

3.4 Main features of the social network sites

The above section defines the social network sites and differentiates it from the networking site. This section covers its main features. Sangiamchit (2017; p.348) identifies four main features including profiles, connection lists, stream of updates, and multiple modes of communication. Profiles are one of the core characteristic of the social network sites, they are used as a virtual identity for users where they can introduce themselves by inserting their personal pictures as a profile picture, reveal their name, ages, occupation and work place. Ellison and Boyd and Ellison (2013, p.159) define profiles as "spaces for self-presentation and

content distribution". Profiles privacy differs from site to site in a way that each site has its own visibility options. There are some sites, in which its users do not have the option to manage who can view their profiles and their profiles remain open and available for everyone like it is the case in YouTube. Other sites have private features either to set their profiles available for everyone or limited only to the friends who are available in their friend-list. This feature is usually available on some platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, and LinkedIn.

Friend-list or connection list is another feature that characterizes the social network sites. Through this feature, owners can establish their own network by requesting or confirming their friend requests. It is up to the users to delete the requests from other networkers whom they do not want to have a connection with as they have the right to minimize their network and unfriend with others whom they are already friends with them. Nevertheless, this feature does not only control those who can access your profile but also those who can see the content you share. When the user's friends or the users themselves post and update any content on their profiles, they both can react, comment to each other's' posts. Doing this will build a strong connection between both parties.

Apart from these two features discussed above, streams of update along with the multiple modes of communication are another content-related feature of the social network sites. I chose to combine these two features as they are related to each other. Through the stream of updates feature, multiple ways of communication can appear. This involves sharing various media along with multimodal features including texts, photos and images (Ellison and Boyd, 2013). Thereby, users via these options can post and interact in many ways. For instance, they can post a photo, comment on it in a written post. Alternatively, they can upload a picture that includes texts on it; this is known as internet memes. Likewise, social network sites serve as a social terrain for social interaction, language use and practices. Among these different network sites, Facebook gains attraction and consequently becomes one of the most popular platforms worldwide (Orth, 2020), with more than 2.6 billion monthly active users (Statista, 2021). Therefore, this thesis focuses on Facebook and its use among students. The coming section will introduce to the reader the concept of Facebook. It describes its functionality, structure, and how this platform can be seen as an exemplar of the multilingual practices

3.5.1 Facebook

As discussed earlier, Facebook is duly defined as the most popular social network site. As a February 2021, it has an average of 1, 88 billion active users per day with an increase of 8% year over year (PRNewswire, 2021). According to Aspapacharissi and (Eldh, Årestedt and Berterö, 2020)Yuan (2011, p.91), Facebook is considered as “the global online giant”. It is popularity appeals on the social benefits and the multimodal features it offers to its users (see section (features of FB) boundaries. It was initially created for college students; however, later on it expanded to cover all people, from different ages and occupations (Teck Terms Dictionary, 2010). Facebook seeks to give people the power to share and make the world more open and connected (Facebook, 2013a).

Generally, Facebook is used mainly for social purposes (Madge et al., 2009). However nowadays limiting Facebook merely to its social functions conceals the essence of the other multiple functions it provides and meanwhile it neglects the origin of Facebook, because Facebook was mainly created for students to facilitate their learning process through sharing academic stuff. This is in line with May et al. (2015, p.15) whom they claim that “today, most university students have seen to make use of Facebook as the intermediary too for them to spread words to their circles as well as their lecturers using the wall post feature on Facebook”. In Algeria, Facebook tend to be the most popular social network site. Statistics according to NapoleonCat (2021) revealed that the number of Facebook users in Algeria, in March 2021, has an average of 26 300 000 which counts for 59, 3% of the entire population, with a large group of users between the age of 25 to 34. These statistics serve as a sound evidence that Facebook is the predominant platform among Algerians as well as they demonstrate that adults are the ones who create a greater proportion of the Facebook use. This group of people (adults) are chosen to be a sample of this study.

3.5.2 History of Facebook at a glance

Due to its popularity over the social network sites, Facebook became recognizable by the majority of people. Yet, only few of them have an idea about how this platform begins to evolve. Therefore, this section will present the reader its earliest foundations. Facebook was founded by a second year Harvard student, Mark Elliot Zuckerberg in February 20014; along

with his co-founder classmates Dustin Moskovitz, Chris Hughes, and Eduardo Saverin (Kirkpatrick, 2011; Freberg, 2019). Initially, membership was only available for students who belong to Harvard University. Later on in 2005, Facebook became gradually opened for other students across overseas universities, college and high school, in order to stay in contact. Then, in 2006, Facebook enables registration access to everyone aged 13 and older (Kirkpatrick, 2011). In 2007, the number of active monthly users have reached more than 20 million as Facebook updates and creates new services such as businesses, organizations and even education. In Facebook setting, these services are known as Facebook pages or groups. The difference between pages and groups is that the former is mostly designed for public, on the other hand, groups tend to be private. This study sheds the light on Facebook groups that are mainly related to sharing academic staff. To be more precise, this study focuses on one of the student group where students share lecturer, thoughts, transferring initiative and ask questions. As an accepted social network, Facebook can be used as a learning and educational tool where users can share educational and learning content (Tess, 2013; Cortijo and Javed, 2014).

3. 5.3 Facebook groups

Facebook consists of a toolkit of different features (Smock et al, 2011). Facebook group is one of the features that are mostly common in the social network sites (*see section 4.4.*). This is why I prefer to focus on one possible feature, which this study focuses on most, the Facebook group feature. After seven months of the creation of Facebook, the Facebook group feature was launched in 2010 and over 50 million Facebook group was created (Ta, 2011). Facebook groups are created by one person, instead of forcing everyone to build his own friend list, and every member in the group can post on it. Prescott (2016) claims that “Facebook groups enable students to communicate to a smaller audience; these groups can be quickly created with their access limited to particular cohort of people” (p.37). This way, creating a Facebook group, that is dedicated to educational purposes, permits students to share lectures. Additionally, Facebook groups affords peer supports, collaborative learning and interaction (through the comment section) in relation to their courses and module related insights and/or questions (Prescott, 2013). Nowadays, with the domination of the covid-19 era, students use this opportunity to transfer lectures and assignments through the social network sites

(Susanto et al.; 2021). Moreover, in her study on the use of the Facebook group feature, during the Covid-19 pandemic, Avila and Cabrera (2020) argues that “Facebook is considered the best option since the majority of students are more active in social media platforms during the quarantine periods (p.1864). In light with these lines, I share the same argument, as I am myself a PhD student who has gained and learnt a lot from the Facebook page groups. In this section, I discussed one of the most beneficial Facebook features that facilitates the learning process in the area of education. The coming section will explore the reasons behind choosing Facebook as a core setting for this study.

3.6 Facebook as a research topic

In addition to its popularity and its fastest growth on the social utility, Facebook becomes a topic that needs to be investigated, observed, and documented. Wilson (2012) elucidates that the utility of Facebook, among scholars, warrants it to be an effective platform to observe human natural social behaviour in a natural setting. These online social behaviours include practices such as generational, gender and culture (Dumova and Fiordo, 2012). In addition to these social arenas, linguistic practices such as code switching and gender differences have been a study of interest on Facebook (Halim and Maros, 2014; Crowston and Williams, 2000; Herring, 2013; Androutsopoulos, 2014b). Since the online social interaction marks the absence of face-to-face communication, Facebook users employ a variety of linguistic devices in order to protect their faces from any sort of threats (Franch and Conejois-Blitvich, 2018; Danet, 2013). This is known as im/politeness strategies, another social field that this study covers (*see chapter 5*).

Posting updates, commenting, and connecting to others on Facebook facilitates the process of observing the data and therefore, it provides social scientists scholars to study the human attitudes in a natural setting (Wilson et al., 2012). In this study, I am focusing on the aforementioned social behaviour that I mentioned previously (*code switching, gender, and politeness*). Researchers on online interaction such as Bell et al., (2014) claim that despite the language difference and style, students are aware of the linguistic repertoire used by other students. As well as they are aware that humour, as a positive politeness strategy functions as a social practice in an interaction (Lantz- Andersson, 2018).

Along with these lines, I argue that the social media medium has introduced a new style of communication, this mode of communication therefore shapes users' both social practices and linguistic practices as well as it opens the door to highlight the differences between men and women social/linguistic practices (*see chapter 3*).

3.7. Facebook as a social capital

The advent of Facebook as a popular communicative social network platform shapes human lives, interaction, and behaviours. According to (Burke and Karut, 2014) Social network sites, including Facebook, due to the multi functions and the different features, have a significant impact on agents, herein Facebook users. Social capital according to Bourdieu and Wacquant (1992, p. 14) refers to the “sum of the resources, actual or virtual, that accrue to an individual or a group by virtue of possessing a durable network of more or less institutionalized relationships of mutual acquaintance and recognition”. In this study, resources can refer to the linguistic repertoire a user possesses. It can be figured out through the online practices that users use to communicate to the ones who are available on their social network. Usually, social capital is positive facet in human interaction with other participants (Helliwell and Putnam, 2004). Subsequently, this may lead to a higher frequency of using positive politeness strategies. Another interesting about the social capital is that its nature is fluid and flexible as it differs according to the situation and the interlocutors per se. Coupled with these lines, Ellison et al., (2007, p.1145) maintains that “for individuals, social capital allows a person to draw on resources from other members of the networks to which s/he belongs. Similarly, Ellison, Steinfield and Lampe (2007) present a study focusing on exploring Facebook as an environment that used for learning/ educational purposes. Participants were 800 American undergraduate students and they were approached through email survey. The main aim of the study was to identify the relationship between students' use of Facebook and the prolongation of their social capital. The results revealed that the primary aim behind using Facebook among undergraduate students is to maintain their existing offline network relationship with other acquaintances. The study suggested that the recurrent use of Facebook helps students who face a lower self- esteem to develop and gain their social capital. Thus, gaining a social capital will in its turn help them to engage in an interaction with their acquaintances who are either students or teachers. When the process of interaction

starts, students will immediately start learning as this latter according to Vygotsky (1978) starts in accordance with the social interaction.

3.8. Previous studies on Code switching on Facebook

Hitherto the bulk of studies on computer mediated communication witnessed a shift from focusing on quantifying the use of languages to exploring the multilingual practices including individuals' choices of languages and the factors behind it within their online context ((Leppänen and Peuronen, 2012). In their erudite work, Falk (2013) and Tsiplako (2009) elucidate that code switching is the joint online practice that happens on different social network sites, particularly Facebook. As I stated earlier in section (4.5), Facebook is used for different purposes, establishing connections, updating news, sharing information or enhance the interaction between users. Maros and Halim (2014) claim that code switching is one the social phenomenon that serves to maintain and facilitate the interaction as it is a natural phenomenon particularly among bi/multilinguals individuals who belong to a multilingual environment. Therefore, interaction on Facebook is considered as multilingual (Moradi, 2014). Participants in this study have a multilingual background hence they are considered as multilingual users.

A robust body of studies continues to grow in relation to online written communication, focusing on Facebook as a social network site and code switching as both a natural communicative and social phenomenon among multilingual communities. For instance, Ting and Kai-Liang Yeo (2019) focuses on examining the use of language among Malaysian's multilingual students on Facebook through their wallposts, as well as exploring the code-switching functions. The study analyzed 24 Facebook wallposts written by students and it shows that English language was the most code-switched language used among students on Facebook. They concluded that different code-switching functions on Facebook were employed such as building rapport, strengthening a comment, and interjections.

Maros and Halim (2014) conducted another study, in which they investigate the occurrence of the code-switching phenomenon on Facebook. Collecting the data took one-year analysis of 439 Facebook updates written by five Malay bilingual teachers of English. The analysis focuses only in the written posts that contain a switching between codes. This study will

follow the same procedure, which is to analyze posts and comments that include code-switching practices written by students. The study almost reveals the same results of Kai-Liang Yeo (2019) studies, as code switching in online communication has many functions including clarification, showing emotions, and emphasis.

In Algeria, a study conducted by Achili (2019), shares some similar variables to the current study as it focuses on gender differentiation and code switching among 4th year multilingual students of English in Algeria. Nevertheless, the research setting of this study was in SMS messaging. Achili analyzed 120 messages to identify the code switching practices in their messages. The result revealed that code switching tends to be a feminine phenomenon as females tend to code switch more than males. Concerning the language use, data revealed that English was the most code-switched language among SMS users.

In another study of code switching in relation to Facebook among students, Younes and Mimouna (2019) in which they investigate how students of English, living in Oran, use code switching on Facebook. Data was quantitatively analyzed from 75 corpus of Facebook updates using a questionnaire. Results revealed that a greater proportion of students do implement code switching in their online writing for communication and meaning negotiation. Nevertheless, it suggests that code switching is not merely used for communicative purposes, but also for academic activities including project works, assignments, files, and lectures' notes.

The above studies prove that code switching is not restricted to spoken discourses merely, but rather it is also related to written discourses, online discourses in this case. However, some lacunae need to be covered. For instance, the majority of studies tackle code-switching phenomenon on Facebook, focusing mainly on its types. The contribution of this study lies in understanding the online practices of code switching in terms of the linguistic habitus, linguistic im/politeness strategies and gender variations among multilingual students. Research in this concern is very limited. In Algeria, more specifically, in the Kabyle context, no studies have been studying the nature of code switching in relation to these perspectives. It is true that there are studies in Algeria and Kabyle that dealt with code switching and gender, but as I stated earlier, none of them have looked at this phenomenon from its essence; I mean its nature. Additionally, most of the previous studies, despite of the fact that

they study code switching on online live setting, Facebook, they did not study in its live occurrence. Hence, this current study attempts to study the code-switching practices using a netnographic approach to capture “live” data on its “live” occurrence.

3.9. Motives for choosing Facebook: from a narrative personal desire to an existing literature

As I stated earlier in the background chapter, my motivation behind choosing Facebook as a research setting is that from the time I created a Facebook profile, I was able to notice my friends', who most of them are students, expressing their thoughts using a variety of languages within the same stretch of their wall posts, comments and even their chats. This boosts my curiosity to dig in deeply and examine the core elements of their online linguistic practices, including their code-switching practices and how these practices differ from males to females in terms of the choice of codes and the im/politeness strategies they employ. During my Bachelor and Master degree, I had some friends who came from other provinces to study in a university that is far from their home. To help them stay connected and updated, especially during the holiday period, one of the students created a Facebook group and the majority of the cohort were added and became members of the group. Hence, every student, who is a member of this group had the right to share/ post, comment any Information, queries, questions, and even lessons or files. Like such, Facebook helps us to stay connected and, at the same time, updated about any news that are related to their courses. Moreover, the majority of the Algerian students become easily familiar with the platform due to its uncomplicated features and popularity (Sarnou, 2021). This also indicates that students prefer Facebook over the other academic platforms such as MOODLES because on Facebook they found a sense of liberty and informality that are not there in the formal educational platforms.

Moreover, apart from the idea that Facebook is consider as the popular phenomenal social network around the globe (Schreiber, 2015; Nichols, 2020; Orth et al., 2020; Golder et al., 2007; Mazman and Usluel, 2010), it has been also proven to be starkly used by students as a high proportion of Facebook members are students (Ellison, 2008; Stutzman, 2006). In Algeria, it gains an enormous success among users (Abainia, 2020) and it quickly becomes a comfort shelter for students from different fields and levels because it supports and boosts

their learning outcomes (Boumarafi, 2015). Henceforth, based on the aforementioned claims, I chose Facebook over other social network sites because the majority of students, particularly university students, use it. Nowadays Facebook, unlike before, is not tied only to communication for socialization, but rather it is also linked to academic purposes, including “students self-reliance in learning through inquiry and sharing” (Boumarafi, 2015, p. 33). This section highlights the major motives of choosing Facebook as a research setting the next section discussed its role as an educational platform.

3.10. Facebook in Education

As the use of social network sites is evolving and for a wired generation that became open-minded and immersed in such growth, looking at these sites to be implemented in the educational setting is appropriate. The ubiquitous of Facebook invites scholars to conduct research from many fields. An example of these fields is education (Aydin, 2012; Tess, 2013), sociology, marketing and sociology, law, and social sciences (Wilson et al., 2012). In this study the focus is more or less on Facebook and its use in the educational setting with a great emphasis on the Algerian context. Nevertheless, it is important to mention that there were a paucity of studies in relation to Facebook as an educational tool (Vrocharidou and Efthymiou, 2012). The earliest study that highlights the use of Facebook for educational purposes was in 2007 by Ellison et al (2007). Although Ellison et al study of 2007 was mainly concerned in Facebook and its relation with the social capital, their results revealed the crucial role of Facebook in education in terms of aiding students who have a poor self-esteem to enhance their social capital network (*see section, 4.9*).

An abundance of research in relation to Facebook and education has been marked from the 2007 and onwards. For instance, research by Madge et al., (2009) and Prescott et al., (2013) concluded that students use Facebook to share courses content with their peers. Additionally, Bosch (2009) claims that using Facebook as both teaching and learning tool has been helpful in enabling both teachers and students to share their resources quickly in an easier way. Prescott et al., (2015) conducted a qualitative study to gain insights about academic staff experiences in relation to Facebook as an educational tool. All the chosen participants had a Facebook group in which they share their courses and all of them have agreed that Facebook serves as a helpful tool to communicate and share content with students.

In recent times, educational institutions started to embrace the digital world and be creative in approaching students/ teachers who use any sort of the social network sites (Boumarafi, 2015; Paladan, 2019). Studies that are associated with the use of social media in the learning and teaching sphere confirms that there is a high potential of using social network sites among students not only for communicative functions but also for learning purposes. For instance, Tiryakioglu and Erzurum (2011) maintain that Facebook is an educational means based on a survey, which advocates that the majority of students have a Facebook account and they used it to communicate between their classmates through a Facebook academic group page. A similar study conducted by Al Munitairi (2013) assessed the use of Facebook by both students and teachers in the educational setting, particularly at Kuwait University, revealed that Facebook contributes to the enrichment of their educational performance in a way that facilitates the interaction and speeds the information through sharing content. Having explained the setting of this study, the next chapter explains the linguistic dimensions of this research

3.10.1 The Double-Edged Nature of Implementing Facebook as a Learning Platform

After discussing the literature pertaining to the use of Facebook as an educational resource, it seems pertinent to provide some critical discussion concerning its merits, and potential challenges. Thus, this section discusses the affordances and inherent limitations of Facebook groups, being used as an educational platform among students.

Facebook offers several affordances that make it an attractive option for educational purposes. Its ability to widen the learning context allows for interactions beyond the classroom, enabling a blend of formal and informal learning environments (Manca and Ranieri, 2013). By facilitating resource mixing and hybridising expertise, Facebook connects students with diverse knowledge sources, fostering a richer and more collaborative learning experience.

As noted by Said *et al.* (2014) and Wang *et al.* (2012), Facebook's functionality supports its use as a learning management system, providing tools for announcements, resource sharing, and discussions. These features make it a valuable platform for both synchronous and

asynchronous learning, accommodating students' varied schedules and learning paces. (see section 1.5). Moreover, its user-friendly interface and ubiquity enhance its attractiveness among students, with studies indicating a generally positive perception of its role in learning (Arouri, 2015).

One significant limitation of Facebook is related to privacy and security concerns. Facebook has faced criticism for its data privacy practices, raising concerns about how student data might be handled when the platform is used for academic purposes. Students and educators may feel uneasy about sharing personal information or engaging in sensitive discussions on a platform that may not provide robust safeguards against data breaches (Becker and Pousttchi, 2012). Such apprehensions can undermine trust and limit active participation, a critical component of collaborative learning.

Another issue is the blurring of boundaries between personal and academic spaces. Facebook is primarily a social platform, and using it for education may inadvertently lead to distractions. Notifications from non-educational activities, such as social interactions or advertisements, can interrupt the learning process. This overlapping of personal and professional spheres might also make some students uncomfortable, as they may prefer to keep their academic and social lives separate (Madge et al., 2009).

The platform's informal nature can also present challenges in maintaining academic rigor. Discussions on Facebook may lack the depth and focus typically required in formal educational settings. While the platform fosters casual interaction, this informality might detract from the critical and analytical skills essential in higher education (Selwyn, 2009). Moreover, Facebook does not inherently provide the structured frameworks often necessary for organizing complex academic tasks, such as project management or in-depth research collaboration.

Accessibility and inclusivity are additional areas of concern. While Facebook is widely used, not all students have equal access to reliable internet connections or devices, creating disparities in participation. Additionally, students who are less familiar with digital technologies or have limited proficiency in using Facebook's features might struggle to

engage fully. These barriers can exacerbate inequalities and limit the platform's effectiveness in supporting diverse student populations.

In summary, while Facebook offers unique affordances for educational use, it is not without its limitations. Privacy concerns, distractions, informality, accessibility issues, and management challenges underscore the need for caution and critical assessment when integrating Facebook into educational practices. Educators must carefully weigh these limitations against the platform's benefits, ensuring that its use aligns with pedagogical goals and supports equitable, effective learning.

3.11 Code Switching

In most cases, multilingual speakers are those who are appropriately inclined to use more than their mother tongue language, mainly two languages or dialects. The belonging to a multilingual or a bilingual speech community may lead the users of a particular language to alternate and shift codes. In the sociolinguistic settings, this phenomenon is known as “code-switching”. In the Kabyle, the most homogenous and linguistic community in Algeria, speakers have a full command of different language repertoire and this will lead them to move from one language and from one variety to another. Consequently, code switching will be marked.

Among the contact phenomena that gain scholarly interests in the sociolinguistics settings is code switching (hereafter, CS). Studies on social sciences, particularly linguistics (Poplack, 1980; Grosjean, 1982; Appel and Muysken, 1987) and in sociolinguistics disciplines, (Blom and Gumperz, 1972; Auer, 1988; Myers and Scotton, 1998) have covered the term code switching and made some attempts to define it through its various definitions and interpretations in the literature. Moreover, sociologists have also sought to distinguish this concept from other “similar” terminological terms such as code mixing, and borrowing. That is why different approaches to address code switching have risen widely.

Before going any further with code switching, discussing some key concepts and terminology of this field must be addressed and therefore clearly explored.

3.11.1. A code

Researchers in the sociolinguistics field used different terms to refer to code switching. A researcher in the field, when reading others' studies on code switching, may come across similar terms such as code mixing, code alternation/ insertation, and borrowing. Hence, I found it very crucial to "decode" the term to the reader as well as to differentiate code switching from other similar terms.

Sociolinguistically speaking, a code refers to the language or the variety an individual uses while communicating with other members in a particular speech community. Gul (2003, p.6) posits that Stockwell defines a code as "a symbol of nationalism that issued by people to speak or to communicate in a particular language, or dialect, or register, or accent, or style on different occasions and for different purpose". In fact, choosing a code is governed by many factors including the context, the setting, and the participants themselves i.e. the addressors and the addressees. (Holmes, 2001). Some researchers in the field refer to the notion "code" as "language" and they used the two terms interchangeably (Muysken, 2000). Others like (Gafaranga and Torras, 2001) have used the terms distinguishably. Through my discussion, I will be following Muysken's path and using the term code switching interchangeably with language.

3.11.2 Code Switching

Various scholars have been investigated code switching phenomenon and attempted to define it. This linguistic phenomenon is perceived by the majority of laypeople as the practice of using two languages. However, in the sociolinguistics settings, by taking it in its simpler form of meaning, code switching (also code-switching, CS) is the use of two language varieties, or more, within **a single utterance**. In her approach to CS, Woolard (2004), as cited in Sharaf El Din (2014) have expressed a similar view in which she asserts that code CS refers to "the investigation of an individual's use of two or more language varieties in the same speech event or exchange". (p. 79).

Another recent definition used by Nordquist (2019) who defines code switching as "the practice of moving back and forth between two languages or between two dialects or registers of the same language at one time."(n.p). similarly, *Winford* (2013) adds that code

switching is a process of alternating two divergent languages or dialects within the same context. The term can also be defined as “the alternation of languages within a conversation” (Matras 2009, p.101). A conversation does not only address the verbal or spoken communicative skills, but rather, it also involves a non-verbal or written contexts such as in computer mediated communication (CMS) and social networking sites (SNSs). (Sukyani, Didi, 2012).

It is of a great interest to elucidate the fact that code switching phenomenon is not exclusive merely to bilinguals; even monolinguals can shift and alternate from one register and from one dialect to another, but with using one language. Among linguists, this is referred to as “**style shifting**”. Style shifting according to Mayerhoff (2006) is “variation in an individual’s speech correlating with differences in addressee, social context, personal goals or externally communicative imposed tasks” (p. 28). Putting it simply style-shifting is, generally, the outcomes of a code variation within one language.

Although there have been some delusion and misapprehension about language alternation and code switching among laypeople and professionals, who perceive the phenomenon as a sign of language deficiency and competence, it is evident from the above definitions that code switching is a normal natural phenomenon that occur in divergent settings. Especially among bilinguals and multilinguals as it requires a high level of grammatical, pragmatic, and syntactic competences. In this regard, Bullock and Torribio (2009) add that code switching “reflects the ability of the speaker to appropriately select a language while obeying socially and culturally imposed constraints”. (P.242). so, the spoken or the written language connects with the society and it is abided by the sociocultural practices.

3.12. Distinguishing code switching from borrowing

Pragmatically, both CS and borrowing (B) are two linguistic-contact phenomena that involve the use of two languages into contact with each other, and they can take the written and the spoken form. However, semantically, both terms differ the thing that leads scholars to investigate the distinction between these language-contact phenomena. Distinguishing the two terms will help to understand how language come into contact.

While reviewing the literature on CS and borrowing (B), many scholars in the field have made distinctions between the two similar notions and successfully managed in teasing the term CS

apart from borrowing. Grosjean (2010), Weinreich (1953) were among the first scholars who attempted to distinguish the two terms, though Poplack and Meechan (1998, p127) maintain that the problem of distinguishing the two terms is “at the heart of a fundamental disagreement among researchers about data”. This debate lasts even twenty years later.

Drawing on Gingras’ (1974) attempt to distinguish between CS and borrowing (B), he suggests that the term CS usually takes the forms of utterances, phrases, and statements, and words while B inserting a single word can be considered as borrowing. However, one needs to differentiate by a single word insertion, whether it is considered as a CS or B. In this regard, Carol Myres-Scotton (1993) maintain that it is hard to assume that there is no applicable criterion for considering a single word insertion as CS and not B. Yet in her 2006, Carol refers to borrowing as “the process when one language takes in words from another language” (p. 209). Correlatively, there is “a doubt in the classification of other-language material as either switches or borrowings arises particularly in relation to single words, whereas the longer the stretch of other-language material the easier it generally is to identify that material as a switch” (Deuchar, 2020, p. 2)

Borrowing according to Grosjean (2010) is characterized by integrating words that are phonologically and morpho-syntactically integrated to the base language whereas CS is marked by the alternation from one language to another. Additionally, Grosjean (2010) adds another useful distinction between the two terms in which he presents CS as “involving two grammars (an alternation between language A and language B) whereas borrowing only involves one” (p58). In a nutshell, the figure below clearly demonstrates Grosjeans’ claims:

Figure 3.3: The difference between code-switching and borrowing (Grosjean, 2010, 58)

Another point I would like to highlight is that some scholars in the field of linguistics, sociolinguistics in particular, such as Auer refer to CS by using the term “code alternation”.

However, this claim has not been highly supported nor recommended among other researchers. For instances, the term alternation according to Muysken (1995), as cited in Bochorishvili (2019, p17) “mainly deals with single lexical items that are transferred from one language to another. Such instances will be referred to as CS in this study”.

3.12.1. Types of Code Switching

Since the structural social capital dimension of code switching is concerned, it is of a great interest to identify the major types CS because discussing them will help the researcher to categorize data, later on, into segments. Though the research looks at code switching from the sociolinguistics lens not a grammatical one. Poplack (1980) divided code switching into three major types namely: intra- sentential switching, intra sentential, and tag switching.

Figure3.4. The type of code-switching and the degree of switching in them (Poplack, 1980. P.615).

As it is illustrated above, in Poplack’s categorization of code switching, inter-sentential switching occurs outside the clause boundaries and it requires more competence in L2.Tag switching in the other hand requires a minimal bilingual proficiency in L2. It is to “insert” a tag element from one language into another discourse that is different from the other language. For example. Unlike the two aforementioned switching types, intra- sentential code switching involves a high level of grammatical competency between two codes (L1 and L2) and it occurs at the clause and sentence level. This kind of switching is also known as “code mixing”. Poplack (1980) also highlights that all of three types of switching codes can occur all together in one discourse. (p.123).

However, other scholars in the field divided code switching into two types mainly inter-switching and intra switching; they eliminate the “tag switching” because this latter is quite similar to intra-sentential switching type as they both require drawing from one linguistic

code to another. Boztec (2005) confirms that by saying “tag-switching can be grouped with intra-sentential switching because both involve inserting words from one language into another”.

3.13. Sociocultural and anthropological dimensions of code switching

Wider studies have been adopted to understand code switching phenomenon and its nature. Twenty years ago, an interest of studying language contact phenomena and bilingualism came out. During the 1950's and 1960's, the term “code switching” started to be revealed in the linguistics settings. After its emergence, several research and publications sought to tackle the phenomenon. “A search of the Linguistics and Language Behaviour Abstracts database in 2005 shows more than 1,800 articles on the subject published in virtually every branch of linguistics”. (Nilep, 2006, p.1). Consequently, this led to different interpretations and different perspectives within the sub-linguistics fields, syntactic approaches (Poplack 1979 -1981), sociolinguistic ones (Blom and Gumperz, 1972; Myers and Scotton, 1998; McKay, 2005), cognitive-pragmatic perspectives, theories of politeness (Lakoff1973, Brown & Levinson 1987, sociocultural approach and the “brought along” approach (Auer,1992; Bourdieu 1991). However, as this study concerns itself in understanding and analysing the nature of code switching as a sociocultural phenomenon and its politeness strategies, I consider it necessary to focus only on two main perspectives which are the sociocultural and politeness perspectives, rather than its structural and grammatical dimensions. Limiting code switching in its structural features and grammar is insatiable and insufficient to fully describe and analyse the nature of code switching as a social phenomenon. Auer (1984) agreed in the same point in which he elucidates that “code switching is not merely a matter of linguistics well formedness; it also has communicative content left unexplained by the analysis of syntactic surface constraints” (p.2). In other words, studying CS in relation to grammatical production, neglecting its practice of moving back and forth while conversing and interacting may gain a little bit of interest in the study of linguistics and language contact. In that vein, in his book. *The Status of Linguistics as a Science*, Sapir (1929, p. 213) refers to that as ““a tradition that threatens to become scholastic when not vitalized by interests which lie beyond the formal interest in language itself”. Additionally, the French anthropologist and sociologist Pierre

Bourdieu was interested in language and linguistics due to his ethnographic study in Algeria, Kabyle. Bourdieu (1991b) himself rejected the traditional approach of language studies, following the aim of this study, my research is positioned and related to the sociocultural linguistic field. Sociocultural linguistics refers to “the intersection of language, culture, and society. This term encompasses the disciplinary subfields of sociolinguistics, linguistic, anthropology, socially oriented forms of discourse analysis (such as conversation analysis and critical discourse analysis), and linguistically oriented social-psychology, among others” (Hall and Bucholtz, 2010, p.18). .

3.14 Gender variation and Code-Switching

Introduction

The main thrust of this chapter is to present and explore the previous published and analysed literature regarding the gender variation on the level of the use of code switching among males and females’ students on Facebook. By gender variation, I do not mean the biological attributes of both genders, yet the language (s) each gender uses while communicating on Facebook. A whole chapter will be devoted to discuss literature on the social media platform, Facebook. The review will consider, mainly, two broader theoretical disciplines namely: gender and language variation (CS). Before explaining the bound between these two disciplines, I will, first of all, review each topic separately, starting with identifying a pertinent terminology of each field. Then, a review of the approaches related to gender issues. Some of these approaches is incorporated with the French sociologist, Pierre Bourdieu; (feminism and gender habitus) will be discussed. Furthers more. Male and female Kabylean students’ use of language will be also analysed.

3.14.1. On the emergence of Gender studies

As the current study looks at how language is used by each gender in online communication, I am interested in a wide range of gender studies and language variation, mainly code switching, used by Kabylean postgraduate students while posting and commenting, on the social networking site, Facebook to determine if this phenomenon is a masculine or a feminine one. Hence, this chapter outlines my perspective on what is meant by gender, focuses on reviewing the existing literature and theories on gender and language, and how

these theories contribute to my thesis. Moreover, within this chapter, I address the concept of gender as a powerful concept, taking into account the Bourdieusian lens.

Cameron (2020) writes that the main focus in the recent decades was on social identity and performance. One of the outcomes of this focus has paved the way to central issues of power and gender relations. In 1972, the University of California, Berkeley, marks the year of establishing the modern field of language and gender by one of the departments' staff, the linguist Robin Lakoff who wrote her first essay about "Language and Woman's Place". However, Lakoff was not the only pioneer of the field; there were many other linguists and anthropologists such as McConnell-Ginette, Zimmerman, and Tannen. (Cameron, 2020; Maheshwari, 2020, Tannen, 1993).

3.14.1.1 Gender

Gender is one of the key social factors that have been studied widely in the discipline of sociolinguistics, anthropology, and socioculture (Nicola, 2018; Upton, 2012). In a similar way, Ridgeway (2009, p.145) states that "gender is a primary cultural frame for coordinating behaviour and organising social relations". To put it simple, gender is associated with agents' behaviour that are socially constructed by society. Bradley (2013) explains that "being a social construct, gender is not something fixed, but something that varies according to time, place, and culture" (p. 4). Ontologically, the concept of gender used to be associated merely with the biological factors of individuals and a term that distinguishes the two sexes (males and females). However, epistemologically speaking, and with the rise of many disciplines, gender becomes "ultimately concerned with language in a social context, shaped by discursive and socio-cultural practices" (Litosseliti, 2013. p.1). However, many theories used different interpretations to define the notion of gender in many fields. For instance, (Fenstermaker and West, 2002, pp.26-30) sum up each theory with its own perspective. In the Moroccan culture as "the strength that comes from the fact that it is channelled through powerful cultural components that strongly regulate the lives of Moroccan men and women through powerful social institutions". These institutions govern the use of languages among individuals and gender perception and they are characterized by eight (8) features namely: "history, (ii) geography, (iii) Islam, (iv) orality, (v) multilingualism, (vi) social organization, (vii) economic status, and (viii) political system". (Sadiqi, 2003, p.17).

Similarly, since Algeria is the largest gate in the Arab continents and Mediterranean basin as a whole, it attracted many tribes such as the Phoenicians, Romans, Arabs, Vandals, Spanish Berber, and French, and, linguistically, it was a “pluralistic country” (Benrabah, 2007, p. 229). Therefore, it is worthwhile to mention that both the cultural and the linguistics background of Algeria influence the way its members use the language. Interestingly, with regard to the Algerian context and its language use, particularly within the 7th and the beginning of the 8th century, Algeria witnessed unprecedented historical, social, and economic changes, which have led to both linguistics, and gender issues changes.

The biological theory restricted gender to “sex; that is to say, gender according to this theory relates to individual sexual developments at puberty as well as males and females organs. In fact, this claim limits gender to sex and thereby gender equals sex. Meyerhoff (2006) distinguishes the two terms by saying that “sex” refers to the biological attributes of men and women whereas gender refers to the social constructed roles of individuals. In its turn, **the** linguistic theory reduces the term gender to its linguistic/ grammatical category; masculine and feminine nouns and pronouns. In addition, social constructivism theorists took to define gender as act of “doing rather than being”. In other words, gender refers to the attitude and the performance of individual in a particular cultural setting. In this vein “gendered identities are internationally achieved” Kendall and Tannen (2001, pp.556-557) this means that gender is manifested through agents’ role and acts in a society and therefore it is constructed in their identities when performing. Within these different theories, the key interpretation I draw upon in the coming section is the social constructivism view along with Bourdieu ‘s interpretation of gender. Within the Algerian context, it is hardly possible to separate gender from its historical, cultural, as well its linguistics or language heritage. Males and females use of certain linguistic varieties is controlled by the cultural structure of the society.

3.14.1.2. Gender Issues in Algeria

Every speech community has its social and cultural structures in which gender position is determined. Similarly, each society is characterized by its unique gender structure, which shapes individuals’ identities, personalities, and choices they make. (Risman, 2018). Therefore, since gender is constructed by these social structures, it is viewed as dynamic,

complex and fluid. (Widodo and Elyas, 2020; Cameron, 2005), the thing that makes it “a potential site of struggle” (Sauntson, 2012, p. 5).

In Algeria, when it comes to languages, women are quite aware about the social norms that the society imposes on them; these norms are the ones that shape their use of languages. Therefore, one can say that the use of languages among women is somehow conscious. Trudgill (1972) coined that type of consciousness as “a status consciousness”, because society that shapes their social importance and acceptance of their linguistic choice. That is to say, it is the society that enforces the linguistic norms on women. Additionally, women, in the Algerian society, are raised from an early age to be somewhat polite, the fact that leads them to use more prestigious forms of language especially when they include the French language in their speech, whereas men tend to use more vernacular forms (Rabahi, 2013; Trudgill, 1972; Labov, 1966, 1990). Surprisingly, Eckfert (1989) points out that this must not be called prestige, but power. Based on Eckfert contribution, my argument in that is women, who are denuded in their status from accessing power, need to enact their membership of the community. Their membership level is demonstrated through the symbolic capital that is available in that community and the way they interact and invest identity with other members.

In addition, as a result of deprivation from manifesting or accessing to power, women find themselves trying to resort to higher frequencies of **standard** and prestigious forms and even to language shift, as a strategy to manifest and to beat this sense of powerlessness, more than men do. (Eckfert, 1989). Notably, this shows that men’s are not too much inclined to use the standard language. This deemed to be as linguistic marker that reflects males’ dominance and masculinity in public spaces (Trudgill, 1972). Interestingly enough, sociolinguistic studies in the Middle East societies, on linguistics varieties, link prestigious linguistic features with SA, the outcome of their study reveals that men are the ones who use these features quite often than women. In contrast, in Arabic societies, women shift between languages using prestigious forms. (Al-Wer, 1997, 2014; Al-Wer and Herin, 2011; Al-Rohili, 2019). However, the argument about the adherence to link prestige to standard Arabic (SA) is questionable because the use of SA itself, especially in daily basis; online communication for instance, is unaccustomed and unusual. In most cases, Arabic societies, particularly the Algerian ones there are many other prestigious varieties, including rural and urban ones, which are usually used in informal settings. For instance, the Algerian Arabic is a rural variety and while French

is an urban one. French language gains a higher status because it is “perceived as a symbol of ‘modernity’, ‘enlightenment’, and ‘openness to the Western world’” (Sadiqi, 2003. P.11).

Back to the studies that has been conducted in Algeria, Achili (2019) in which she investigated the use of language in relation to gender among Algerian students, concluded that, unlike men, Berber females are inclined to use French, which is a prestigious variety in Algeria has reported particularly Kabyle, similar findings. Non-standard Arabic in that corpus is widely used by males more than females do.

Lakoff (1973) raises another critical issue on her influential work on “language and women’s place’, she analysed the use of language among women in the western industrialized societies and she concluded that women’s use of languages in these societies is powerless because they are restricted and barred from using the languages/ choices compared to men. They are therefore lower in status and less powerful than men’s language and this influence their position, power, and authority (Lakoff, 1973; Eckert and MacConnell-Ginet; 2003). Speaking about power.

It is noteworthy that there is a difference between the men and women languages; either in speaking or writing. This idea got the support from many sociolinguistics. Since my central focus is on the written language, specifically written online discourses, I will review what scholars observe and write about this side and then compare them to the Algerian contexts. For instance, Gyllard (2006), in his observational study of the linguistic differences between males and females, found that unlike men, women use more literature in their writings. The use of literature among women takes me back to the idea, which I mentioned earlier, of Eckfert (1989). It is widely known that the literature itself uses standard language, and the idea of using it among females confirm what other studies have concluded, i.e. women tend to use standard language to show their position in a particular context and also to save their faces from any sort of threatening. In this similar vein, Deuchar (1989), maintains that reason women use the standard language is that the latter is considered as a positive politeness strategy to avoid face-threatening acts during a conversation. Politeness in speech plays a crucial role in understanding and interpreting women and men’s use of language (Mesthrie et al, 2000). I will explain how politeness is essential in the language use and how it relates to gender in the coming section.

3.15 Linguistic Politeness and Gender

As I have just mentioned earlier the relation between language behaviours/ use, gender and politeness is a mutual one. Rudick and McGeough (2019, p.2844) notes that “politeness is an interpretive act within individuals’ interactions”. By individuals, it is meant both men and women. However, Politeness in language use tend to be more tied to females more than males (Spender, 1980; Milles, 2003). As the linguistic behaviours, features, use, and strategies differ from one gender to another, politeness, as well, has been proven, by many pragmatists and linguists, to be different from males to females. (Lakoff, 1975; Brown and Levinson, 1987; Cameron, 1992, and Mills, 2003). Despite of the rich empirical studies that have been studied in relation to language, gender, and politeness, very little research of them have been done in Algeria. For instance, El Hadj-Said (2016) conducted a quantitative study on the use of politeness strategies in Algerian requests. The findings showed that there is a big propensity in using positive politeness strategies. Sekkal (2018) has studied a similar investigation in which she conducts a socio-pragmatic analysis of politeness and complimenting among the Algerian context. The study carried a mixed approach (participant observation + a questionnaire). Sekkal’s (2018) findings confirms the alleged opinions that women show more politeness strategies than men do.

In Algeria, women’s attitudes towards the linguistic varieties is characterised by being more polite than men. In this vein, Rabahi (2013, p.57) claims that “Algerian women are socialised from childhood to be polite and conservative. This fact leads Algerian women to use more prestigious forms of speech including French”. This is due to the fact that women, from an early age, are culturally regulated. Yet, the use of a prestigious language does not necessarily be related to politeness in general and women, specifically. Since the linguistic features (including politeness), differ from one society to another and from one situation to another. Not surprisingly, previous studies show that due to the French colonialism in Algeria, there have been an orientation among Kabylis who immigrated to France. Obviously, the French language replaced Arabic and become the second language among most of the Kabyle males (Roberts, 1981-1998). Therefore, admitting the fact that politeness is tied to women and not men in connection to prestigious language(s), French, for instance does not seem convincing because each culture has its own norms and each situation has specific strategies, as I argued above, the thing that makes politeness a dynamic feature (Koay, 2015; Meier, 1997). This is

from one side, from the other side, as I defined the term gender in **section 3.3**, the nature of gender itself is fluid and dynamic. This is what Gardner-Chloros (2009, p. 83) confirm when they state 'gender is not a fixed, stable and universal category whose meaning is shared within or across cultures'.

Shifting back to the south-eastern coast of Africa, a study was conducted in a small village in Madagascar, while investigating politeness, revealed that men are more polite than women (Brown. 1980).

Tracing back to the relationship between gender, language, and politeness, the seminal works of the American sociologist Robin Lakoff's (1973- 1975) on women language and politeness were helpful in figuring out the bound between the three micro levels; gender, language, and politeness. According to Lakoff, (1973; 1975) the use of tag questions (isn't it?, don't we?), suggestions, and interrogative statement is a sign of politeness that involves checking for Information, confirming it, or asking for an agreement. In Algeria, Babo (2012) on her Master thesis studied both male and female linguistic practices among Chlef speakers, a community that is located in the north of Algeria, revealed that the use of tag questions is used by both males and females. An example that is taken from her corpus is illustrated as the following:

"*ræhi ssxæena, mæʃi?*". It is hot, isn't it?

"*Sæ3ti jæeba, mæʃi?*". My watch is nice, isn't it. (Babo, p. 2012. P.9).

The husband-and-wife researchers; Penelope Brown and Stephen Levinson (1980-1989) have carried out another seminal work of gender and politeness. Yet, the study was stemmed, at first, by Brown (1980) when she conducted her study in Tenejapa, a southern Mayan community in Mexico. Then, she developed a model of linguistic politeness in cooperation with Levinson. She concluded that women in that community use "used the extremes of positive and negative politeness, while men spoke more 'matter-of- factly' ". Mesthrie, Swann, Deumert and Leap (2000, p. 231). Additionally, Bown and Levinson (1987) postulate that the use of hedges, as a negative strategy, was mainly associated with women. A very similar conclusion has be drawn by Lakoff (1975) in which she asserts that hedging is a feminine strategy that is mostly used when women are unable to express their proposition in a direct way. This is again relates to the social position of women and the social milieu they grew up in where uncertainty is a marker/ a strategy of their subordination.

Anthropological differentiation between men and women positions is constructed around some stereotypes such as women are supposed to be carer, good wives who take care of their

children at home whereas men are the ones who have that higher status in terms of the absolute symbolic access to power. Tassadit (2001, p.103) draws an insightful analogy when he refers to the women space and status in Berber society. He wrote: “women are depicted as a homogeneous body whose members are all the same and identical”.

it the former concept is elusive to understand gender variations in relation to linguistic norms, choice, and attitudes.

3.16. Bourdieu and Gender

The French sociologist Pierre Bourdieu’s works in sociology were influential in exploring the conundrum of the social world. recognizes the epistemological side of the social classes as a notion that encompasses the social fields and habitus that is related to politics and economy, along with the habitus of gender and power (Adkins and Skeggs,2004; Lingard, 2005). Because he sees gender as a second micro-level principle in a society, Bourdieu’s works on gender studies are somewhat limited until he published his first book that is entitled his book *La Domination Masculine* or *The Masculine Domination* in 2001(Nicola, 2018; Telling, 2013). In this book, Bourdieu seemed to share the same principles of the feminists.i.e. when he mentions the term gender he means the same thing the feminists mean and this is apparent in his book “*The Bachelors’ Ball*”. I will discuss this point, in more in the next section; “gender and feminism” (see section 3.16.1), but before that I will add more contributions and stances of Bourdieu towards gender and power field and habitus. During the 1962, the period that marked the post-war, Bourdieu pictured the evolvement of gender, which radically changes the social structure and the social practices in rural France. Therefore, we cannot admit that Bourdieu’s interests towards gender as a social factor that determines individual’s directions were neglected. In Algeria, particularly Kabylia, Bourdieu’s anthropological data about gender were mainly presented in his book “*la domination masculine*”. As an introduction of this book, Bourdieu maintained that the empirical data he got from his studies in Kabyle is described as a “direct study of a system still in a functioning state” (Bourdieu, 2001, p.6). In fact, Bourdieu used this expression to accolade the Kabylia’s social structure that was preserved even after the colonialism in behaviours as well as discourses. Within this sphere, Bourdieu justifies why he chose Kabylia as a train for studying by postulating that the choice of the particular case

of Kabylia is justified when one knows, on the other hand, that “the cultural traditions that has been maintained there constitutes a paradigmatic realization of the Mediterranean tradition” (Bourdieu, 2001, p.6).

In line with Bourdieu’s book of *La Domination Masculine*, Bourdieu (2001) uses an impressive analogy to describe the power relations that are dictated through gender as a social constructed factor - “the phallogocentric vision of the world”. Another central tenet of the book, is that Bourdieu relates the habitus to gender. Habitus is the attitudes we got from the society of practice (Martina, 2006). According to Bourdieu, habitus is related to social life of individuals and hence it influences their symbolic capital. Bourdieu defines the symbolic capital as “the form that the various species of capital assume when they are perceived and recognized as legitimate” (Bourdieu, 1989, p.17).

keeping the focus of Bourdieu and gender, cultural capital indeed plays an eminent role in women’s life, more than it does in men’s practices. This is because they -women- are the primary source of transmitting this capital to their children; yet men tend to be more relate to the educational degrees so as to get a job. (Bourdieu, 1984). Relating this claim to the Algerian cultural capital, women in that society were socially determined from an early age to be put as “house wives” where they take care of their house, husbands, and children. Whereas men are socially and culturally determining to finish their studies and get a job.

3.16.1 The Intersection of Gender and Language: Insights from Feminist Studies

The relationship between gender and language has been a central concern in feminist studies, where scholars explore how language perpetuates or challenges gendered power dynamics. Seminal feminist works, such as those by Robin Lakoff (2004) on ‘Women’s Language’ and Deborah Tannen provide foundational insights into the ways language is used to construct and maintain gender identities. For instance, both Lakoff and Tannen identified linguistic features associated with women; such as, politeness, and indirectness, expressions of powerlessness (Lakoff and Bucholtz, 2004). Interestingly too, while Lakoff (2004) sparked significant debate and set the stage for extensive research, critiques have emerged questioning the deterministic implications of her framework. For example, critics argue that

viewing "women's language" primarily as submissive overlooks the situational pragmatics and individual agency behind such linguistic choices.

Critically, building on Lakoff's insights, scholars have examined the appropriation and subversion of gendered language. As an example, Hall and Bucholtz (2012) explored how women in various cultural contexts adopt language traditionally associated with men, challenging rigid gender norms. However, I should argue that these appropriations are not universally empowering; that is they often occur within constraints that limit their transformative potential. For instance, adopting 'men's language' may invite criticism or marginalisation, highlighting the persistent societal policing of gendered behaviours (Vani K. et al., 2023; Szczesny et al., 2016).

Research into the role of language in constructing gender identities has further nuanced this field. Bergvall et al. (2014) emphasised how linguistic practices actively produce and sustain gender categories. Yet again, this raises the question of whether such constructions can be destabilised through linguistic innovation. While feminist translation, as explored by Ergun (2010), aims to challenge linguistic sexism, its impact is often limited to specific contexts and struggles to address the deeper systemic biases embedded in language itself. Feminist scholars, particularly those influenced by Lakoff (1975) emphasise that gender is not a fixed biological attribute but a socially constructed phenomenon. For this, language plays a central role in this construction. For instance, Lakoff's (1995) seminal work on 'Language and Woman's Place' (introduced the concept of "women's language," identifying features such as, politeness strategies, and tag questions as markers of femininity. In this regard, Lakoff (1975) argued that these features are not inherently female, but are socially imposed through gendered expectations, reinforcing women's subordinate status.

Additionally, Tannen's (1990) seminal research in 'You Just Don't Understand: Women and Men in Conversation' expanded on Lakoff's (1995) ideas by framing gendered communication styles in terms of "rapport-talk"; that is typically associated with women, and "report-talk" that is often linked to men). Thus, one might argue that Tannen's (1990) perspectives, illuminated how societal norms dictate different conversational strategies for men and women, perpetuating stereotypes about emotionality and rationality.

Additionally, Hall and Bucholtz (1995) reveal the contextual variability of gendered linguistic practices. For instance, Japanese women's strategic use of "men's language" and the gendered use of Spanish in New Mexican weddings (Hall and Bucholtz, 1995). They (Hall and Bucholtz (1995), further illustrate how cultural norms shape and mediate these dynamics. However, such studies also underscore the importance of intersectionality, as gendered language practices are often influenced by race, class, and many other social factors that are not always adequately addressed in linguistic research. Furthermore, the interplay between language, gender, and power underscores the need for interdisciplinary approaches. Linguistics, sociology, and feminist theory must intersect to unpack the multifaceted ways in which language perpetuates and resists inequality. Crucially too, while feminist studies have significantly advanced our understanding, addressing gender-based linguistic inequalities requires moving beyond description to action. This includes advocating for systemic changes in how language is taught, translated, and regulated, ensuring that it becomes a tool for empowerment rather than oppression (Van and Shohamy, 2002).

Furthermore, intersectional approaches, such as those introduced by Cho and Crenshaw (2013) highlight that gendered language use cannot be fully understood without considering other axes of identity. This includes race, class, and sexuality. Cho and Crenshaw (2013) illustrated that African American Vernacular English (AAVE) is often stigmatised, particularly when spoken by 'Black women', reflecting the interplay of racism and sexism in linguistic discrimination. Thus, such analyses demonstrate that the intersection of language and gender is far more complex than early feminist studies suggested (Freed, 1995).

In conclusion, the study of gender and language reveals the profound ways in which language both shapes and is shaped by societal norms. From Lakoff's (2004) identification of gendered speech patterns and Cho and Crenshaw's (2013) intersectional lens, feminist scholars has significantly advanced our understanding of this dynamic relationship. Hence, these studies not only expose the power dynamics embedded in language, but also offer pathways for challenging and transforming these inequalities. Language, as a living and evolving medium, remains a crucial site for both the reinforcement and resistance of gendered power structures.

With regards to Bourdieu's works in relation to gender: in his work 'the Algerians' (1962), Bourdieu conceptualizes gender to sexual differentiations. In this matter, Skeggs (2004, p.21) maintains that "the body experienced is always a social body made up of meanings and values, gestures, postures, physical bearing, speech and language". During the post-modernism era of linguistic studies, particularly with the work of Foucault, Lyotard, and Derrida, the simplest meaning of language as a tool that conveys messages or discourses was challenged. Discourses in that era used to describe the everyday human social practices using meanings that are based on signs and symbols (Apter. 2005; Barham, 2012). Bourdieu's works can be seen in four features, summarized by Blackledge (2011) as the following: at first, it appeared in his ethnographic studies about language in the northern of Algeria, Kabyle, during the French colonialism era and in Béarn, in the southwestern of France. As a second level, Bourdieu's interests about language have been spotted on his critical analysis of academic fields; the critique was based on linguistic analysis. The study of language also appears in his theoretical base of linguistic practice where he developed his key concepts around habitus, field, and capital to analyse the social context. Finally, since language has soci-symbolic functions, each symbol/ word reflects power and cannot be exempted from a context because words cannot be said to be a value neutral, but rather it has to be put in a social context/discourse (Bourdieu, 1977).

3.17. Language shift and Gender Variation

Language is a unique instrument of human in a way it distinguishes them from other non-human creatures, animal for example. One of the answers to the question of "why should we be so interested in the details of language in the first place?" William (1995) answered: "because it is considered the most accessible part of the human mind".

Code switching differs due to many factors; age, gender, level of education, context and so on. Bilingual/ bilingual speakers' use of online written code switching varies from one person to another and from one gender to another. These differences may be at the level of code-switching types as well as the choice of language among males and females. In fact, language

choice is generally influenced by both the age and the gender of the speaker. When it comes to selecting the intended language, both Algerian females and males differ. In this vein, Sadiqi (2003) points out that “gender interferes greatly with language use; women do not often have the same choices a man” (p. 6).

Since the major concern of this study is studying code-switching phenomenon in gender perspectives, both genders do implement code switching in their conversation; however, women have much more affiliation with the alternation of codes. (Sadiqi, 2003). Hence, women tend to use more prestigious language and code switching more than men, and thus the differences can be also seen in the use of prestigious urban varieties and rural ones. (Achili, 2019; Bassiouney, 2009). Moreover, the difference between the two genders may also occur when at the level of choosing between urban and rural varieties. In this essence, Bassiouney (2009) adds “[...] women are more prone to choose the urban variety as a symbolic means of asserting their identity”. (p. 166). A study pinpointed by Achili (2019) reveals that unlike men, Berber females use more French, which is considered as a prestigious language in Algeria. They also tend to use English more than men when texting messages, whereas, Berber language is rarely used in texting. Additionally, women in Algeria prefer to shift from the Algerian Arabic (AA) to the French language. According to Flemons (2020), women find themselves at ease and free when they shift to the French language because this freedom is not available for them in the Arabic language that is presented by the ruling elite. However, restricting the linguistic heritage in Algeria to freedom and politics does not seem convincing since it neglects the soci-inguistic, social culture and the social capital of the society.

Conclusion

In this chapter, I have shed the light on the social networking sites social factors namely gender, language and politeness. At first, I have highlighted how the gender studies have

come up and emerge, then I defined the term gender from many perspectives, arguing that gender is not fixed but rather fluid and dynamic. Moreover, the chapter tries to clarify the lacuna between the gender issues in Algeria and Kabyle, in terms of the language differences and the linguistic politeness ones; where women, in contrast to men, were too much inclined to prestigious languages and positive politeness. I add some literature about the use of language, in general and the use of code switching, in particular on the social networking site, Facebook. As I will study Facebook as social capital arena in Algeria. I will finally relate code switching to the politeness strategies that are used on online settings, between men and women.

Chapter Four: Theoretical Framework

Introduction

In accordance with the thesis argument, in order to understand students' dynamics in online communication, notably within Facebook educational groups, both educators and language researchers need to investigate how these dynamics are manifested, in accordance with

students' practices. Crucially, this study provides insights into the collaborative learning process in Facebook group and the community of practice it creates. Importantly too, this thesis highlights a research gap which is a lack of exploration of how the sharing dynamics are manifested in online communication. Secondly, a lack of understanding how students use Facebook groups and what are the type of learning that is happening in Facebook learning groups. Putting these ideas front and centre, has led me to reflect on a theoretical framework to conceptualise my study, using Bourdieu's Forms of Capital (linguistic Capital and linguistic habitus, and social/ cultural capital, to analyse how students' practices are manifested in the group, and to see how the Facebook group they used by students and what type of learning does it offer. Therefore, I should further argue that the use of Facebook educational groups can be viewed as a form of social capital due to its affordance in providing access to different resources and fostering communication by creating networking opportunities for students. Putting all these ideas front and centre, has led me to think about framing my research into two theories that are explained in the coming sections.

4.1 Theoretical Perspectives: Why does it Matter.

My argument behind the implementation of the use of theoretical perspectives is that they are used to interrogate data and interpret reality. The purpose of this section, therefore, is to provide an overview of the meaning of the theoretical perspective in qualitative research, and to outline a blueprint for the rationale behind integrating it. To begin with, a theoretical framework is considered as the central base of a research study. A clear definition has been presented by Merriam and Tisdell (2016), in which they state that a theoretical framework refers to the "underlying structure, the scaffolding or frame of your study (p.85). Its use can be further applied to understand certain aspects of certain phenomenon. In this regard, Anfara and Mertz (2015, p.15) further define theoretical frameworks as "any empirical or quasi empirical theory of social/and/ or psychological processes at a variety of levels". The importance of implementing a theoretical framework lies in its benefits in which it: a) provides focus and organisation to the study, b) exposes and obstruct meaning, c) connects the study to existing scholarship and terms, and d) identifies strengths and weaknesses (Collins and Stockton, 2018, p.5). To reiterate, the process of selecting a theoretical perspective in the study, comes from appreciation of relevant reading, and individual reflections on theoretical

standpoints. The literature review demonstrated that education and linguistic practices are inflected by the French language and the cultural capital of Algeria.

It is significant to highlight that my aim is not to test the theory, but to use it as a guide to unpack how students are manifesting their learning and language habits on the Facebook group, focusing on gender levels and the type of learning that is going on in the group. This means that I did not employ these theories prior to the data collection stage to direct the study. Rather, I utilised these theories and concepts while examining and discussing the data to make sense of it, when analysing and discussing the study findings. This way, I approached the study inductively and not deductively.

4.2 Social capital: a form of capital

The aim of this section is to provide a comprehensive grasp of the concept of social capital and its relevance to the present study. To better elucidate the concept of social capital, it is important to decipher it into its constituent parts: (social+ capital). Then, I will discuss how this concept can be applicable to my research. To visually represent these concepts, I used a bee shape to conceptualise the use of Facebook educational group among students, illustrating the relationship between understanding students' dynamics in their Facebook group, and gaining insights into the role of the Facebook group being a social capital where student collaborate and share knowledge and language. In figure 4.1, the bee head represents the Facebook group, with body to conceptualise how it is viewed as both a social capital and human capital. Last, but not least, the wings are used to refer to the functions that social capital demonstrate in the Facebook group, when sharing and exchanging resources. These concepts will be explained in the coming sections.

Figure 4.1: Visual Representation of Facebook as Social Capital among Students

Originally, the term capital, in social capital, was originally “monetary” (Smith and Kulynych, 2002, p.149). This means it was merely revolving around money, economics, and finance. However, Bourdieu (1986, 1997), argues that the term capital is not solely related to money. But rather, it encompasses three fundamental forms namely: a) economic capital which is, as explained related to promises of money and investments that can enable the development of individual cultural capital, which is linked to educational achievements, the thing that, in turns, contributes to the development of the economic capital. cultural capital according to Bourdieu (1986) represents the resources that individuals have access to through socialisation, education, social, and cultural practices. Therefore, this form of capital reflects individuals’ cultural competencies, including their dispositions, knowledge, and the way the speak.

Linked to students’ practices in the educational Facebook group, the practice of interacting and engaging require that students possess collective knowledge, skills, and social connections to bring into the group for the purpose of contributing to each other’s learning experiences. This referred to as social capital. According to Bourdieu and Wacquant (1992, p.119), social capital can be defined as:

“The sum of resources, actual or virtual, that accrue to an individual or a group by virtue of possessing a durable network of more or less institutionalised relationships of mutual acquaintance and recognition”.

Put it simpler, social capital refers to resources and social connections that exist within a particular community. Taking resources into considerations, Spottswood and Wohn (2020) further argue that resources can be tangible and intangible. The former could be referred to the process of transferring a particular skill or knowledge to others, while the latter pertains to provide guidance and assistance, as well as exchanging knowledge and information. Hence, in this thesis, social capital is used to gain insights into how students utilise the group, particularly in terms of sharing learning resources and interacting with one another to collaborate and support their learning process. Collaboration on Facebook is based on the active participation of students to work together to achieve their learning outcomes. It involves group members to work together, sharing their ideas, knowledge, and resources. Likewise, I would argue with World and Bank (1999) that social capital is the “glue that holds them together” (p.44).

The concept of social capital has been further developed to differentiate between two separate social capitals, which are: bridging and bounding social capital. According to Helliwell and Putnam (2004), bounding capital, as the name indicates itself, is “embodied in bounds among family, friends, and neighbours, in the workplace, at church, in civic associations, perhaps even in the Internet based virtual communities”. These bounds facilitate the interaction based on the shared interests, resources, and groups that would be inaccessible for some (Braudt, 2014). Therefore, I should argue with Chen and Meng (2015) that this form of social capital is internal as it is embodied and intertwined among individuals’ who share similar background.

On the hand, bridging social capital refers to the “distant ties such as loose friends and workmates (Woolcock, 2001, p.1437). These ties are considered as bridging capital that involve interactions, reflecting the dynamics that are often observed in online communities (Adler and Known, 2002, p.19). This suggests that this type of social capital is formed through diverse, that offers information, but separately as it operates in different circles and does not provide emotional support (Paige et al., 2017).

It is important to understand the mechanism through which the Facebook educational groups facilitate the process of bounding and bridging among students. By joining specific group that is focused on a particular course, students can build a virtual community by connecting, sharing/exchanging resources, and collaborating with their peers in an informal way. This understanding is crucial in gaining insights into how Facebook educational groups are related

to social capital and how students develop their social capital using these groups. The relation between Facebook and social capital has been a subject of researchers' interests (Raza, Qazi, and Umer, 2016). Additionally, the impact of Facebook study groups on building and social capital among teenagers and students has been also studied (Kasperski and Blau, 2023; Hedairi, Salimi, and Mehcrvarz, 2023; Elisson et al, 2007; Johnstone et al, 2013). However, in the Algerian context, limited attention has been given to explore how social capital in Facebook study groups is formed among students. This gap elucidates our understanding of how social networking sites, such as Facebook online study groups contributes to the formation of social capital among students.

Linked to online social networking sites, Braudt (2014) identifies four sub-forms of online social capital, and that are illustrated in diagram below:

Figure 4.2: Online Social Capital-Subforms.

Online social capital refers to the attributes of individuals' social network, and the potential sum of knowledge that are available and can be gained from this network in online platforms (Bourdieu and Wacquant, 1992). On the other hand, offline social capital pertains the social connection and resources that are realised through in person interaction (Abbas and Mesch, 2018). Students' engagement and interaction in the form of sharing resources and collaborating a virtual community of practice whose members share common goals, and develop a sense of belonging., through bounding the capital, that are explained in section 4.3.

To reiterate, this study focuses mainly on two forms of capitals, namely cultural and linguistic capital. That is, it emphasises on language skills that are manifested in the online educational Facebook group among students, and their learning habitus that are manifested. To visualise

how these forms capitals intersect to my research, I further use the diagram (4.3) bellow, as an illustration. The diagram will be fully discussed in section 4.2 bellow.

Figure 4.3: the Manifestation of Cultural and Linguistic Capital in Online Communication

4.3 About Pierre Bourdieu

Before going to explaining how the forms of capitals of Bourdieu relate to my study, I found it crucial to first of all, introduce a short biography of Bourdieu himself.

Pierre Bourdieu (1930-2002), a French sociologist and cultural anthropologist, was born in a small village in the southern of France called “Denguin”. After receiving his doctoral degree from the École Normale Supérieure in 1954, Bourdieu was sent for a military service went to Algeria where he took a teaching position in 1958. At that time, Algeria was still under the domination of the French colonialism. During that ear, Bourdieu took an ethnographic study in Kabyle, the largest homogenous group in Algeria. In relation to his fieldwork there, Pierre published his first book “*Sociologie De l’Algérie*” (the Sociology of French) in 1958, along with many other book publications, such as: *Algerian Sketches*, *Images d’Algérie (Picturing Algeria)*, which contains around 150 pictures that Bourdieu took during his ethnographic.

Keeping my focus on language and Bourdieu, Bourdieu’s interests and works on language and society arise in reaction to the French linguists Sausure 2011 and Chomsky 1965. Bourdieu (1982, p.30) argues that in Saussure’s *Langue and Parole*, he did “speech the product of the language” which means that the structuralist Saussure sees the speech production or the

linguistic practices as an immobile product of language, the same Saussurian idea was held by Chomsky in his analysis of competence and performance. Wacquant (1992, p.214), states that Bourdieu analyse language as “an instrument of power relations, rather than a mere means of communication, that must be studied within the interactional and structural contexts of its production and circulation”.

4.4 Bourdieu and Language

In his book “Language and Symbolic Power”, (LSP), Bourdieu, as cited in (Moraru, 2020, p.5) argues that “language itself is not intrinsically powerful, but rather the value of linguistic practices is influenced by the power relations between interlocutors in a particular context”. Bourdieu (1991) in his book (LSP) offered a model of called linguistic production and circulation in which he highlights three main concepts namely: **linguistic habitus**, **capital** (power), **field**, and **the linguistic market**. Bourdieu refers to the latter as the communicative context in which agents exchange their linguistic capital. (Bourdieu, 1993). Capital refers to the command or the ability to produce habitus (languages) relevant to a particular market. Each one of these Bourdieusian concepts will be explained deeply in the coming sections. Interacting with others using different expressions and utterances is considered as the outcome of both the linguistic habitus and linguistic market. i.e. the manifestation of the linguistic skills that we, individuals, acquire through our social milieu. Bourdieu coins the term linguistic market to refer to the fact that different language and different language varieties have a symbolic value. Bourdieu completely rejects the autonomy of language and hence he proposes that the linguistic practices between agents are deliberated and produced in a context (market) that is shaped and influenced by the sociohistorical and economics constrains ((Bourdieu, 1977a, 1990, 1991). Based on what has been discussed above about Bourdieu’s interests and works on language, I present the Bourdieusian social field analysis along with Bourdieu’s LSP to understand the code choice and code switching as a linguistic and social capital; how it relates to individual behaviour, ethnicity, gender, and other social position. To begin with, it is appropriate to define the Bourdieusian concepts about what he coined social space, or “field” and, then, identify the dialectic bound between the three notions: **field**, **habitus**, and **capital**.

Bourdieu acknowledges that the social world is an assembly point that encompasses the social structure that an agent or an individual of a particular society used to reproduce or transform as an outcome of the dialectical relationships between agents and their social structures (Bourdieu, 1977b; 1989, 1990b). Regarding the use of language and its social practices that this study focuses on most, I draw upon Bourdieu's social practice theory, as it is interwoven with the habitus, human attitudes that is learnt from families or communities that individual belong in. In addition to the capital (both the social and the cultural), that governs the human behaviour, which is manifested in a given field. Consequently, social practice according to Bourdieu (1984, p.101) is demonstrated as follow: “{(habitus + Capital)} +field=practice”. I chose these Bourdieusian tools of thinking to understand the way the online code-switching practices are manifested among males and females Kabyle students. Habitus, capital, and field will be discussed in the next section.

4.5 The embodied cultural Capital

Bourdieu (1986, p.243) elucidates that the embodied state reflects “the long-lasting dispositions of the mind and the body”. Moreover, Bourdieu (1984) add that these dispositions encompass four other aspects: a persons' attitudes, intellect, knowledge, and style of speech. Crucially, these four facets of dispositions are influenced and related by linguistic resources (capital) that individuals possess from their social world. Therefore, I should argue with Bourdieu (1977, p.660) that “linguistic capital is an embodied capital”. Linguistic capital refers the sum of language resources which facilitate individuals' speech, attitudes, knowledge, and practices (Klapwijk and Van der Walt, 2016).

4.5.1 Linguistic Capital

As discussed, the kernel aim of this study is to examine how Kabyle students use language in relation to their social and cultural background that mediates their choice of language. This reflects back the idea of Bourdieu's habitus. A (linguistic) habitus is a set of dispositions that dictates individuals thinking, behaviour, perception, and actions in relation their social context or market (Belvedere, 2013; Bourdieu 1977b, Bourdieu and Thompson, 1991). Put it simply (linguistic) habitus refers to the attitudes an individual possesses from their family or their speech community. Though there has been some critiques and debates about Bourdieu's concept of habitus in terms of objectivity and subjectivity (Belvedere, 2013), the choice of

drawing upon Bourdieu's habitus appears promising in both subjective and objective levels. It helps understanding individuals' personal past experiences (subjectivity); in addition to the objectivity of the linguistic/ social etiquette and how these etiquettes can be internalized by individuals in a particular market (Maton, 2008). Giving the potential to individuals' experiences is crucial as it shapes their actual practices. For instance, by taking the context of Algeria (see chapter 1), Algerians had a great influence of the French colonialism, and therefore this has subsequently shaped their linguistic norms as well social cultural ones.

4.5.2 Cultural Capital

Another conceptual tool in Bourdieu's social practice theory is Capital. Bourdieu (1997) indicates that capital refers to the symbolic resources including skills, knowledge, attitudes, and levels of education. For this study purpose, I will focus on the language skills that are embedded in the linguistic capital. Linguistic capital is a form of Bourdieu's cultural capital. Individuals are endowed with different linguistic capital, including the language competency in their dominant language. However, those who lack that skill and/or competence are inclined to partially acquire it, add another system or repertoire to their linguistic schemata, and hence secure of 'profit of distinction' (Bourdieu, and Thompson, 1991, p.18). Thus, linguistic capital seems to serve the main aim objective in this study as it further contributes to a clear insight in examining how the socio/historical and linguistic backgrounds shapes agents' online use and code choice of language(s).

4.5.3 The Field

A field is the social sphere or market in which individuals generate and manifest their practices (Thompson, 2008). How the choice of each language, in terms of code switching mediates and shapes the use politeness strategies on Facebook. Bourdieu (1985) describes field as a structured social space. Based on that description, a field is a combination of many other fields. For this reason, this study looks at code switching (linguistic), gender (students males and females), and Facebook as sociolinguistic arenas which have their own social etiquette. The linguistic market can be seen as an example of Bourdieu's (1986) field, that this characterised by different social networkers that belong to different social positions, students from different levels of education, in the case of this study. Hamid (2016, p.38) argues that a field a linguistic market is "a field of linguistic exchange in which people trade their language varieties and linguistic proficiencies". This study conceptualises Facebook as a field where

linguistic and learning exchange, where not only the forms of capitals are manifested, but also the creation of a community of practice. Henceforth, the coming section discusses how the studied Facebook group is regarded as an -online- community of practice (CoP). But before that, I should make also refer to the main critiques to Bourdieu's work.

4.6 Key Criticisms of Bourdieu's Social Capital Theory on Language Use

Pierre Bourdieu's theoretical contributions to language use and gender studies have stimulated significant debate. While Bourdieu's work offers valuable insights into the interplay between language, power, and social structure, many scholars have criticised its limitations, particularly in addressing gender dynamics. Thus, this section seeks to explore the key criticisms of Bourdieu's theory.

Prominently, Järvinen (1999) critiques Bourdieu's emphasis on self-reproducing power mechanisms, arguing that it leads to a defeatist view of society's gender system. This criticism resonates with broader concerns that Bourdieu's theory downplays agency and resistance, especially among women (Emerson et al, 2019). By framing linguistic practices as overwhelmingly constrained by habitus and the linguistic market, Bourdieu risks oversimplifying how gender norms can be challenged or subverted. For example, women's strategic use of language to resist patriarchal structures or create solidarity within marginalised communities suggests that linguistic agency plays a crucial role in reshaping power dynamics (Shahid, 2024; Ahearn, 2001). Therefore, Integrating Järvinen's (1999) critique into an analysis of Bourdieu's work highlights the need to account for transformative possibilities within gendered linguistic practices.

Another crucial critique has been made by Adkins (2003) who extends this criticism towards Bourdieu's theory by exploring the influence of Bourdieu's ideas on feminist accounts of gender transformations in late modernity. Adkins (2003) questions the coupling of reflexivity with detraditionalisation, arguing that Bourdieu's framework does not fully address how individuals navigate and reconfigure traditional gender norms in contemporary contexts (Bathmaker, 2015). This critique is particularly relevant in discussions of language and gender, where shifts in cultural and professional norms often redefine what constitutes valuable

linguistic capital. For instance, the increasing visibility of women in leadership roles challenges traditional expectations of 'feminine' speech', as assertive or authoritative linguistic styles gain greater acceptance (Blankenship and Robson, 1995; Eagly and Johnson, 1990).

Significantly too, responding to critiques of Bourdieu's language analysis, Susen (2013) emphasises the need for a more nuanced understanding of the questions his work raises. That is, while Bourdieu's theory effectively illuminates how language reinforces power structures, it does not adequately address the complexities of gendered linguistic practices. Thus, Susen (2013) called for nuance aligns with feminist critiques that Bourdieu's concept of symbolic power often homogenises gendered experiences, overlooking the diversity within and across social groups (Flower, 1990; Sharp, 2020). For instance, an intersectional approach of Berger and Guidroz (2010) reveals how women's linguistic capital is shaped not only by gender but also by race, class, and other identities.

Importantly, Bourdieu's framework remains valuable for gender scholars, particularly in explicating the concrete circuits of symbolic power that shape gender constructions (Luengo, 2018). While Bourdieu may not have explicitly prioritised gender in his analyses, his concepts of habitus and linguistic market provide tools for understanding how societal norms influence gendered language practices (Myles, 1999). By building on Bourdieu's insights, Luengo (2018) suggests that scholars can uncover the mechanisms through which linguistic practices sustain or challenge these hierarchies, making his framework a powerful resource for feminist inquiry.

Crucially, I should argue that despite the aforementioned varied perspectives, critics collectively demonstrate that engaging with both the strengths and limitations of Bourdieu's theory can enrich studies of gender and language (McDonough and Abrica, 2023). Moreover, McCall (1992) elucidates that by addressing these critiques, scholars can extend Bourdieu's framework to explore not only how gendered linguistic practices reinforce social inequalities, but also how they provide opportunities for resistance and change. Therefore, this perspective ensures that Bourdieu's work remains a dynamic and relevant tool for understanding the evolving interplay between language, gender, and power in society.

4.7 Community of Practice (CoP)

Wenger-Trayner (2015) and Wenger *et al.* (2002) define a community of practice as a group of people who inquire about common concerns. Implementing aspects of this theory has been argued to be crucial in understanding the way students share resources in the groups and the way they collaborate with their peers who share the same domains, and the same level of education. Hence, the interrelationship between CoP and this study is that it relates to RQ1, ***“what roles does the Facebook study group paly in students’ learning experiences?”***. This suggests that this question addresses the role of this group in creating a learning community of practice, in which students collaborate with their peers by sharing their concerns, learning, and knowledge resources. In this regard, CoPs is further defined as:

“Groups of people who share a concern, a set of problems, or a passion about a topic, and who deepen their knowledge and expertise in this area by interacting on an ongoing basis” (Wenger, McDermott, and Synder (2002, p.4).

Based on this definition, it can be argued that, in online Facebook study group, CoPs create collaboration by fostering shared concerns, deepening collaborative knowledge sharing, and providing an ongoing interaction on a particular topic, through the commenting feature on Facebook. These mechanisms therefore contribute to an informal collaborative learning environment where students collaboratively engage in a learning environment where students share resources and collaborate together to achieve common goals, including building knowledge, contribute to it, and revising to pass the exams. Within a similar vein, Hara (2009, p,139) argues that CoPs is a “collaborative informal networks that support professional practitioners in their efforts to develop shared understandings and engage in work-relevant knowledge building”. To reiterate, Wenger et al (2002), Lave and Wenger (1991) had given limited attention to the concept of Online Communities of Practice. However, with the rise of technology, there is an increased focus and interest on investigating online communities within the context of CoP (Qi and Wang, 2017).

Linked to Facebook learning groups and based on Hara's (2009) definition, Facebook learning groups can be seen as a collaborative informal network that supports students in the group in developing shared knowledge resources and concerns related to their academic course materials. This includes sharing experiences/knowledge, and offering help to support each other's learning journey, through discussions and interactions. Hence, this indicates that group creates a sense of inclusion among students in a way it helps them to form a bounding social capital. This argument was supported by Wenger and Snyder (2000, p.139) in which they elucidate that CoPs refers to "a group of people who informally bound together by shared expertise and passion for a joint enterprise"

4.8 Aspects of CoPs in Facebook Study Group

For a community to be classified as a community of practice, three critical elements are required: a domain of knowledge, a practice of community, and the act of practice itself (Wenger-Trayner, 2015, and Wenger *et al.*, 2002). When these three elements are combined together, they create a knowledge structure, which in turn gives the rise to the process of knowledge sharing. The coming sections discuss each of the aspects that construct a community of practice.

4.8.1 Domain of knowledge

Wenger et al (2002) argue that process of domain knowledge involves establishing a shared foundation and developing common areas of interests where members can actively engage in their own learning and discover personal significance in their participation. This signifies that it is the domain, or the area of interest that creates a shared domain among members of community. Linked to Facebook online groups, Facebook provides an ideal space for students with common interests in educational domains and language practices, fostering an active participation, which involves ongoing interaction and knowledge sharing (Razak and Saeed, 2014). Attaining this domain relies on the community of practice's ability to adapt, develop, and serve the needs of a particular organisation. It therefore addresses issues and problems that might cover a wide range of topics of members' interests. In this vein, Wenger *et al.* (2002) assert that for a community of practice to be successful, the objectives and needs of an organisation should align with interests and motivation of its members. The presence of a

domain of knowledge contributes to knowledge development, which, in turn, leads the community to be a powerful source of knowledge, and collaboration. This view was supported by Wenger, McDermott, and Snyder (2002) argue that the domain serves as a driving force in a community of practice, deriving people to actively participate in the community, fostering their learning experience, and gives significance and value to their practice.

4.8.2 A community of people

Another crucial element of a CoP is the construction of a community of people. This study contends that creating a sense of belonging among member, fosters their commitment to the domain of knowledge, and consequently enhances their engagement in collaboration. This stance was affirmed by Wenger et al., (2002) learning is not a mere intellectual process, but it is also about feeling a sense of belonging, which entails cognitive and emotional processes.

Therefore, I shall argue that community is the core aspects of interaction, learning, sharing and building social capital between individuals. Building a community according to Wenger *et al* (2002) requires a consistent engagement revolving around relevant domains discussed within the community.

4.8.3 Practice

Practice is another core element in creating a community of practice. Practice, in a community of practice, refers to the where the process of exchanging knowledge occurs. The process of doing the practice entails delving into an existing knowledge that individuals have in their repertoire, i.e., educational and cultural capitals, which is linked to a particular domain. In this regard, Wenger *et al.*, (2002) argue that the concept of practice encompasses elements that are derived from both implicit and explicit knowledge, resulting in a shared outcome. Therefore, as Mohajan (2017, p.28) claims, practice refers to “knowledge in action”.

Through participants’ active participation, participants develop their understanding about the practice of the community of practice they belong to. This enables them to actively engage with a variety of “tools, language, role-definitions, and other explicit artefacts as well as various implicit relations, tacit, conventions, and underlying assumptions and values (Handley et al, 2006, p.5).

Conclusion

In this chapter, I have outlined the study's theoretical foundations, by presenting four key concepts and two core theories, namely Bourdieu's Forms of Capital, and Community of Practice. The rationale of adopting these two theories is explained below:

Social capital (SC) assumes a crucial role serving as a vehicle that facilitates students learning and language exchange, within students' online community, in an online educational group.

Chapter Five: Research Methodology

Introduction

This chapter charts and justifies the methodological approach that is used in this thesis. It introduces the data collection method and analysis to answer the three research questions that are confirmed in Chapter One. The chapter commences by outlining some primary methodological concepts. These include the philosophical view and positionality that underpinned the study, research paradigm of the research, which is Interpretivism. Then, it moves on to elucidate the rationale behind choosing the qualitative approach, and the online ethnography approach in this stage, and how it fits to this study. After that, the chapter describes the research context along with the participants' background. Last, but not least, the chapter presents the sampling frame and how participants are recruited. The chapter contributes to the main thesis argument that Facebook educational groups are an asset to understand how males and females engage in online learning education and how their linguistic resources are constructed.

5.1. Research Questions

As it is mentioned in chapter one (section 1.3), this thesis settles in the following questions that are derived from my positionality (section 1.4) and from existing gap in the literature (chapter two).

How do students' dynamics in the group differ from males to females?

The purpose of this question was to explore the habitus of how students share their course-related materials in the group. The aim was known to be relying on these materials to gain profits, which are in this case, passing their exams. Meanwhile, this question addresses the role of this group in creating a community of practice among students.

2. How do students harness symbolic capital that is conveyed linguistically in their Facebook group?

With respect to the second question, the way students practise their linguistic capital (repertoire) will be described. These practices will be addressed based on what students, share, post, and comment on the Facebook group, with a focus of their code-switching practices and language choice. Kabyle students of English have the full access to different linguistic repertoire. The other potential aim, this question seeks to look at the way students use their linguistic capitals; which languages they use and what factors drive their choices, and to offer a sense of their linguistic diverse when posting or commenting to each other.

3. How do students' dynamics in the group differ from males to females?

The main thrust of this question is to understand the communicative online practices of the Kabyle students in the group and how these practices vary from males to females. Sharing practices differ based on the online practices to understand gender self-representation the online communication

5.2 Philosophical Underpinning the Study

Elaborating on section 1.3, it is important to concede how personal biases, background, and experiences have determined the research design and the interpretation of the findings. Reflecting back to my PhD journey, I had some loose beliefs about the way the knowledge I had about my study can be developed and most importantly understood. By knowledge, I mean the social world, people in society, their values, their language dynamics, learning dispositions, and gender variations. Nevertheless, I have never thought about how this knowledge can be mapped out; does it set separately from the culture or does it emerge from shared assumptions and beliefs of a particular cultural context. Moreover, I have not considered that there is no way in engaging in any research without first thinking about setting a paradigm that implies my own beliefs and interpretation about the world. A paradigm according to Guba and Lincoln (1994, p.14) is 'the basic belief system or worldview that guides the investigator, not only in choices of a method but in ontological and epistemological fundamental ways. Cohen et al (2018) refer to these beliefs as a worldview. These worldviews consist of four research paradigms namely: post-positivism, constructivism, advocacy/participatory and pragmatism. (Creswell, 2013, pp.15). However, this does not mean that these paradigms are archaic and only limited to these set of beliefs; because paradigms are in ongoing evolvement and the reason, I choose to refer to the ones Creswell

(2013) identifies is that they are purely related to the qualitative studies, and this is what I am adopting to answer my questions. These terms are explained in the diagram that I have developed it below:

Figure 5.1. Mapping the relationship between ontology, epistemology, methodology and research paradigms.

Coming back to my study focus, the kernel aim of this study is to offer a deep interpretation of a complex phenomenon starting from an induction reasoning, i.e., from a specific observation about an individual to a general concepts and theories (Haradhan, 2018). Moreover, since Mertens (2010) claims that researchers, before conducting their studies, must examine their philosophical assumptions about the knowledge and the nature of reality to arrive at decisions which could be used in the research process, I believe that individuals can become empowered social actors of their own learning experiences, linguistic habitus, and cultural capital through their online practices on the Facebook educational group. In this way, I understand the learning and the language practices through the lens of social constructivism. The use of social constructivism worldview aids individuals to “develop a subjective meaning of their experiences”; the researcher’s role is to “make sense of (or interpret) the meaning others have about the world” (Creswell and Poth, 2018, p.24). To

probe the investigation of students' online practices, including their learning experiences and linguistic practices on a Facebook group, I intent to interpret different views regarding these practices. At this point, I should acknowledge that my interpretations were influenced by my personal background as a multilingual speaker, and a Facebook user. Therefore, in the below section, this philosophical view and my positionality underpinned the ontology and epistemology stance of the research will be presented.

The ontological assumptions are concerned with the nature of reality and how it is constituted; whereas epistemology refers to the forms of knowledge and it deals with the 'how' question; how this knowledge can be investigated/ acquired and how it can be transmitted to the others. (Cohen et al, 2018, P.5). Put it simply, epistemology deals with understanding the process of knowledge. That is, how knowledge can be gained and collected, on the other hand, ontology focuses on the assumptions we possess about the nature of knowledge and what exists (Grix, 2001, Richards, 2003). This study aligns with the interpretivist research design and online ethnographic perspective. Interpretive research is "guided by a set of beliefs and feelings about the world and how it should be studied" (Denzin and Lincoln 2005, p.22). The Interpretivism perspective originates from the philosophy of Edmund Husser's phenomenology as well as "Wilhelm Dilthey's and other German philosopher's study of interpretive understanding called 'hermeneutics', the latter is a tool of explaining and understanding a social issue. (Mertens, 2005, p.12; Walt, 2020). Therefore, the epistemological position of the Interpretivist paradigm is that the knowledge is created and explored through experiences, meaning it is constructed. (Scotland, 2012; Carr and Kemmis, 1986).

5.2.1. Ontological Stance

Taking the assumption that there is no single reality, my ontological worldview fits with the interpretivism paradigm. Male and Female students in the Facebook group hold diverse perceptions regarding their linguistic and sharing practices on the Facebook group, in different ways. Hence, multiple realities coexist as students in the group perform various practices, that also differ from males to females. The level of their practices is based on different levels of the learning style, the topic of interest in the group and the online network.

For this reason, I immersed myself in the field, investigating students' online practices, including their posts and comments.

Studying the language in general, and in bi/multilingual settings in particular, is generally agreed to be complex. As previously discussed in chapter 2 and 3, language is a discourse that symbolises the power and the culture of a society and as such, it is a mean of establishing connections between individual of speech community (Bourdieu, 1971; Makihara and Rodriguez, 2020). The meaning of establishing connections echoes to the essence of language, which is a social phenomenon; meaning that language is a matter of communication not a representation (Bo, 2015, p.88). Likewise, my study embraces the principles of social constructivism. This makes the study embraces the constructivism ontological position. My worldview perspective about how students construct their own meaning in relation to

5.2.2. Epistemological Stance

This research embraces the interpretivism assumptions as an epistemological stance. That this, what can be understood about students' online dynamics on their educational Facebook group is thought to be socially constructed. Interpretivism is an epistemological stance that investigates the nature of reality. Crotty (1998, p.8) describes it, as "how we know what we know". Further epistemology can be defined as the "acceptable knowledge in a discipline" (Bryman, 2008a, p13). The study is concerned about how we gain knowledge around the linguistic practices and gender variations on Facebook. Particularly, the study looks at how Kabyle students, males, and females, use their online dynamics and why their attitudes differ. In addition, the study focuses on how students' linguistic practices, choices, and strategies differ from each gender and hence how each gender shares the knowledge or the "truth" with each other on a social network setting. Bourdieu (1960) theorizes the nebulous nature of the reality by emphasizing that cultural disposition and the culture's taste form the reality/truth of individuals within society. This disposition is usually common between individuals who share the same social background, same ethnicity, class, nationality, and education. Reality, from its subjective perspective, is constructed by agents. It is "itself understood as the product of the aggregation of these individual acts of construction". (Bourdieu, 1987). Furthermore, as discussed deeply in the theoretical perspective chapter,

(See chapter 3), habitus is created and shaped by the society and as such it governs both the social actions of individual and their mind (way of thinking). (Bourdieu, 1977; Lizardo, 2004). Therefore, this study takes an interpretive epistemology that is based on a subjective view of knowledge (Potrac and Nelson, 2014; Willis et al., 2007). In other words, it is not surprising that the researcher personal background and experiences that derived from observing and interpreting a particular behaviour, linguistic behaviours in the case of my study, affect the study results. However, as a researcher, I am totally aware about any bias to maintain a robust research design. As such, “Interpretive researchers collect and analyse existentially experienced, interactional texts” (Denzin, 2001, p.42). Hence, by taking the interpretive epistemology, this study falls into the qualitative research design.

5.3 Choosing the Research Methodology: Qualitative Approach

Research methodology is a reflective practise that involves the process of selecting, evaluating, and justifying the research methodologies (Wellington, 2015). It “inquires into, documents, and interprets the meaning making process (Patton, 2023, p.3). The starting point of conducting any research begins with identifying research questions, which in their turn decides about what methodology to use (Flick, 2023; Creswell and Clark, 2018; Stake, 2010). Hence, the main aim of this research is to investigate the complex nature of students’ online practices and how these practices differ from males to females, through their learning (sharing) practices and through their linguistic dynamics that they perform. In this regard Creswell (2013) claims that qualitative research is a process of inquiry that is used to explore a social or human problem in a natural context. Crucially too, Merriam (1998, p.6), concludes that qualitative research methods are grounded in the idea that “reality is constructed by individuals interacting with their social worlds”. The study therefore embraces the qualitative research which seeks to explore an in-depth narrative of individuals’ perceptions and experiences, as it is firmly based on a constructivist epistemological understanding of the nature of the reality (Silverman, 2005). Furthermore, Ivey (2023, p.22) argues that “qualitative research is concerned with the systematic investigation of people’s experiences, attitudes, motives, beliefs, and behaviours concerning a phenomenon of interest”.

Therefore, as a qualitative researcher, my objective is to gain elicited interpretations emerged within a natural setting. Doing this provides diverse viewpoints, which help in achieving a thick

understanding of the epistemological nature of the study using relevant data collection methods such as an in-depth interview and observation (Richard, 2003; Roberts, 2004). As such, it is important to emphasise the niche within the Kabyle context, as a marginalised community in Algeria, in relation to the qualitative research (Belabbas, 2020; Rouabah, 2023).

Therefore, this research adopts a qualitative inquiry which relates a socially oriented nature of this research, which focuses on understanding the quality, and not the quantity (Decrop, 2004). The current study focuses on more in depth understanding about the linguistic and the learning dynamics among males and females' students on a Facebook educational group. Alternatively, quantitative research can provide quantifiable data regarding the students' practices when interacting and sharing on their Facebook group, and how these practices differ from males and females. In the quantitative approach, researchers might enter the fieldwork with pre-defined hypotheses and theories (Ayers, 2007; Mohajan, 2020). In this research, I did not adhere strictly to any set of guiding assumptions, theories or guidelines (Braun and Clark, 2021). Rather, I let the data speak for itself. The coming section further discusses the reasons why I chose to adopt a qualitative approach over a quantitative one.

5.3.1 Justification of the Methodological Approach

To reiterate, this study aims to better understand how participants (male and female) students exhibit their learning dispositions in an online social networking site, particularly a Facebook group. Crucially, too, this study also aims to examine how these students display their symbolic capitals (resources) when engaging and interacting with their peers on the group. Since the aim of the qualitative inquiry is to understand certain aspects of the lived world (Richard, 2003, p.10), the qualitative approach is selected to describe and discuss the phenomenon investigated. According to Hennink, Hutter, and Bailey (2020) a qualitative study seeks to determine people's attitudes and experiences in their natural settings. It also identifies how these attitudes and experiences are shaped by the economic, social, and cultural contexts they belong to.

My study is related to multilingual users of languages, their linguistic practices on online settings and how these practices can be different from males to females. It also tries to gain a profound understanding of the role that the Facebook group plays among Kabyle students at the department of English at Mouloud Maammeri University of Tizi-Ouzou. Therefore, my

study abides the qualitative approach as it helps the study to develop insightful investigation of the online dynamics and gender variations in the group. In this vein, Hatch (2002) elucidates that what characterizes the qualitative inquiry is that it provides a deep understanding of a social phenomenon and the practices that influence this phenomenon. In a similar way, qualitative approaches are “more common in studies which investigate how people act and react when using CMC in social settings” (Mann and Stewart, 2000, p.4).

However, this does not mean that the qualitative research is seamless and does not encounter any challenges. There are some contestations within the literature about the limitations of the qualitative approach. For instance, Morrow (2005) argues that qualitative research is centred on subjective interpretation of data, which in turn raises a potential bias. Along with these lines, Taquette and Matta Souza (2022, p.2) further argue that “qualitative research is complex because the researcher is subjective in the society under study; he/she performs the research and simultaneously suffers in its influence being thus confronted with ethical issues because studies are contacted with human being”. This again highlights that the qualitative approach is “subject to researcher bias” (Morrow, 2005, P.254). Nonetheless, this disenchantment among scholars is partially debatable. Researchers need to be clear about their attributes in interpreting the data. Such attributes are generally shaped by the researchers’ contextual and cultural background. According to Al-Sadi (2015), these interpretative attributes are crucial in understanding the meaning of individuals under study. Therefore, to avoid any problems, researchers should carefully take into consideration the contextual background of the participants involved in the study. This idea goes in line with what Holloway and Fulbrook (2001, P.99) refer to as “context-intelligent”, in which they emphasise on the researcher being included and involved in the participants’ context. As far as the qualitative data analysis is concerned, qualitative research is generally time-consuming, and this is due to the various processes that involves (Denscombe, 2017). Yet, I consider this claim as a strength because the laborious process that the qualitative research process takes, is the result of an in-depth exploration. Furthermore, time can be managed and controlled. As such, during the process of data analysis, I managed to overcome this challenge by setting a timeline and follow it through the whole process of this research. This challenge drew my mind to the opposite nature of an online ethnography.

5.3.2 The Use of Online Ethnography

“As ethnography goes online, it is clear that the [sociological] fascination continues.”

(Murthy, 2008, p,839)

The ethnographic approach has been proven to be useful not only in the anthropological and sociological studies, but also it is extremely vital to study online practices, including language dynamics, and social behaviours in a particular community (Corona, 2017). Since this study is interpretative in nature which aims to understand and describe male and female students' online practices on an online setting, herein Facebook group, online ethnography as a research design is used in this research. Even though there will be no physical distance between the research and the target participants, the online milieu provides a deep and reach data via delicate and reflexive practices (James and Busher, 2009). In this context, ethnography is not linked to a particular culture, but it is related to social behaviours and of a group activity (Creswell and Poth, 2018; Wolcott, 2008). As the study focuses on exploring male and female students' online practices in negotiating their course-related materials on a Facebook group, online ethnography was adopted to achieve the study main objectives and answering the questions.

Ethnography is not a discipline but rather it is an approach adapted in many other fields including cultural sociology; social and cultural anthropology; organizational science; business administration; development aid; pedagogy; art; gender, cultural, and queer studies; and of course, design (Müller, 2021, p.3). Among the reasons that I chose an online-ethnography is that it captures the online world and experiences among users on computer-mediated communications (CMC) and the different types of social networking sites (SNSs). It can also adapt to create an online interaction among users as well as to understand deeply their social behaviours and cultures (Beneito-Montagut 2011; Jong, 2019). As such, online ethnography is rooted to core ethnographic principles of participant-observation while also seeking to selectively and systematically incorporate digital approaches such as social network analysis, data science and analytics, visualization methods; social media research presence and videography.” (Kozinets, 2015, p.3). The core elements of online ethnography are culture and

society. These elements according to Kozinets (2015), form “worlds of meaning”. Therefore, in order to comprehend the meaningfulness among individuals from a shared community, it is important to examine the way individuals interact and the way the influence of culture is figured out in their online practices. Ethnography provides a thick description about individuals’ social actions and relationships. Thick description is a core vocabulary in the qualitative research. The expression is coined by Clifford Geertz to describe the different perspectives of ethnography.

The main task of online ethnography is to describe how the use of learning resources and language practices on Facebook is related to their both social and even educational culture. Describing this will in turn help me as a researcher to further track, explore, and examine these practices and how they differ from males to females’ dynamics. Furthermore, it will also help me to draw a dichotomy about the way each gender (males and females) maintains their social relationships on a social network platform, Facebook. The task of ethnography in this similar vein according to O'Reilly (2009), Hammersley and Atkinson (2007) is that ethnography helps the researcher to watch the occurred phenomenon, listen to what has been said among human agents and ask questions. Ethnography therefore requires from the observer/ researcher to immerse him or herself in the human agents’ culture within the context of their online interactions via a sustained and direct communication with them.

Reflecting back to the introductory chapter of my research, I stated it clear that the fact that I have been raised in a multilingual community and I am a multilingual speaker. This helped me as researcher to immerse myself in the context and subsequently gain an in-depth explanation about individual agents; their use of code switching on online settings and how the strategies of choosing codes differ from males to females. For this reason, the online ethnographic research approach is used to understand and gain insights about a natural phenomenon that occurs on natural settings (Carson et al., 2001). Concerning the time span being used in my study, I consider a short-term span rather than long-term ethnography because the ethnographic approach does not necessarily require a long duration of immersion, as it is the case in the anthropological studies. In this vein, Pink and Morgan (2013, p. 2) claim that: “Ethnography is not always characterized through long-term engagement with other people’s lives. Rather it involves intensive excursions into their lives”. These excursions according to the same researchers include specific techniques such and methods

such as observations, a better selection of the participants and relevant data analysis tools. Additionally, Millen (2000) followed the same techniques when was investigating his research on human computer interaction (HCI) where he developed an approach that he termed “rapid ethnography”. Therefore, online ethnography is not inclined to a long-term immersion but rather it is related to the use of the aforementioned research techniques to understand people’s experiences.

Despite of the beneficial account of the online ethnographic approach, it has been challenged regarding the ethical boundaries and practicality. One of the criticisms is that netnography tends to be partial and subjective (Hine, 2000). However, this claim eliminates the nature of ethnography because ethnography, in general, does not focus on the approach being subjective or objective, but rather ethnographers themselves.

Another central challenge of modern ethnography that is conducted on an online environment is its divergence of concepts. Researchers on the field have used a multiplicity of terms to describe it. For instance, “Internet-related ethnography”, “social media ethnography (Postill and Pink, 2012), “virtual ethnography” (Hine, 2000), “webnography” (Horster & Gottschalk, 2012), “cyber-ethnography” (Ward, 1999) and “netnography” (Kozinets, 1998, 2002, 2010, 2015). As a cub researcher, while I was reading the literature about individuals’ online practices, I got confused because these nomenclatures are not synonymous yet distinctive and each researcher in the field has used a portmanteau term to describe the same concept and the same qualitative research method that occurs on the internet. However, this differentiation is totally intelligible as there is no unique concept to describe the internet and the methods that are conducted on it (Costello, 2017). But still, netnography cannot be used interchangeably with other terms since other concepts are too generic and broad as they encompass all the elements that are applicable to the online milieu whereas netnography is a distinctive qualitative approach because it focuses only on one aspect which is humans and their behaviour. In this matter, Kozinets (2015, p.96) claims that netnography is “more human-centred, participative, personally, socially and emotionally engaged vector”. This is exactly what my study is going to shed light on, students’ practices on online environment, particularly Facebook. **(see chapter 4)**. For these reasons illustrated above, my study relies on online ethnography to describe users’ online practices in relation to gender dynamics.

5.4 Data Collection Methods

The previous section introduced the method and the rationale behind choosing it. This section discusses how the research questions can be answered based on using specific methodological tools and strategies. These techniques according to Holiday (2016, p. 13) consists of “divergent research procedures such as, interviews, observations, conversation analysis, discourse analysis, and personal narratives”. Importantly, these research procedures were stemmed from the epistemological and ontological positions of the research, aiming to respond to the research questions (Crotty, 1998). However, this idea was challenged by Ormston *et al* (2014) in which they claim that it is challenging to find a research method that goes incompatible with the research endeavour.

Since this study concerns itself with online ethnography, as its core research methodology, online ethnography, just like ethnography, can combine a wide range of methods. Some examples of these methods are surveys and interviews (Kozinets, 2010). Because the nature of ethnography utilises observation as its backbone method (Trimmer and Wood, 2016), data of this research will be collected through participant observation and an-in-depth semi-structured interview.

This is known as a research design. “Research designs are procedures for collecting, analysing, interpreting, and reporting data in research studies” (Creswell and Clark, p. 58). These procedures and techniques were derived from the ontological and epistemological positions of the study and seek to probe the investigated phenomenon.

To probe the investigated phenomena; the online practices among males and female students on Facebook, it is necessary to select an appropriate research design that frames my research and answers my questions. Since the study is about users’ online linguistic practices, an online ethnography, netnography, digital ethnography (Pink *et al*, 2016), virtual ethnography (Hine, 2000) is employed as a central research methodology followed by participants’ observation and an-in-depth interviews as data collection tools or methods. This is followed by a discussion about sampling and the ethical considerations involved.

5.5.1 Participant Online Observation

After participants consented to take part in the study, the researcher began systematically observing and collecting data from their Facebook posts and comments. The start and end dates for collecting both posts and comments varied depending on when participants submitted their consent forms. As noted earlier, the study included both male and female participants, with a total of 17 individuals. Initially, I aimed to recruit 20 participants, evenly divided between 10 males and 10 females. However, due to the limited availability of male participants, the final group comprised 8 males and 9 females.

All texts and multimodal features shared by participants that demonstrated linguistic practices, particularly, code-switching practices, were captured as screenshots. A total of 235 screenshots of students' posts and 217 comments were collected, showcasing linguistic practices shared by students within their groups (see appendix, 6). These posts and comments primarily served as a medium for sharing educational materials and resources, conveyed through textual content and/or accompanying visuals such as pictures. Additionally, all related comments that participants responded to were collected for analysis. These posts and comments were revisited during the online structured interviews, where participants reviewed their selected content, herein posts and comments, and provided detailed explanations of their language choices. They elaborated on how and why they used specific languages to communicate and spread information to their peers within the selected group.

Significantly, Facebook posts served as a foundational element for observation, aligning with Robson's (2011) recommendation to "cross-check" participants' reported behaviours with their actual practices, thereby enhancing the credibility of findings through source triangulation.

Previous research on English use on Facebook has employed comparable data collection methods. For example, Dabrowska (2013) investigated code-switching among Polish and Hindi Facebook users, analysing its functions and typologies. Her study included 300 texts, divided between ten Polish and ten Hindi users, with a focus on posts partially written in English. Similarly, Kong et al. (2015) explored the language preferences of multilingual Chinese and Korean students studying in the United States. Their study incorporated a scenario-based online survey, semi-structured interviews, and a random selection of

Facebook posts, comprising two written in the participants' first language, two in English, and two that blended both languages.

Building on the methodologies of these studies, the researcher adapted participant selection criteria to align with the specific requirements of the current research (see Section 5.7.2).

To gain insights into the use of the linguistic practices among male and females' students on their Facebook group, it is crucial to explore participants' experiences in natural settings, which is why online observation was employed.

The main thrust of doing an observation in this research is to investigate and hence gain insights about live and natural dynamics of students' use of participants. What practices they uses and how these practices differ from males to females when sharing multimodal features. Another key rationale behind choosing observation is that this method can highlight the unmentioned and unvoiced issues that students may feel intimidated or uncomfortable admitting them in the interview. At this point, O'Reilly (2009) and Cohen et al (2011) claim that observation is designed in a way that prohibits the issue of "missed data" and helps in gaining a deeper explanation about the different social practices. Along with the observation method, ethnographers, in order to broaden their investigation, are allowed to combine other research instruments such as interviews (Bryman, 2008).

This approach allowed the researcher to observe real-time social interactions and collect authentic data. By observing actual behaviours, the researcher was able to gather information directly from participants' actions rather than relying on their retrospective or anticipated descriptions of past situations (Cohen et al., 2011; Mann and Stewart, 2000; Robson, 2011). Observation was an effective research method as it helped uncover the contextual elements of the phenomenon being studied, revealing complex interactions between the participants and the areas under study (Hammersley & Atkinson, 2007; O'Reilly, 2009).

In this study, the goal of observation was to examine how participants communicate and construct knowledge through the use of code-switching in their online interactions. Observing their communication provided the researcher with a deeper understanding of the contexts of these exchanges. Additionally, this method avoided missing crucial data and contributed to a

more comprehensive understanding of social practices (Cohen et al., 2011; O'Reilly, 2009). As Robson (2002; 2011) suggests, observation can serve as a tool for cross-checking data from other sources, since actions may differ from verbal reports. Therefore, observational data were compared with perception-based data from the interviews. Scholars like Cohen et al. (2011), Dörnyei (2007), and Robson (2011) question the validity of perception-based data due to limitations such as memory biases and participants' selective reporting. The use of observation in this research, combined with other methods, herein semi-structured interview, provided a more nuanced understanding of the studied contexts.

Data from participants' interactions on Facebook—both on Facebook post walls and comments were collected over six months (from September 2021 to March 2022). In this regard Mann and Stewart, (2000) and Cohen et al (2011) claim that despite being time-intensive, observational data offers rich and detailed insights into the situation being studied.

Online observation offers naturalistic setting O'Reilly (2009) and Cohen et al (2011). Unlike focus groups, which may be influenced by group dynamics and social desirability biases, online observation allows participants to behave more authentically in their natural environments. This can lead to more honest and genuine insights, particularly when participants are unaware that they are being observed, as is often the case with passive observation methods. In contrast, focus group discussions often lead participants to conform to group norms or feel pressure to agree with dominant opinions. Therefore, by immersing in long-term Facebook observation, the researcher became adept at identifying changes and capturing dynamic interactions through the linguistic practices of participants, via “screenshot data”

5.5.1.1 Justification of Using Screenshot Data

In the context of this study, the decision to focus solely on ‘screenshotable data’ elements that include text and images derives from practical and ethical reasons that are discussed below.

A crucial practical reason for excluding audio and video content relate to technological and methodological limitations. For instance, Audio and video data typically require specialised tools for processing and analysis. In contrast, screenshot content can be more easily handled

manually, or with widely available software, simplifying both data collection and analysis. Crucially too, this study has been constrained by the technology available to the participants, limiting the feasibility of capturing or analysing dynamic content such as video and audio, which may not have been easily accessible or reproducible across all participants.

From a theoretical perspective, the focus on screenshot data might have been aligned with the study's broader research objectives. As far as this study is concerned, it is not designed to examine website design, or visual content consumption. Yet, this study is concerned with capturing student's interaction as an illustration to their interview data. Thus, theoretical frameworks that emphasise visual/audio communication mostly prioritise static content, an idea that does not align with my research objectives.

Furthermore, ethical considerations also played a role in excluding the audio and video content. Audio and video recordings often carry privacy concerns, as they can contain identifiable information or sensitive data. By limiting the study to solely taking screenshots, the researcher intends to minimise ethical risks and simplify the process of anonymisation. For example, video content might require more extensive consent and permission from participants, and need careful handling to maintain confidentiality. The next section discusses the second research tool that is also employed in this study.

5.5.2 Online Semi-Structured Interviews

As discussed in section 5.1, the ontological and epistemological position is centred on the social constructivist paradigm. This paradigm suggests that reality is socially constructed by individuals, through the social interaction with others by means of language and discourse. Henceforth, apart from the online observation, the design of the study also includes interviews to gain in depth insights and understanding about males and females' students' use of languages and strategies they include when they code switch. Interviews are the most popular format of qualitative research in which knowledge, interpretations and views can be analysed. (Bryman, 2008; Jamshed, 2014).

Interviews were conducted to explore how participants online linguistic and sharing practices are perceived. As mentioned in section 5.5.2.1, analysing online observation alone may not

provide a deep understanding of the issues at hand, as they tend to offer only surface-level data (Creswell, 2014; Dörnyei, 2007).

To address this limitation, interviews were used as a complementary method, alongside the online observations for several reasons. First, interviews allowed for follow-up on interesting points that are captured during the online observation. Moreover, they provided participants with the opportunity to elaborate on personal information, experiences, motivations, reasons, and perceptions that obviously could not be fully explored through the observation as suggested by Cohen et al. (2011). Furthermore, since online linguistic practices are not always immediately clear, interviews facilitated a deeper interpretation of the data. Finally, interviews helped to validate the findings from the observations, as recommended by Bryman (2016) and Cohen et al. (2011).

Moreover, qualitative interviews serve as an opportunity for the researcher (the interviewer) to explore a phenomenon that are indirectly observable (Mackey and Gass, 2013, p. 173). Consequently, in this study, observing users' linguistic practices and strategies on Facebook might be adequate in terms of understanding their choice of language over the other language (s). Like such, interviews can be used as a tool to follow-up extra understanding from the online observation. In this vein, Bryman (2016) validates that interviews authenticate all issues that are investigated through surveys and observations. This is why the researcher decided to use interviews. Generally, qualitative interviews are grouped into structured, semi-structured, and unstructured (Richard, 2003). The former will not be discussed because it often falls within the quantitative data (Barbara and Crabtree, 2006; Bryman, 2016). For this reason, the study encompasses both the unstructured and semi-structured interview. This is referred to as "in-depth interview". This type of interview "more often refers to the both the semi-structured and unstructured interview" (Bryman, 2016, p. 201). They aim to obtain "a deeper understanding of the issue, its structure, processes and policies that permeate participants' stories ", [...] and hence, "they lead a more conscious awareness of the power of the social and organizational context of people's experiences" (Motta, 2012, p.548). In- depth interview is a flexible research tool in collecting data (Cohen et al, 2011) and it allows the interviewer to understand the interviewees' experiences, perspectives, and practices that might be undisclosed and ambiguous in another research tool, online observation in this case

(Allamrk et al, 2009). Because of its nature that advocates a flexible protocol, which allows the researcher to explain participants' attitudes, experiences, and beliefs, it can generate a transition from one aspect of the same discussed topic to another that may arise through the conversation (Ryan and Bernard, 2003).

The wide growth of the internet shapes the way we interact, the way we access to knowledge, and the way we conduct research. Regarding computer-mediated communication and social networking sites and their relation to interviews, digital or online interviews follow the same procedures as traditional media (Mann and Stewart, 2000). Moreover, unlike earlier, now an interview is not mandatory a face-to-face meeting. It can be conducted over phone, skype, or mail through various other forms of the internet and telephone without physical presence. (Showkat and Huma , 2017). Because the milieu of this study is in online, online interview would be suitable as the central focus of the study is investigating a social phenomenon, herein online linguistics behaviours and strategies using it. Along the same lines, Salmons (2012) points out that the main thrust behind choosing an online interview is related to the nature of the research. "Some researchers want to study behaviours or phenomena that take place online by exploring them in the kind of setting where they occur" (Salmons, 2012, p.12). Generally, the users of social media tend to be geographically dispersed in the online medium. Thereby, online interview serves as an opportunity for the researcher to approach participants virtually without a physical presence (Salmons, 2012; James and Busher, 2009).

It is worth to highlight that, at first, I was thinking of conducting face-to face interviews and travel back to Algeria to meet my participants offline. However, considering the situation of the corona virus disease of 2019 (Covid-19), the majority of researchers shifted, or rather were forced to use virtual/ online data collection methods (calls, video conferencing, and so on). This is due to the social distancing measurements and travel restrictions the government announced (Chandratre and Soman, 2020; Lobe et al, 2020). Additionally, with the explosive growth of technology and concurrently with the Covid era, the educational institutions, staff and particularly students have become more equipped with some social distant platforms and applications such as Zoom, WebEx, and Skype. Therefore, it is assumed that "their digital skills and competences have accordingly grown, consequently making their participation in online research data collection easier" (Lobe et al, 2020. P.2). Likewise, my participants are students of English, and the researcher assumes that they are familiar and aware of the use

of these platforms. However, the researcher, before deciding about which platform she is going to use, has first to prioritise each of the participant's choice of the interview channel, or the platform of the interview he feels comfortable with the most.

The interview schedule for this study is designed to fulfil the aim of the research as well as to suit participants' expediency. Once participants have agreed to take part in the study, a consent form and participation sheet have been sent to their personal email addresses, requesting them to complete, sign and return these documents. Since everything must be based on participants wants, the researcher will firstly discuss the time, setting and the date that accommodate each participant's availability to be interviewed. The interview, with each participant, lasts from 45 to 60 minutes. This duration is convenient for both the interviewer and interviewees as it minimises the fatigue. In this regard, Richards (2003) claims that participants will experience some sort of fatigue, as they may feel tired when the duration is more than an hour, that is why less than 60 minutes would be more suitable for both parts. After agreeing with the participants for a date and a time as well as the platform to conduct the interview, I reminded the participants that the interview will be recorded. The interview design will include three stages. The first stage of the interview will be devoted to explaining the research study, including personal/ educational background of the participants, alongside with their perspectives in using the Facebook group to study and how their languages on Facebook are practised. The second stage will consist of open-ended questions to engage into discussion with the participants, meanwhile, the research will take notes, record a video meeting as stated, or record the audio only. To reiterate, a total of 17 interviews were conducted online between September, 2021 to March, 2022.

One of the key advantages of interviews is their ability to facilitate a more interactive and dynamic exchange of information (Bryman, 2008). Unlike questionnaires, which provide static, predetermined responses, interviews allow for follow-up questions and the opportunity to probe deeper into a respondent's answers. This flexibility helps clarify ambiguities, explore unexpected insights, and adjust the direction of the conversation based on the participant's responses. In this way, interviews are better suited for capturing complex, qualitative data that may not be fully expressed through closed-ended questions in a questionnaire. Another justification for using interviews over questionnaires is the opportunity for immediate clarification. In a questionnaire, once a question is answered, there is no chance for the

researcher to clarify or elaborate further. In contrast, interviews allow researchers to quickly address misunderstandings, explain the context of questions, and encourage more elaborate responses.

5.6 Selecting a Research Site

This section provides a detailed discussion about how and why the research setting is chosen. Equally too, it encompasses the process of how participants are recruited and the way gaining access is secured. Moreover, this section outlines the researcher's positionality and the ethical considerations involved in this study.

Selecting a research site is a crucial step in any research as it is considered the main source of the collected data (Lanza, 2008). A research setting refers to the physical as well as the social cultural sites where the researcher bases his fieldwork (Given, 2008). As such, the setting of this study is based on one of the social media platforms, Facebook, which is a tool of socialising with others and entertainment and is expanding very widely in Algeria. The choice behind choosing to conduct this study in a Facebook group that shares course-related content is grounded in a multitude of reasons. In this regard, Boumarafi (2020) elucidates that the use of social networking sites among Algerian students, in academic fields, has been proven to be helpful in their educational achievements. Additionally, Boumarafi (2020) highlights that Facebook is the prominent social site where students can benefit academically, this is can be through creating private/ public groups among students or private chat groups (Boumarafi, 2020). Henceforth, the setting chosen of this study is a private official Facebook group created by students of the department of English at Mouloud Mammeri University in Tizi-Ouzo. Kabyle is chosen because it is regarded as both a sociocultural and a multilingual community (Solamz, 2018). Importantly too, the selection of Kabyle students of English as main participants of this study is because that these students possess a diverse linguistic repertoire, including languages/dialects such as Tamazight, Kabyle, Arabic, and French. Additionally, they have an English language proficiency, due to the fact that they are students of English.

Added to this, my rationale behind situating my research on a Facebook group is because it is the dominant social networking sites in Algeria. It provides an accessible and a convenient way to reach the target community. In this case, students' community. Ghounane (2021, p,83)

argues that Facebook becomes “a refuge for billions of users in all domains, such as education”. Importantly too, Ghounane (2021) adds that despite the less formal environment of Facebook, it is widely used among teachers to share their lecturers and other educational materials. In my case, I chose an educational Facebook group that is established and administrated by admins, who are also students. Below is a screenshot picture of the group under study.

Content redacted due to lack of consent to use .profile pictures in publication

Figure 5.2: Screenshot of the Facebook under Study

As it is shown in the above screenshot, the group under study name, in French “Département D’Anglais Officiel, UMMTO, meaning the official department of English language. The name of the group followed by two flags: the British and the American one. This is to indicate that the group accepts both the American and the British English when posting. Furthermore, the group has the feature of sharing posts, post reels, photos, and files.

5.7 Data Collection Procedures

Morrow (2005) maintains that the procedures, quality, and depth of the qualitative data are more crucial than the actual number of participants. This section discusses the procedures of the recruitment process involved in this study.

5.7.1 Accessing the Field Work

The research was conducted from September 2021 to March 2022. The online social networking group was selected as a main setting for data collection. Prior to commencing the

study, ethical approval was obtained from the University of The West of Scotland. Having obtained the ethical approval in August 2021, the chosen sample has been contacted. Seeking an approval for a study to be conducted requires careful plans and procedures. The processes involve providing essential details regarding the main objectives of the research, its aims, methodology, and the ethical considerations involved (Hennink et al., 2011). Additionally, to facilitate gaining access to the research setting, researchers should explain who they are and why they are conducting the research (Kozinets, 2018). Consequently, researchers, when entering the field, need to portray themselves as rigorous researchers by demonstrating a commitment to robust ethical standards that are relevant to their research (Cohen et al., 2011).

With respect to my case, I sought access from one of the group admins to seek access to this group. My aim was to gain entry to this group where I could find potential participants to recruit. For this reason, I contacted my friend, who has been a student at the same university, and I asked to suggest a Facebook group where students share their academic resources and concerns. She directed me to a lecturer at the department of English language who, in her turn, directed me to an official Facebook group of Kabyle students at Mouloud Mammeri University. I then was able to find some participants, who are studying English from different levels and from different fields to be observed. After the potential participants agreed to participate in the study, the research will send some documents to be filled by the participants. This includes the information sheet and the consent form.

Once my request was approved, I gained the official access to the group. With this access secured, I proceeded in writing a post on the group page where I introduced myself and provided a concise overview of my research, taking the ethical considerations that are explained in section into account. I then called users who might be interested in participating in my study, encouraging them to express their interests or reach out to me for further details. Doing so helps me to gain support and approval from the community. Students have shown great cooperation, expressing their interests not only in the topic itself, but also in the desire to establish their educational group as a research site for studies on online learning and language dynamics at the level of gender variation. As such, students' engagement and interests played a crucial role in garnering the necessary endorsement from these students' community.

5.7.2 Identifying the participants: Purposive and Snowball Sampling

The process of recruiting research participants according to (Eide, 2012) involves the researcher to identify individuals who meet the criteria for study and ask them to participate in your study. Likewise, the process of participant identification and sampling selection involved in this study is grounded and complex. This study relies on a non-probability sampling which includes both a convenience and a snowballing sampling. These sampling techniques are commonly employed to recruit participants in qualitative research (Gentles *et al*, 2015; Sukmawati and Sudarmin, 2023). These types of sampling are used together to recruit Kabyle students (the participants) who are males and females' students of English from various disciplines, which are didactics, literature, and applied linguistics. Initially as stated earlier, convenience sampling is used as an initial technique as it helps the researcher to recruit participants who are convenient and eligible for this research through my personal network.

Further participants whom I have interviewed have directed me to recruit other participants. This strategy is known as "snowball sampling". According to Parker, Scot, and Geddes (2020, p. 3), snowballing sampling is "one of the most popular methods of sampling in qualitative research, central to which are the characteristics of networking and referral". Coupled with these lines, the snowball sampling technique involves finding existing respondents who in their turn direct you to other referrals. This is why the term generally referred to as "chain referral sampling" (Johnson, 2014, Cohen et al., 2011). At first, it was a challenging task for me to find participants who shares contents on the group. However, after conducting four interviews with participants from the purposive sampling, I have managed to overcome this challenge as they directed and helped me to other individuals who actively share in the same group. However, this technique has been challenged for its "selections bias as well as a lack of external validity, generalisability, and representativeness" (Parker, Scott, and Geddes, 2020, p.2). Nevertheless, this does not necessarily lead to a biased representation; it could be referred to the trust building between the researchers and the participants. This is because if the participants refer to others, they are vouching for credibility and trustworthiness of the researcher, leading to higher cooperation and more openness. This trust can help mitigate responses biases and enhance the quality of data collected (Noy, 2008).

It was crucial that all participants were postgraduate students of English. My rationale behind the selection of this criterion was based on the idea that in addition to the linguistic capitals that Kabyle students had in their repertoire, including, Kabyle, Arabic, French and English, these students have a full command to other languages, such as German and Spanish. Accordingly, having the access to different language resources among participants is indeed helpful as it brings valuable linguistic capitals to the research endeavour. This linguistic diversity enhances the study's potential for exploring various language dynamics and enriches the data collection process. Moreover, when participants expressed their interests, I made sure that they are active in sharing in the group, by looking at their sharing practices on their Facebook group.

To reiterate, the kernel aim of this study focuses on the online practices shared in the group, all the participants must be active by sharing on the selected Facebook group. For their educational background, participants will be from different disciplines at the selected university. The process of selecting participants according to Lanza (2008) involves many factors to be considered by the researcher. These factors include the language history of the participants, their proficiency, multilingualism, education, gender, social values and so on. Hence, these were the same criteria based in which I select my participants.

Considering the number of the target population, and the nature of the qualitative research per se. The total number of participants is 17, consisting of 09 females and 08 males. As part of the recruitment process, I sought a balance between males and females. Nevertheless, I ended up with females being more interested and engaged more than males. Bryman (2012) argues that one of the challenges encountered by qualitative researchers is determining the sample size of individuals to be interviewed, preceding the collection of data. This is because it is "practically impossible to correctly know how many research participants should be interviewed before theoretical saturation has been achieved" (DeLuca, 2022, p.43). Importantly, in terms of the sample characteristics, it was nearly homogenous. The research participants were all multilingual Kabylis, students of English, and aged about twenty to twenty-four years old. Interestingly too, all the participants that I have interviewed were studying in the field of "languages" in their secondary school. As stated earlier, this means that they have been studying one of other foreign languages, which is either German, Italian, or Spanish.

When the selected participants agreed to take part in this study, I started emailing them the Participants Information Sheet and the Consent forms. As such, I took to negotiate with participants to schedule a meeting time for the interview, based on their preferences and free times. Surprisingly, this period of time was challenging and time consuming for me as researcher because participants took a long time to reply back and decide about the selected time that suit them. This long duration has been also related to the wild the fires that occurred in the Kabyle region in Algeria. However, this small period of time made me again reflect on the qualitative nature of my research study, in which I argued that selecting an adequate number of participants can be manageable in qualitative research. To this end, my participants were 17 in total. 17 (09 females and 08 males). In this regard, Morrow (2005) argue that the paramount consideration in qualitative is related to the quality of data in terms of its depth and thoroughness, rather than on the participants numbers.

5.7.3 Pilot study

Before conducting the actual fieldwork, and after being granted the ethical approval from the UWS Research Ethic Committee, and securing an access to research site, an initial pilot study of one month , for 2 participants, has been conducted as a part of the study in order to try out both the online participant observation and online interview. Importantly, piloting is considered useful, according to Byman (2016), to ensure that the researcher's questions clearly articulated and to validate the effectiveness of the data gathers methods. Equally, a pilot study for the interview will contribute to the success of the interviews it offers the researcher to rehearse the interview content and timing (Hackley, 2003). Moreover, piloting the interview will help the researcher to edit, refine or even discover additional questions.

Crucially too, The aims of this one month's pilot study period of the online participant observation is (1) to assure that the selected page/ group is appropriate for the study, (2) to help the researcher to be familiar with the group members as well as (3) to improve the data analysis skills that take the place in the computer mediated communication settings. This known as computer-assisted qualitative data (Kozinets, 2010). Four participants (two males and two females), aged between 20 to 30 years old, will be approached to took part in this study. Participants will be from different in different disciplines; didactics and literature and linguistics. The pilot study for the interview will be carried out along with the one-month period.

Interestingly though, during the process of piloting this study, the duration of the interview has been different from one participant to another. Participants find it hard to easily grasp my interview questions, the thing that led me to refine and simplify my questions. Yet, for the language use, although I gave the participants the total freedom to speak in any language they want, they enthusiastically appear happy to speak using the English language, as they are students of English. Nevertheless, code-switching has been marked from time to time, and they were aware of it. This happened usually when they could not find the exact words they want to convey in English.

5.8 The Process of Data Analysis

Since this study is based on the interpretive paradigm, the process of data analysis starts concurrently with the data collection. Therefore, when collecting data, the research will start, accordingly, breaking the data into codes and themes. In this study, in order to analyse the qualitative data, including both the online participant observation and the online interviews, I applied qualitative content analysis, which is suitable for all the qualitative methods including live interactions of individual, interview transcription, protocols of observations and even documents (Mayring, 2000; Scheufele, 2008). The aim of using this method is to figure out the emerging themes related to the student's online interaction, specifically the use of languages when posting and commenting, and the sharing dispositions that are manifested in the group. Moreover, to figure out how these sharing and language practices are different from males to females. The following section discusses the use of content analysis in this study.

5.8.1 Qualitative Content Analysis

Qualitative content analysis according to Bryman (2012) and Robson (2016) which highlights and emphasises the use of thematic (coding) or analysis. Additionally, Herring (2004, p.343) defines content analysis as "a research technique by which observations of discourse phenomena in a sample text may be made, illustrated, and discussed". Equally, Anderson and Kanuka (2003) elucidate that content analysis is invariably lined to texts documents in online communication. As such, the process of sharing and the interaction of participants in their online Facebook group is regarded as texts in which language is involved. In order to reach a

condensed understanding of the online ethnographic data, this research applies a qualitative content analysis to analyse both the online interview and the online ethnographic observation involved in this study. According to Kozinets (2010), the process of netnographic data analysis involves transforming the collected products (interview transcripts, fieldnotes, textual and graphical files, and screenshots) into a final research presentation. Data from both methods will be content analysed following the procedures presented by Milles and Huberman's (1994) that involve reducing the data, display it, and finally, interpreting these data and draw conclusions and verify it. Therefore, the coming section discusses the steps I followed to analyse participants' posts and comments.

In the initial phase of conducting the qualitative content analysis, I put a significant emphasis in transcribing the raw data and engaged in the 'pre-coding process' after conducting interviews and screenshots of posts of each participants. Subsequently, I took to screenshot all the posts and comments of participants' online practices and thoroughly engage in reading them on multiple occasions. I identified and highlighted sentences that appeared significant, supplementing them the interview data for the purpose of coding. Following this approach as (Robinson, 2006) has facilitate the organisation of the collected data and increase my familiarity with the materials (data).

5.8.2 The coding Process

A coding system according to Neuman (2004) is a set of guidelines that are employed for the purpose of categorising and documenting the content of source. The coding process involves two types of coding: the manifest coding and the latent one. The former type of coding is known as a structural coding because it focuses on the form and the structure of the text. the form includes words and languages ; while the structure in online communication refers to not only the language, but also the use of emojis, comments, and the languages that are used in each posts (Neuman, 2014 ; Herring, 2004).

On the other hand, the later type, herein the latent coding (also known as a semantic coding) concentrates on the implicit and the semantic meaning of a text. It aims at identifying and interpreting the post to find relevant themes (Neuman, 2014). Relatedly, Anderson and Kanuka (2003) assert that, an example of a latent coding, in the realm of online communication, could involve the analysing the tone and attitudes of a certain post. Tones

according to Herring (2004) are related to pragmatic aspects and norms such as humour and politeness. Crucially, following these processes of coding when analysing data has contributed to understanding of the online world and the nature of human online interaction (Anderson and Kanuka, 2003). Again, coding process has in turn three stages that are discussed in the next stage.

5.8.2.1 First Coding Stage

In the initial stage of analysis, which was categorising participants posts and/or comments based on the languages used by the participant. These categories were based on the language used and the emojis employed. In the following table, I have illustrated the first coding stage, including some screenshots that I have taken from the participants posts and comments.

Example of a participant screenshot	Language/ variety used
<p>The screenshot shows a Facebook post with a red background. The text in white reads: "Lokan andkhemem un grp de revision L1 Phonetics mashi bien ?" followed by a "🙄" emoji. Below the text is a "See Translation" button. At the bottom, it shows "You and 47 others" liked it, and "28 comments". Interaction buttons for "Love", "Comment", and "Send" are visible.</p>	<p>Algerian Arabic (Lokan) + Tamazight (andkhemem) + French (grp de revision) + English (phonetics) + emoji</p> <p><i>Translation into English: if we create a group to revise L1 phonetics, would it be better?</i></p>

<p>YAMMAN BOZZI حبيبي صحا رمضانك Like Reply 1y</p>	<p>Algerian Arabic (حبيبي صحا رمضانك) + emoji</p> <p><i>Translation into English: my dear, Happy Ramdan</i></p>
<p>Entre parenthèses kan: Y'aura pas deux examens par jours. Saha ftourkum. See translation You and 142 others 73 comments Like Comment View 29 previous comments All comments</p>	<p>French (entre parenthèse + Tamazight (Kan + French (y aura pas de examens) + Algerian Arabic (Saha Ftourkum)</p> <p><i>Translation into English: between paratheses: there will be no two exams per day .Enjoy your meal.</i></p>

Figure 5.3. Categories of participants posts based on the language used.

Importantly, engaging in the initial coding process was crucial as it helps me to ensure systematic categorisation (Huberman, & Saldaña, 2014) , involving the description and the interpretation of data when conducting the fieldwork. Crucially too, the process of categorisation helped me to analyse the linguistic practices as well as the sharing practices of each participant. Again, the analysis of these linguistic practices was mainly on the linguistic practices that are used by each participant, and not on counting or measuring this languages. Having demonstrated the first coding process that was mainly focused on the description and the categorisation of data, the second coding process will be further discussed in the coming sections.

5.8.2.2 Second Coding Stage

The second phase of the coding process in qualitative content analysis goes beyond description to a critical and rigour analysis, involving the process of narrowing these codes (Dörnyei, 2007; Robson, 2016). As such, in this study, I have reviewed all the posts and comments and illustrate them with interview data of each participants. This is to identify how male participants practices differ from male ones by looking at the use of emoji that each participants used.

5.8.2.3 Third Coding Stage

During this phase of the coding process, an in-depth examination was conducted regarding participants comments and posts that they share in the group. It helped me to understand the way each post or comment was employed, in terms of identity tags, humour, religion, and politeness. Additionally, it helped me to identify the formality, the tone, and interpreting meaning of each post. Moreover, during this stage of analyses, I have looked the sharing resources of participants to arrive at an understanding of how participants' sharing practices can be differentiated from other participants, in terms of picture they share, the internet memes as a cultural capital (Nisenbaum and Shifman, 2017) and how their use differ from each gender (Lukacs,2022). Additionally, I have looked at each the emojis participants used , in order to understand the emoji code as stated by (Evans, 2017). The bellow table, illustrates an example of the memes and picture used by each gender, identifying the tones.

Example of a participant screenshot	Category / type of sharing	Gender

	<p>Tone: Sharing for Humour (laughing emojis followed by Written comment . (informal)</p>	<p>Female</p>
	<p>Tone: serious Sharing to get share the information (formal)</p>	<p>Male</p>

Figure 5.4. Categories of participants posts based on gender sharing.

5.8.2 Thematic analysis

Although qualitative content analysis has some similarities with the thematic analyses, as stated by Bryman (2012) and Robson (2016), thematic analysis has been also used to “characterise particular perception and/or experience, which the researcher sees relevant to the research questions” (King and Harrocks, 2010, p.150). In this regard, thematic analysis can be defined as a robust a method “for systematically identifying, organising, and offering insight into patterns of meaning (themes) across a data set” (Braun and Clarke, 2012, p.57). In line

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with this study aims, I used thematic analysis to present a meaningful description of participants' online dynamics that they demonstrated on their Facebook group. Thus, thematic analysis lies on the capability to uncover unforeseen insights from the perspectives of diverse participants (Nowell et al., 2017). Moreover, Clarke and Braun (2017) and Braun and Clarke's (2006) argue that thematic analysis provides a simple, flexible and accessible analytical approach for novice researchers. Conducting a thematic analysis involves a systematic process with different stages to unveil themes within a dataset. The coming section discusses these stages.

5.8.2.4 Familiarisation of the Data

The first stage of analysing the data thematically is mainly a descriptive one. As such, this initial stage where researchers immerse themselves in the collected data to be familiarised with the data. This involves transcribing and reading the data multiple times. (Braun and Clarck, 2006). In this study, particularly after the process of transcribing interview transcripts, I engaged in a dual process by simultaneously playing the audio recording and re-read the transcripts. This has helped me to uncover pertinent texts and jotting down any relevant notes and key words. To reiterate, the interviews were conducted in English; however, some participants did code switch some words into French, which in turn made me to translate them into English. In fact, these words that the participants mentioned in French were not relevant for the data, but since I did word by word transcription, I have included them in the interview transcripts. In this regard, the process of familiarisation serves as a foundation for creating a solid basis when identifying relevant texts in relation to the data.

5.8.2.5 Generating Initial Codes

Following the phase of becoming familiar with the data, the second step is the creation of initial codes. during this phase, I revisited the notes and the highlighted texts I read in the first phase, to make sure that they are relevant so as to start coding (Braun and Clarck, 2006). The displayed data has been analysed manually instead of using computer assisted data analysis software such as NVivo. At first, started to use Nvivo , but then, I shifted to the manual analysis. The reason why I decided to use a manual analysis is based on the fact that learning how to use this software appropriately would take time and since I am restricted by time to finish this study, I preferred my data to be analysed manually. In this regard, despite

its efficiency in easily coding the displayed data, the qualitative software, NVivo, is considered as a “complicated software programme, the use of which requires considerable efforts with a steep learning curve” (Salmona and Kaczynski, 2016, p.9)

5.8.2.6 Searching for themes

After breaking the data into codes, I started identifying themes. The identification of themes in thematic analysis, involves systematic categorisation and interpretation of the meaning. As outlined by Braun and Clarck (2006), these stages involve arranging diverse codes into relevant themes and organise the potential coded data that are extracted within these theme. Thus, in this stage,

5.8.2.7 Reviewing themes

During this stage, a comprehensive review of all the identified themes took place. To elaborate, some themes have been eliminated if there was not enough substantial of data to support them. The purpose of this phase was mainly to gain a comprehensive understanding of the different themes within the data, their interconnection and the relevance to the data (Braun and Clarck, 2006).

5.8.2.8 Defining and naming themes

This stage involves that the selected themes should carry meaning. That is, each theme has to be supported by existing literature to increase the reliability and accuracy of the data. The benefit of this stage is to develop the capacity to decide what constitutes a theme and what is not (Braun and Clarck, 2006).

5.8.2.9 Producing Reports

In this last stage of thematic analysis, I thoroughly reviewed the selected texts to confirm and check that the identified themes, especially the rich ones, are relevant and aligned with the overall findings of this research.

5.9 Transcriptions

Following the data collection phase, the researcher starts the process of transcribing the interviews into written texts. This process is regarded as the first step in the data analysis

process, particularly when the researcher is the one who is doing the transcription (King, et al., 2018). Transcription is one of the fundamental process in qualitative research, Widodo (2014, p.101) elucidates that “it is desgined to capture and unpack the complicatedness and meanings of naturally occuring phenomena (e.g., values, beliefs, thoughts, experinces) in social encounters. Transcribing the data requires a repeated cautious listening or watching (Bailey, 2008); this process help researchers to familiarize themselves with the data thoroughly (Dornyei, 2007), and filter it by identifying the relevant data from the less important one (Gibson & Brown, 2009). This is known as the process of reducing the data (Cohen, et al., 2018). In the curreernt study, the process of transcription helps me to familiarize msyelf and engage with the interview (Gibson and Broen, 2019) and note down any initital thoughts or interpretations (Saldaña, 2016), and then reduce and summrize what is relevant to the study. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that the researcher, during the process of jotting down initial interpretations, must be aware of not let any initial thoughts lead the analysis.

Analysing and intrepreating data are two separate stages. The former process involves reducing, cutting and reconstituting data while the latter seeks to understand participants’ experiences and behaviour (Spiggle, 1994).

As stated earlier, the process of transcription started right after each interview was conducted. Each interview was transcribed using a regular verbatim transcription (full transcription), or Orthographic transcription as Braun and Clarke (2013) termed it. This means that every single word should be written down, this includes non- verbal nods like um, hmm, uh, filler words like emm, you know, like, pauses, and laughters. Verbatim transcription helps me to obtain a profound understanding of the unique experiences that the participants describe (Sebastian, 2021). Understanding these experiences help me to get insights about participants’ interests and perceptions about code switching. Similarly, it hepls the researcher to gain a full account of what the participants said with what word filler they use. Additionally, verbatim transcriptions in qualitative research according to (Bailey, 2008) “need to be very detailed to capture features of talk such as pauses and laughters as they invite different exchanges between the interviewer and the interviewees”(p, 128). For my case, when I ask some participants about why did they code switch from one language to another, they laugh, pause, and then share their thoughts. Laughters and pauses in here are considered as relevant data to understand the linguistic/code-switching practices of participants. Word for word transcription is time consuming (Braun and Clarke, 2013). According to Cohen et al (2018) and

(Seidman, 2013), an interview of one hour may take a whole five hours to be transcribed. At first, I spent 5 hours transcribing a 35 minute interview and this is because I kept a record of a verbatim transcription. Constantly, I started the process of deleting the irrelevant data, such as greetings and jokes in the warm up. This includes greetings and jokes that were used to minimize the level of formality during the interview (Cohen et al, 2018).

As I explained in previous sections, all of my participants are multilinguals. They are Kabylis/Imazighen who speak Kabyle/Tamazight as their mother tongue, MSA Arabic, French, English. The majority of them also speak German or Spanish. Consequently, since they are students of English who can speak and understand English, my interview questions were written in English. All participants showed a positive impression toward using English as the main language in the interview as they find it an opportunity to practise their own English language. However, I gave the participants the total freedom to switch to their mother tongue if they do not have the right word in English. Interviews were transcribed right after each meeting with my participants.

Aligning with the qualitative approach, the researcher allowed the participants to tell their experiences and personal experiences about their linguistic behaviours on online practices. Actually, permitting participants to talk about their experiences and perspectives, was a common technique in the ethnographic methodologies of semi-structured interviews. Doing such according to LeCompte and Schensul (2010), allows the researcher to gain a profound insights on selected topics related to the research questions understand the cultural and linguistic beliefs and perspectives of the participants (*see chapter 5*). Similarly, interviewing gave the opportunity for participants to discuss their own perspective in relation to their daily practices. One of the primary goals of the interview was to explore the way in which the online Facebook practices of Kabyle students of English is portrayed in relation to their cultural and linguistic habitus while sharing, posting and commenting.

The transcriptions will be stored on Microsoft Word document, printed, read multiple times and analysed. As a first step towards analysing the online interview data that begins simultaneously with the fieldwork, the analysis process begins by summarising the transcripts of the data separately into different codes and theme, then interpreting the data and compare them based on the interviewees' responses. However, during the process of

summarising, the researcher must be conscious of not missing any crucial data that is relevant to the study and to the research questions, aims, and objectives. (Hammersley and Atkinson, 2007). Moreover, he must expect any emergent codes and new categories of data throughout the fieldwork; this is due to the flexibility of the qualitative content analysis (Altheide, 1996). After that, the displayed data will be interpreted and lastly themes will be identified and theoretical conclusions will be drawn until the analysis reaches theoretical saturation (Chen and Bryer, 2012).

For the online observation, screenshots are very helpful as they capture a vivid image to help understand students' interactions on Facebook fully, their linguistic practices, as well as their sharing practices. Analysing the data will take the same procedures followed in the online interview; summarizing the screenshots content of the group page into codes and themes, interpret the observation data, and lastly identifying the themes that are highly relevant to the research objectives.

Likewise, I followed the process of traditional qualitative analysis that is used as a part of ethnographic analysis, particularly online ethnographic analysis (Kozinets, 2010). The reason behind this is that the core feature of my analysis is related to linguistic data and not anthropological ones.

5.10. Trustworthiness

In contrast to positivist and quantitative perspectives, essential criteria are required for evaluating naturalistic and post-positivist qualitative research studies (Guba and Lincoln, 1985; 2013). The interpretivism nature of this current study allows me to fully understand participants' behaviour on their Facebook group. On the other hand, as an interpretivist researcher myself, I should acknowledge that I am aware of the interplay of subjective interpretation from both the participants and my myself, which presents challenges in ensuring the trustworthiness of the findings, when interpreting the data. Trustworthiness is a quality feature for interpreting and appraising qualitative research data (Morrow, 2005). The concept of trustworthiness according to Guba and Lincoln (1985, 2013) encompasses four main criteria namely, credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability. Each of

these criteria are discussed in the coming paragraph sections. Credibility (internal validity, Patton 2014).

5.10.1 Credibility

Credibility is one of the fundamental parameters in qualitative research in which the research findings can be validated, and most importantly trusted. Achieving credibility involves several strategies. In my research, during the stage of data collection, I avoided asking my participants leading questions, by encouraging them to provide further details and give examples of any situations when necessary. This strategy was highlighted by Korstjens and Moser (2017), and Guba and Lincoln (1985), as a prolonged engagement. As the name indicate itself, prolonged engagement refers to the active practice and immersion of the researcher in the field, during the process of collecting data.

To maintain credibility in my findings throughout the data analysis process, I supported the identified themes with verbatim quotations, extracted from participants' original data. This step was important as it does verify if the interpretations of the data align closely with participants' words (Feredy and Muir-Cochrane, 2006). In a similar vein,

5.10.2 Transferability

Unlike generalisability, which is commonly related to external validation in quantitative research, transferability is a qualitative criterion which refer to the process of transferring research findings from a particular context which can be applicable and relevant to another context (Guba and Lincoln, 1985). In this regard, Holloway and Fulbrook (2001, p.547) assert that transferability involves that "the findings or theoretical ideas emerging from one setting can be transformed to similar situations or participants. In this study, transferability is achieved through contextualising the research setting, giving detailed information about the research participants and the research design. This can help the reader in determining whether any aspect of this study can be transferred and applied in another a different setting. In this regard, Guba and Lincoln (1985) assert that determining the transferability of research lies in with the reader's responsibility, not the researcher. To this end, I should argue that transferability urges the need for transparency in reporting detailed background of the research to enable readers make their own informed decisions about the accuracy and the relevance of the findings to their own research context.

5.10.3 Dependability and Confirmability

Finally, in accounting for dependability and confirmability, Riazi (2016, p.87) argue that, in qualitative research, the two concepts refer to the “consistency of the data collection instruments and procedures and the detailed description of the research process”. These were ensured through the use of “audit trail” technique (Lincoln & Guba, 1985) that provided a detailed record of the research process. It also gave a thorough description of the methodological choice, through a rich explanation of the different data collection tools that were used, followed by data analysis procedures, and research findings. Additionally, an in-depth account was given to the process of participants’ selection and recruitment. Ultimately, a transparent account of my positionality in this research was given to understand any potential sources of the researcher’s bias (Morrow, 2005; Maxwell, 2012). According to Denzin and Lincoln (2008), a researcher bias is linked to how the researcher’s role and influence can impact the quality of the research. For instance, in my research, I am familiar with the research setting, which is the Facebook group that shares course-related and educational materials. Additionally, just like my participants, I am a multilingual speaker myself who has different access to different languages.

Importantly, to minimise potential biases, I approached the study with a high degree of reflexivity, by openly acknowledging my insider position. Relatedly, “transparency” is a key too; I clearly stated to the reader the methodology I use to conduct this study at its outset (Holliday, 2010). Equally, to maintain a good quality of my research, I established a good rapport with my participants, giving them the permission to ask any questions they have about my study or the way I conducted it. In a similar way, I allowed my participants to ask for any additional clarifications or questions that they found difficult or challenging to fully grasp. Additionally, the supervisory teams served as external auditors, identifying any biases that might be held by the researcher (Decrop, 2004; Creswell and Miller, 2000). They have checked and corrected the processes of data collection, as I have also shared the interview guides, my pilot study, and also my notes on the coding. Doing this according to Riley (1996),

5.11 Positionality

This section acknowledges my positionality as a qualitative researcher in this study. Creswell (2014) asserts that researchers’ position in a qualitative study is a key as they-researchers-

are considered as the main data collection instrument for identifying personal values and biases at the initial steps of the research. Most importantly, too, Philips et al. (2013) add that the co-construction of meanings in qualitative research involves both participants and researchers. Therefore, researchers should recognise their roles as an integral part of the social world under study, acknowledging their own potential subjectivity. As indicated by Unluer (2012), qualitative inquiry is inherently marked by subjectivity. In this research, I acknowledged my subjectivity through reflexivity, by clearly identifying biases, behaviours, as well as feelings that could have an effect on collecting the data and interpreting it (Byrne, 2021).

Throughout this research process, I was moving across the ‘insider-outsider continuum’, as outlined by Hellawell’s (2006, p. 488). I considered myself as both insider (emic) and outsider (etic) Being a multilingual speaker and a Facebook user who shares similar status with the community, provided me with a better understanding of the participants as well as it helped me approaching the participants in an easier way. As it is discussed in section 1.1 and 5.7.2, I am familiar with the research setting and I know some Kabyle friends who helped me by suggesting other Kabyle participants. This allows me to be recognized in the research setting as it helps me to build a trustful rapport with the participants themselves and therefore be a reliable and known researcher. This in turn will boost participants’ will and desire to openly participate in this study by freely express their feelings about the investigated phenomenon. Another reason why I took an insider position is that the participants are aware that their linguistic practices are observed because in the second round of the interview questions (see appendix 1), the researcher will ask participants to bring back their Facebook memories that show their code-switching practices and their choice of codes. Consequently, I consider myself as an insider researcher (Robinson, 2000).

However, this study considers an outsider perspective in a sense that although I know some Kabyle relatives and friends, and I am fully aware of the linguistic/ sociocultural practices of their cultural background, Kabyle is not my mother tongue. I use the Algerian Arabic very often. This, however, does not provide any risk since the core aim of this study is to examine students’ dynamics and in an online social networking site, Facebook, and this can be easily highlighted through their writings on Facebook. For the interview, as stated in section, 5.2.7, all the participants are students of English. This means that the researcher, while interviewing

them, will use English as a main language. This takes me back to the study Eckert (1989a). Eckert was American ethnographer who had an experience with the Jocks and not the Burnouts. Interestingly, this helps Eckert to get wider beliefs about schools as well as about every single observation that highlights the adolescents' experiences in Belten high School (Eckert, 1989a). Likewise having an outsider position will allow me to gain an understanding of the investigated phenomenon from a wider perspective. Taking both an insider and outsider roles will help me to avoid any bias as well as to rebalance the interpretation of data analysis in this research and develop a wider understanding of participants' dynamics in their Facebook group.

5.12 Ethical Considerations

Conducting a netnographic study urges the researcher to carefully follow the ethical procedures involved. This section discusses the ethical considerations followed by the researcher. To minimize the risk of any ethical issues in netnographic research and to ensure an ethical research per se, I consider following Kozinets' (2010) guide. Kozinets (2010, p.140) points out four main procedures that should be taken into considerations while conducting an online ethnography. Firstly, "identifying yourself and informing relevant constituents about your research. Secondly, "asking for appropriate permissions". Thirdly, "gaining consent where needed, and finally, properly citing and crediting culture members".

Identifying yourself and the research entrée

Participants will be informed in details about the researcher and the research. This is related to the research entrée as well as the upcoming interactions. In order to inform the participants about my research, and myself the researcher will start disclosing her affiliation

and her degree to the group members of the online community. A written post on Facebook about the research and its areas of investigation will be posted on an official group page where Kabyle students of English use to exchange and interact on academic stuff that are related to their studies. While engaging into the research entrée and after the participants sign the consent form, ensuring that they are willing to take part in the interview and to be observed online, the research will briefly explain the research, its areas and the data collection procedures. I said briefly because it is not possible and impracticable for the researcher to provide a detailed explanation about the study (Cohen et al., 2011, Mann and Stewart, 2000). Yet, at the same time, the researcher must make sure that the participants are aware about the research main interests. For instance, I must make it clear that I am interested in the way males and females use language on Facebook, the way they transmit that language through posting and commenting and posting. Based on that, they are also aware that they will be interviewed and meanwhile observed based on their linguistic practices and the way they interact and socialize.

Permissions

Doing research in online settings, particularly, on social networking sites requires a permission from the targeted population. Actually, the fact that Facebook is a social networking service, using it as a main platform to for the research calls for ethical guidelines (Bryman, 2008; Kozinets, 2010). Thus, the researcher carefully read and examine the Facebook Statement of Rights and Responsibilities. In section 5 (protecting other people's right), it is clearly stated in the point number 7 that when collecting information from Facebook users, the research must, firstly obtain their consent and secondly, make it clear for the users (participants) about information/data from their Facebook will be collected and used. The research at this stage will ensure that their data (including audio recordings) will be secured and password-protected and merely the researcher who can access it. Still, participants will be informed that they have all rights to withdraw at any stage of the research and any sort of data could be removed if requested by them.

Informed Consent

As stated earlier, netnographic observations are carried out on the Facebook medium where the researcher informs the group members about the content of the study as they are remembered that they have the right to withdraw at anytime. Since (1) the intended research participants of this study are adults; they are all university students, (2) the desired group page the researcher choose to conduct her study is a private group page, informed consent is required for this study (Kozinets, 2010). The research will ask for the consent form using Facebook messaging options or emails, providing explanation about the study, as well as the research ethical considerations.

Citing and crediting

Like any research projects, anonymity and confidentiality in online research is important (James and Blusher, 2009). In this study, the researcher will look at the linguistic and the multilingual practices of participant when code switching on their Facebook walls and comments and how the use of code switching varies from males to females. Therefore, there is no need to identify personal information. The researcher will explain to the participants that their personal information and anonymity will be protected. As well as their Facebook posts and comments will be blurred when they are presented in the findings.

Chapter 6: Findings

6.1. “It is not just a Facebook group; it goes beyond that”: The Online Group as a Core Field of the Habitus Formation

Nested in the sociology of education and the learning dispositions within the online learning context, this chapter, which is the first finding chapter, focuses on the results generated by the qualitative methodology adopted. The data that are collected from a total sample of 17 selected participants, illustrates the process of qualitative content analysis (Milles and Huberman’s (1994) and semi structured interviews (Braun and Clark, 2016-2016). The focus of then being on learning practices and dynamics of the online Facebook group, *Département d’Anglais Officiel, UMMTO*, coupled with an interpretation of the online semi-structured interviews about their own perceptions towards this Facebook group. The participants’ profiles and their language choices offer key insights into how the Facebook group *Département d’Anglais Officiel, UMMTO* serves as a core field for *habitus* formation. The table below presents an overview of the participants' profiles, highlighting their linguistic preferences as well as their linguistics dynamics in terms of posts and comments within the group.

Participants	Language choice based on the screenshots taken	Gender	Number of Posts	Number of Comments
Lisette	French, Kabyle, Arabic (modern standard and Algerian Arabic), English	F	10	24
Massinissa	Modern standard Arabic, French, English	M	15	22
Kamy	French and English	F	7	10
James	Kabyle, Arabic, English	M	13	05
Zina	English, French	F	10	12
Nina	English and French	F	14	18
Dihia	Kabyle, French, English	F	10	08

Emy	Kabyle, Arabic, French and English	F	20	24
Efuru	French, English.	F	12	10
Sid Ali	Kabyle, French and English	M	39	14
Mahi	French, Arabic, English	M	9	10
Lydia	French, English, Arabic.	F	12	10
Mido	Kabyle, French, Algerian Arabic, English	M	22	18
Souhila	French, English	F	09	06
Belo	Kabyle, Algerian Arabic, French, English	M	12	07
Yanis	Kabyle, and French	M	11	12
Aziz	French and Kabyle	M	10	07
Total			235	217

Table 6.1 Participants' Profile

That is said, this chapter is concerned with learning practices that are produced by Kabyle students who communicate with the group by sharing and commenting on a variety of materials about their classes. The rationale behind organising this chapter into three sections is for the sake of clarity, presentation, and organisation. The first finding section deals with the “what” and “how” questions; what participants’ dispositions (behaviour and attitudes, towards the online Facebook group and the way are in which these dispositions are manifested in the group. The group is to be ***“It is not just a Facebook group; it goes beyond that, it has been a second home for students”*** (Emy interview). In this regard, Emy’s perspective suggest that the Facebook group has additional layers in which it is does not just gather students and that share course related materials, but it also creates a sense of relatedness and belonging among students.

Drawing on evidence from the interview and the online observation, the main argument that stems from this chapter is that this online education group, Facebook, provides a worthwhile and engaging agenda for students to get the materials they need to share the knowledge, seeking it, and contribute to it. In this way, I argue that the studied online Facebook group

provides an online Community of Practice among students (Wenger et al., 2002). Additionally, the group is considered as production for a quick revision for exams, in a way that it provides a strategic/pragmatic learning (Taguchi, 2018;2020).

The group thus, serves as a valuable tactic for exam, in a way that coalesces in a team spirit (Moghavvemi, et al., 2018), creating a sense of belonging among students who are also members in the group. Whilst Moghavvemi research did not seek to quantify students' positive and negative views towards Facebook as Al-Dheleai and Tasir (2017) did, but it rather focuses on the way participants socially construct the online Facebook as an education group through which their knowledge sharing dispositions are manifested.

Moreover, my rationale behind describing the group as a core field, in the sense of Bourdieu to the habitus formation is that the screenshot data (the online observation) revealed that participants' knowledge sharing and knowledge contribution in the group created a new set of learning dispositions. That is, participants use their own learning habitus that they gain from the offline class, which is the capital in this case, to share it with the wider community.

As it is stated in chapter One and Three (Page 6 and 3), the Facebook group that is under observation in this study is called "***Département D'Anglais Officiel, UMMTO***". Translation (Official Department of English). The group is created by students (Admins in the group) in 2015 and it contains 7.8K members. **Figure 6.1.** Provides a screenshot of the Facebook group. *Habitus Formation* implies looking at the online Facebook learning groups as a dynamic through which the notion of Habitus is developed. Bourdieu's Habitus is useful in understanding the practices of the social agents, students of English at Mouloud Mammeri University. The habitus in this study is used for a theoretical lens to explain the production of participants' sharing on the group, as well as how individuals' habitus is shaped by the learning/Education culture of Algeria. My participants' posts and interview answers about their dispositions and attitudes towards the online group of their department might be a barrier that hinder their learning outcomes.

The key findings reflected that participants used their offline context as a virtual seminar venue where they are able to log in to discover updates about their course made by their teachers in their departments. this group is a kind of a seminar venue where students can log in to find information about their department's updates. It provides a context for education to take a place, because in that situation they are not been taught by staff. It is a place to

deposit course resources. It is an online educator of individuals who are also members in the same group. This finding correlates with Shaw (2017) and Ulla and Perales (2021), where they argue on the potential benefits of using Facebook groups as an educational platform through self-study. It is like a compensatory venue (kind of library). Nevertheless, the study also reviews the possible challenges and drawbacks of the creation of Facebook group among university students in a way that they distract them from focusing and in depth study. Posting different notes can be puzzling for some students as notes themselves are depending on ones' own thinking and, therefore, they can be misleading. Nevertheless, this study extends Stephen (2014) argument in highlighting the importance of Facebook groups in promoting students' learning in India, in the field of finance and in other different disciplines.

It is arguable that these students who use the Facebook are strategic learners, and not deep learners.

In response to the first research question, my subsequent argument, based on what I have interpreted, is the use of Facebook education group is that the educational culture found in Algerian universities tends to be multifaceted in a way that is strategic and lacks a unified approach because some parts of are attending institutions in real life and the other type is relying on cyber learning. Students use Facebook groups to share their educational materials and express their generosity. This might be imported in socialism; Algeria is known that is a socialist country, therefore there is an emphasis on sharing towards the community . On the other hand, some might argue that the process of sharing notes degrades the quality of the university education. This is because all what students are experiencing is a series of handouts rather than interaction and this may hinder their learning outcomes.

Further, it can be argued that the behaviour of students legitimates their decision not to go to the actual face-to-face university because they are finding that they can continue their lifestyle by studying in times and space of their own choice. Hence, the actual university experience for them is a series of lecture -note. That is, it can be argued that these students are in fact not at university because all what they are doing is sharing lectures and notes.

Further, it can be argued that the Facebook groups are engaged in endorsing students to do not go to their actual university. In this sense, there are two actual groups: the online group and the offline. The overarching finding is discussed next in the following sections and subsections. Firstly, studying the online group in relation to the practice of the learning resources (capital) is emphasised. Highlighting the learning experiences and habitus found in

the online Facebook groups is also discussed. Secondly, sharing knowledge, including notes, and contributing to these notes by commenting and/or adding other thoughts seem to be promising among participants, in a way it facilitates the serendipitous learning, particularly during the Covid-19. Finally, the use of the online Facebook group as part of the learning experience can indicate how the students.

The Facebook online group is supportive, and it is considered as a setting where individuals who have not attended the lecture, physically, can go to get the education material that was presented in that lecture, from the online group. Thus, from the participants' point of view, the group is considered as part of the education experience, yet it is not part of the institution provision as it exists in a social networking space, Facebook. In another word, it is a creative effort by a group of students to provide a surrogate experience of courses, exams' planning, and results. It is therefore a kind of seminar venue where students can go to be reminded of what covered by the department. On the other hand, I should argue that this online Facebook group is not an educational saviour; it is a short-cut, and it shows a debated study practice. It encourages students to do not go to their actual universities and be reliant on others' notes. Nevertheless, this can be related to the learning culture itself, especially in the 20's, with the growth of the different social networking sites.

This is mainly because, in the online group, participants feel free in a sense that they are exercising these practices outside their institution policies and physical boundaries. These perceptions are related to the idea of the social culture of the university experience. The question asked in relation to the learning social structure is: what is the social culture of the university experience.

6.2 Exploring the peregrination of Kabyle students' learners: Facebook as sanctuary

6.2. 1 A lifeline Vs. a Shortcut: Exploring the Social Structure of the University Experience

All participants' dispositions and perceptions towards the online Facebook group seem to be influenced by their social culture and their university experiences. To understand students' social-cultural university experiences, it might be necessary to get glimpse revolved around participants perceptions and attitudes towards their group. Hence, this section presents a key

finding in relation to the social structure of the university experience. However, in some cases, students approach this Facebook group to with the intention of quickly getting the information without investing efforts to comprehend or critically think.

The online Facebook group appear to be a shortcut to success for students, yet it is not estranged. Participants asserted that they are studying in a collaborative way. Yet, the challenge is in the credibility of the notes themselves. Data showed positive attitudes towards the Facebook group, Participants assert that the group is a lifeline as it provides them with information and opens the gate for further discussion and insights. These finding echoes study of (Dabner, 2012), in which he states that the Facebook site supports the process of information-sharing within the higher education context It is considered as a lifeline platform as it helped participants to get information in advance.

***“It is another type of University”*: Normalising Facebook groups as a Cultural Capital**

The group serves as an “another type of university” (Emy’s interview), hence the title of this section. The other perspective of participants seems to see Facebook educational groups as a cultural capital that is gained through their interaction in the group, sharing insights, and engaging with educational content, where students can enhance their understanding of various topics, in a less formal way. For instance, Facebook creates less stressful environment, the factor that pushes students to think and express their thoughts, freely. As such, in line with Muls et al (2019) ethnographic study on Facebook dynamics among students, their interview data reveals that the social informal interaction leads students to contribute and be more interactive, with their peers. This serves as a potential to reinforce students to ponder and rethink. This has been further expressed by Nina:

“it is an informal group. It is so helpful and important for me. Actually, because they share some helpful stuff, planning of exams, sharing news about what is happening in the department, like they post every details in the group, instead of telling every individual. This is helpful and useful. For example, some of my friends yesterday posted some useful notes from his course. The notes were very helpful because they help they others to understand anything that they did not understand or miss in the classrooms. So it really opens a great discussion and interaction” (Nina, Interview, 16th March 2022).

This implies that the online Facebook group is a friendly environment. Students share their learning materials or their notes of the lectures, not only for those who did not attend the classes, but also for the sake of exam revisions. Nina, stresses that the social informal

interaction among students on their Facebook group offers a source of collaboration, that in turns leads to greater insights and discussion learning among students. On the other hand, as a challenge, this can be an extra push for the other students to be dismiss their actual universities. In addition, their interaction on the group is not monitored by moderators, their teachers (Hani, et al., 2014). This also suggests that the credibility of the shared notes by students can indeed lead to shallow or surface learning among students. Surface learning is a mechanical learning approach where least efforts and passive engagement are marked by students in order to pass exams, without any genuine efforts towards understanding (Cano, 2007; Entwistle and Entwistle, 1992).

Interestingly, some participants stress the role of Covid-19 pandemic in enhancing and creating a collaborative skills and engagement among students, who are members in the group. This is explained in the next section

6.3 The Use of Facebook Education Group during the Covid 19 Crisis

The Covid-19 pandemic has triggered a paradigm shift in education, urging institutions and educators, as well students to swiftly shift adopt an online platform to ensure uninterrupted learning. Linked to this study, Facebook appears to be a tool that fosters educational engagement through online groups. This section discusses a key finding of how the use of Facebook online educational group has influenced students learning experiences. by providing examples of participants' engagements on the group. This through the posts and the comment they post, and through the interview data. Hence, the following section examines how participants have experienced learning engagement and collaborative skills, during the Covid-19 pandemic.

6.3.1 Collaborative skills and inclusivity during Covid-19 pandemic

Bello, Zina, Sid, and Dihia, are the four participants who emphasised on the role of Covid-19 pandemic in affecting students' engagement and participation in the group, in an active way. The four participants' data revealed the shift that Covid-19 pandemic played in enhancing interaction and collaboration among students, Bello (interview), for example, reports that Covid 19, affects the "interaction" and the "corporation" skills.

Bello: our group is a great opportunity to stay updated about everything. Especially during the Covid period everything was closed in Algeria even the university. So this group became more interactive and cooperative too especially that everything was closed and we cannot meet each other at university (Bello, interview, 02nd April 2022)

This also reflects the flexibility and the engagement of participants in terms of treating the learning practices on Facebook groups like the way they do, or may better, in their home actual university. The fact that it helped them during the Covid era, in particular, the group seem to be again a lifeline through which students cope with the challenges of this critical period by advocating its normality to be reliable as an education platform. In this regard, Zina, recounts that:

“For example, during the period of Covid everybody was contributing. we publish the courses, just the handouts, and notes and everything that is related to our courses and department. all students try to help each other and make each other understand” (Zina, Interview, 24th March 2022)

The quote above also indicates that during the time of the Covid-19 pandemic, there was a notable sense of collective efforts and contribution among students, in the group. Educational materials handouts and notes of lectures have been accessible to all students in the group. This suggests that students feel included. This inclusion leads them to actively helping and collectively engaging to support one another and enhance mutual understanding in comprehending the academic content that is shared. Inclusive approach to education in social media has been identified by Aaen and Dalsgaard (2019). This study provides some support findings by Aaen and Dasgaard (2019) in which they concluded that Facebook serves as a “third space” which is defined by an accessible environment where both communication and learning content are visible to all members of the class, fostering a feeling of inclusivity. Similarly, Dihia adds that ***“Facebook has many options through which we can write, ask questions, and help each other. It is very useful for us as students” (Dihia, February, 2022)***. In this regard, the study supports evidence by Gals et al. (2023), that multimodality features in social networking sites is vital for ensuring comprehension, especially in educational material design as it enhances comprehension by making materials inclusive and accessible to students. This also shows that students are having an open mindset towards technology, herein, social media affordances to enhance education and learning among students. Therefore, the next section discusses participants mindset towards the use of Facebook as an

educational platform that is happening outside their classroom. Outside of the institution policies and physical boundaries. Yet, this does not mean that students do not go to the actual classes, but rather It is because this relate the factors like their own mindset and perspectives that are explained bellow.

6.4 Examining participants' mindset in online Facebook learning groups

All participants express a positive mindset towards using Facebook as an educational tool. But, *"not only education purposes, but also other purposes like communication with our colleagues"* (Lisette, interview, November 2021). Findings revealed that as an educational and social factor where students share knowledge by making a record of lectures and courses that took place in their classes, i.e outside the online group and creating bounds with their colleagues. Thus, the aim of this section is to focus on participants' perspectives about the group, both as educational institution and a social capital.

6.4.1 The Facebook group: an alternative education

Participants seem to have a shared mindset when it comes to sharing educational resources, such as class content, lecture notes, and class announcements. This shared mindset appears be related to sharing these reciprocities and in developing a sense of trust between the group members. They trust the ones who were present in the actual university. This is because they see the ones who share online as the ones who trust because they are studying the same modules as them. Aziz clarifies that:

"our group is a platform where everyone is available for each other. they will be in touch with their colleagues who are studying the same modules as them. For example, there are some lectures which we study in classes and other students volunteer to share their notes and lectures in the group so it helps students to revise, and ask questions"

Aziz's quote implies that is a group of students recreating the University as a place of knowledge-sharing. Students engaged in this through the role initiative without being requested by anyone in the institution. On the other hand, this implies that students seem to be merely opportunists, in a way that this education is dependent. It depends on others'

notes. This in fact will further open the discussion to The field in Bourdieu's description can be referred to as a "a field"

Additionally, my rationale behind referring to the Facebook group as an educational setting is that participants seem to consider the group as a "a seminar avenue", as it shares the university related materials: *"the group is like a gate to the university" Emy's interview.* Thus, this chapter discusses the different functions of the group in promoting students' learning outcomes, through sharing education stuff, administrative ones, and also in creating a social bound. My argument in this regard, is that this group degrades the university experience to access it in this marginal, or liminal way.

Interview Transcript or Screenshot

However, not all the sharing is supposed to be true. Sharing can hinder students' performance and negatively affect their mindset in learning, in a sense that students appear to be reliant on others', the thing that

Figure 6.1 Screenshot of the Facebook Group under Study

The screenshot above illustrates the group under study. *"Département d'Anglais Officiel, UMMTO, [Official Department of English, UMMTO].* UMMTO is an acronym that stands for

the name of the University, **University of Mouloud Mammeri, Tizi Ouzou**. As it is seen in the screenshot, the name of the group is followed by flags of American and the United Kingdom. This is to indicate that the language output of this group accepts both American and British English. An interesting thing though is that the name of the group, itself is written in French. This however does not mean that this group is restricted only to these languages. In fact, a hotchpotch of other languages is also used. Such languages are Arabic with its varieties, English, and Kabyle. Further, this group is private, and it contains 7.8k members. Interesting features are available, for instance, the “invite” bar feature makes it easy for existed members to “invite” their friends to join the group (Ahern, et al., 2016).

Shared Goals of the group:

All participants seem to have shared aims by which they joined this group. These shared perspectives are attributes to invite other students of English to join, share, post and comment their queries. The main shared reason behind the creation of this group was mainly for education and also administrative purposes. All the participants that I have selected were members in the group, they share their thoughts through the “post” feature or the “comment” option (see chapter 3, section 3.3). The importance of the group to participants’ experiences was evident in their interview answers. Interestingly, when asked about the role of the group, the participants were unanimous in the view that their group plays a great role in spreading speedily the information among students and share courses (Ainin, et al., 2015; Moghavvemi, et al., 2018) Such sharing concerns lecture notes and department updates. That is these common purposes are related to the concept of symbolic profits. Yet, it can be argued that they are parasitic on genuine education, in a way that they have two lives in two different spaces: Online and Offline life.

The question that might spring to the reader’s mind is how does this online group function as an alternative educational platform to facilitate students’ learning outcomes?

6.5. Functions of the groups: The Facebook group as an education alternative

As reported by participants, the Facebook group creates an educational atmosphere by shaping educational practices among students, this is through the post and the comment features. These purposes are knowledge-sharing, administration-sharing, and. Participants

believe that the group serves as a bridge to link students with their department. They post updates about their department, concerning timetables, and other administrative concerns, share their notes with each other by helping those who were absent, and. Therefore, the following subsections explains the reasons participants join the group and consider it as an education and multilingual terrain. Yet, taking advantage of these advances requires group members to be active. Being active in this sense can be applied and harnessed through the process of knowledge-sharing that involves the use of the different social capital resources. This is explained further in the following section.

6.5.1 Knowledge-Sharing Intention on Online Communities: A Social Capital Perspective

Knowledge-sharing attitudes in online social networking sites in this sense refers to the process of creating and interchanging of knowledge between members of groups (Moghavvemi, et al., 2018; Wang, et al., 2022; Tsai and Kang, 2019). In online communication, it involves two processes; knowledge-seeking and knowledge-contribution (Kang, et al., 2017 and Wang, et al., 2022). The former, as the names indicates itself, refers to the process of searching for the knowledge. It intends to bring further discussion through the comment section to exchange ideas, improve them, if applicable, and make use of them. The latter type, knowledge contribution, is strongly interrelated to the first type knowledge seeking in a way that in knowledge seeking users use their accumulated social capital resources to contribute to a given context based in a given subject. It is therefore the process of participating in the creation of the knowledge (Wang, et al., 2022). However, knowledge seeking in social networking sites can be a challenge in terms its accuracy and credibility because the provided knowledge, henceforth lecture notes, does not necessarily mean to be valid

Figure 6.2. Knowledge-Sharing in Online Communities

This behaviour contributes to students' success. All participants believe that for the students to gain symbolic profits, herein revising for passing the exams, sharing notes of the lecture that was offline in classes and resources will boost other understanding and enable those who were absent in a particular lesson to compensate and recap what they missed. In this regard, Sid Ali (online interview) agrees that:

Sid Ali: "When new students come to our department (.), when I was a member of the committee, I usually tell them to join that group because they will be in touch with their colleagues. For example, there are some lectures which we study in classes and other students volunteer to share their notes and lectures in the group, so it helps students to revise during exams" (23/01/22).

This demonstrates the importance of the group in gaining symbolic profits and developing a sense of corporation between members of the group. The profits that are gained in this regard are passing the exams. It also denotes that the group is not created only for exam revision or helping the ones who did not attend the lectures, it also created to build a community among students, via exchanging views and ideas. This result echoes other studies of Moghavvemi, et al., (2018) and Ainin, et al., (2015) in which they indicate that Facebook groups are an effective e-learning/teaching tool, in which they give the opportunity to its users to increase their academic performance and reinforce trust as the benefits or the profits they gain are mutual. This trust will, in turn, creates a sense of belonging and build a sense of classroom community (Duncan , 2016).

However, the process of sharing knowledge in Facebook groups can be viewed as a critical issue (Leonardi , 2017). This is because the sharing of notes tends to be subjective as students' perception towards something is not the same. In addition, the way students perceive the information can create a debate and breaks the trust. Yet, one should acknowledge the fact that information-sharing on Facebook groups creates an interactive atmosphere in which this

knowledge, notes-sharing in this sense, can be further discussed (Malik, et al., 2021) and this is through the knowledge seeking and knowledge contribution.

On the other hand, this is a form of education, but it might be also considered as weakened form of education because it is depending on the students' volunteers, making good notes. For example, if the student volunteer who attended the classes makes wrong notes, the revision will be impacted and damaged by the fact that volunteer people do not have a proper understanding of the lectures.

6.5.2 Note-sharing : a Form of Gift

Sharing notes in the group, under the form of exchanging objects. The gift is a part of an exchange system in Algerian higher education.

The perspective we have in here is a pragmatic perspective for joining the group because being in the group helps students to revise and, perhaps, pass the exams. So, the group, in this sense, is an exam oriented so far. On the other hand, the pragmatic perspectives suggest that the group develops a sense of education. This means that the learning experience is superficial. They are learning to get a degree, depending on others' notes. It can be argued therefore that their learning lacks the clarity as this marrow their learning environment.

Sid Ali's perspective above is also mirrored in an extract from Lydia who also agreed on the knowledge sharing function of the group by saying:

Lydia: "I remember during the exam period everyone shares his notes and lectures, questions that the teacher may ask, their experience. It is very helpful because if someone could not come to the university or was absent he or she can write a post or a comment for example by saying please could you share with me the lecture of today or so and everyone will help her or him" (29/02/22)

Lydia clearly argued that this community plays a vital role in enabling students for exam preparation when the person for whatever reasons has not come to university. However, it might be argued that although this seems to be a supportive function, it allows some individuals not to attend university. It erodes the university community by allowing people to pass exams without having been at university and attending courses expected in the form of an online situation where the entire focus was on passing the exams. In this regard, Lydia also recalled the exam period when students in the group volunteered to share their lectures to facilitate the revision process for other students. This kind of information-sharing enables students to exploit the information in the group and to exploit the members of the group who

attended the university. This idea also suggests that students Facebook groups can also be a space where students can meet “online”, exchange ideas, and even revise outside their institutions. In this sense, for students, there are actually two universities, there is the university that the students go to where they have got the material for the lecture, and quite separate from that, there is another online university, the online Facebook group, that is an exam factory that exists online.

6.5.3. Not only an Exam Factor, but also an Administrative Institution

In addition to information sharing in the group, the collected data also revealed that the Facebook group could also be used to share administrative information for students without being obliged to go the main campus. An example of this situation can be linked to the Covid-19 pandemic wherein students have to stay at home and get accelerated to the online world. this situation also, as it is the case in the knowledge-sharing, can involve all students’ members to cooperate by passing the information. Lydia for instance, seems to appreciate the role of the group in maintaining the relationship between students with other students and students with their department. This can also give them the feeling of confidence, connectedness, relatedness, and the motivation to others to also join the group (Bunce, 2018).

Lydia: “It was an informative group that gives information about what is happening in the department, the exams, the schedules, even the results of our exams. We are well informed in advance sometimes, this why I followed and joined the group” (29/02/22)

Lydia’s saw the Facebook group of the department of English as a useful channel to get information about administrative concerns such as the schedules of exams and students’ exam marks. The idea of “we are well informed in advance sometimes” means that before the department of English announces any kind of news (exam table, students’ marks), and stick it in the walls, teachers or the administrative staff may send it to one of the group admins and ask them to post it on the group, before it is published in the department wall. The screenshot bellow shows an example of Sid Ali, the admin of the Facebook group of the department shares a picture from his teacher to inform students about what is new in the department. This also denotes that their group serves as a news channel that keeps every student updated and well-informed:

Nina: "I think it is a good thing, because you are not obliged to go to the department to check up. It is just you get connected and you will know everything. I really want to thank our group department because the people who are working there are active members. I mean every information is posted in there I mean even the smallest information. Sometimes there are even people who want to share their courses" (10.10.22)

Nina was driven by her own mindset, which dictates that she is thinking the way she knows she understands. She looks like a good ambassador for a great support of social media culture. On the hand, Nina's answers denote the link between students and their department, and even the corporation of student in facilitating the process of spreading the information. The English department's teachers at Mouloud Mammeri University seemed to be aware of the group and its benefits in spreading the information among students. In this regard, Emy describes the group as:

Emy: "It is like a gate to the department whatever happed in the department we will be informed about it on the group. I myself post a lot if I have any questions in what concerns studies I go to the group and post. It is also a way to get closer to the other students" (15/01/22)

Analogous to Lydia and Nina, Emy's words suggest that that the group serves as the bridge that connects students with the department and also students with other students. The thing that allows them to post queries related to studies, and ask other students for help, without being obliged to go the university themselves. This implies in the Covid 19 era and the fires that occur in the Kabyle region when the things that lead universities in the area to close its doors. Students of department this use their group as a medium to revise by asking posting questions on the group and expecting to get answers through the comment sections. However, it can be argued in this case that Emy's interpretation seems to be self-serving. Therefore, it can be inferred that the chosen Facebook group creates a new way of communication between teachers and their students. These findings match a similar result as reported by Mus (2019), in addition to the fast and easy features that Facebook group offer students, it is also considered as an informal medium that allows students to share experiences, queries and humour. For the importance of the group, all students share a common goal of joining the group.

Students' posts and comments features in the group helped them to create, share knowledge, and make record of the lecturers that took place in their department. This helps members of the group to get an access to the things that they missed during their classrooms. The example

of Nina above adds another important role of the group in a sense that students in this group are working in a group-based way to support each other. It is basically a self-help group. How The group is based on pragmatic principles about passing the exams, and it is not actually about learning. However, Participants pragmatic way of sharing knowledge seems to be premised on revising and passing the exams. This allows them to harness and build their own social capital by using their resources when interacting with other students in the comment section. Nevertheless, the online Facebook group also aids students to stay updated about their department news, herein administrative news.

As an illustration of what has been declared by Lydia, Nina, and Emy, Sid Ali (see screenshot below) illustrates these points by posting a picture given by his teacher.

Figure: 7.1: A Teacher's Call for Students that is Posted on the Group

The picture to be posted was written by the module teacher, in which he asked his students about a revision session. It can be inferred from this picture that the Facebook group page is used as a channel that transmits the information between teachers who are based in the department of English, i.e., outside the Facebook group, and students who are members in this group. This implies that the Facebook group of "Département D'Anglais Officiel", facilitates the process of sharing the information and through its posting and commenting features. This also indicates that teaches are also aware of the existence of the group and its benefits in

spreading the information in a quicker way. This goes in line with Bowman and Akcaoglu (2014) in which they argue that the presence of teachers on Facebook groups reinforces students' learning environment and also creates a social corporative agenda among them.

6.5.4 An Online Classroom Community: A Social-Learning Agenda

As stated in the previous section, the knowledge-sharing function creates a sense of caring. Data also highlighted the importance of using the group to build a classroom community based. Classroom learning community on Facebook can be viewed as a group of students attempting to support and collaborate with each other to gain educational purposes (Duong and Pham, 2022). Along with the same lines, not only creating an e-learning environment, but Facebook group can also be used to create a social supportive platform for its members.

This is in terms of posting queries or asking for help from other students who are in the group.

Examples of this can be seen in Emy and Nina and Lydia's interview answers:

Lydia: "It is very helpful because if someone could not come to the university or was absent he or she can write a post or a comment for example by saying please could you share with me the lecture of today or so and everyone will help her or him". (October, 2021)

6.7 Comparing Online and Offline Interactions

In the light of what has been explained above, regarding the online groups, all the points were positive as all participants agrees on the benefits of their group. Not only from student-to-student perspective, but also teacher-student communication. Teachers' input can be seen under the form of administrative updates. This can be in term informing students about timetables, exam allocations, missing files of students. Hence, it is important to stress that not all the knowledge-sharing functions are necessarily the main purpose of creating the group.

To conclude, this section tackled the role of the Facebook group in facilitating the process of learning to students by shifting from the formal way of learning to an informal one. Regarding this point, the group constitutes a social networking place for students' learning and knowledge sharing processes, apart from their –offline – institution. Participants continuously reported that their Facebook group supports their learning outcomes and enabled them to

recapitulate what they missed in classes when they were absent. The group also helps students to revise for exams by posting previous exam topics and questions that might be asked during their exams, through the process of knowledge sharing and knowledge contribution. Findings reflected the important role of the Facebook group in sharing valuable content through the posting and comment features provided an alternative way of learning and knowledge sharing/building platform that exist outside an academic institution (RQ1). The results discussed in this theme are also important because they helped in opening the way to perceive the Facebook group as a social linguistic market where participants' use their linguistic social capital when posting a content and/or commenting (RQ2).

Chapter 7: Facebook Groups: A Platform of a Language Gain.

While the preceding chapter (chapter six) deals with how the online group is used for sharing educational resources, respectively this chapter further looks at how the Facebook group is used as a market to harness the linguistic resources and habitus. The overwhelming majority of participants used different linguistic resources to communicate their thoughts in the group, and manage prestige. The heterogeneity of practice was related to language choices, code-switching practices, and the emoji of each participant uses. These dynamics are observed when participants write a post on the group or when they reply to someone.

In the following section, I first provide the social psychology of a language choice in the Facebook group, then I focus on addressing the way Kabyle students' harness their linguistic capital and linguistic habitus in the social field (the group) to interrogate the research question 2. Patterns of their language choice, code switching, and semiotic elements (emoji) in posts and comments posted by students are data used to illuminate

this research question. For instance, the analysis of the screenshots of student's wall post and comments on the group revealed a wide range of different linguistic repertoires (capital) and linguistic habitus. This chapter argues that these linguistic practices are influenced by the linguistic capital that the audience brings to the interaction. Therefore, the aim of this chapter is to understand the dynamics of this social media environment, among Kabyle student, as a vehicle for enabling communication and social support. Moreover, the evidence presented in this chapter also gives insights to the third research question looking at the differences between males and females code switching practices, on the Facebook group.

7.1 Language Choice as a Form of Social Capital on Online Communication

Being raised in a multilingual community, multilingual users of languages need to make their own linguistic choice, from their linguistic repertoire. The research findings demonstrate that different language choices were used among participants when posting and/ or commenting on others' posts. In this section, I examine participants' linguistic repertoire in a selected example from their online interaction. In this section, I discuss participants' choices by reflecting on the observational data along with the interview answer that was generated. I will be focusing on the language used and how it is used in code-switching.

The finding revealed that the choice of language was mainly related to two main factors: the audience and the topic being discussed. Hence, these two factors are discussed below:

7.1.1 Audience written posts and/or comments

Taking the audience's choices into accounts when selecting a code (a language) was mentioned by most participants as a key factor that determines their language choice. Allan (1984; 1999; 2001) in his audience design theory, explained the relationship between the impact of audience on people's language choice. He argued that people's choice of language is an audience-lead. That is, when writing a post and/ or comment, users tend to choose a mutually shared repertoire the way that suits the audience they are targeting so as they, audience, perceive themselves as included and not excluded from the discussion (Liu, 2021). Therefore, the main aim of this section is to demonstrate, through both the interview data and the online observation, how the audience shapes the choice of the language. Lissette, Sid

Ali, and James are examples. The interview data revealed that selecting a language from their repertoire influences the person she is communicating with.

Lisette: I am a person who totally controls the language I am using Because, I mean, a lot of people, even we are using French since we are 6 or 4, lot of people struggle with French. So, why would I use a language that a person does not understand. I am trying my best to control the languages I use. If I' am writing to an Arabic person who does not understand English or French, I would understand, I would sorry, use Arabic until the end. And this is vice-versa for a person who does know French and does not understand English or whatever the language, I am trying my best to make the person feeling at ease and being comfortable with the language he speaks (September, 2021).

For Lisette, audience and their linguistic repertoire must be prioritised when deciding about the language choice. This goes in line with Giles (1992) Communication Accommodation Theory in which users' linguistic dispositions are affected by their conversational partner's communicative behaviour. Such behaviour is considered as a convergence strategy in which interlocutors in the Facebook group adapt to each other's language behaviour in a compatible way (Giles et al., 1991). Likewise, Giles, Coupland, and Coupland (1991) and Tsoumou (2019) argue that convergence technique is considered as a politeness strategy because it maintains a positive face between users and their audience, and minimises the social distance between the addressors and their addressees.

Lisette also provided further explanation stating that she is aware that many of Algerians in her network "struggle" in using the French language, therefore she avoids using French with them. In some part of the interview, when she asked about code-switching (**see section, 6.3.2**), Lisette also adds that in case the person she is communicating with does not know one of the languages she is using, she will stick to one language which that person understands and feels comfortable using it.

This suggests that the choice of language is affected by the audience linguistic capital and dispositions. That is, every language choice has to be based on the audience' own linguistic resources. Doing this will save both the language users' face as well as the interlocutor's face from any loss. Taking a target audience into account when communicating is regarded as politeness strategy.

In a similar vein, Mahy, in the interview data, expresses:

Mahy: "it is difficult to say it really depends on the person and what he writes in the post or the comment when I see a post written in English my mind starts to think using the language

that is written in the post when I find a post written in English or French or both inside my mind my thinking or my choice will depend on those languages as well.”

Similar to Lisette, Mahy also finds that his choice of language depends on the audience and their selected languages that are showed in their posts and/or the comments. Interestingly, he mentioned that seeing a post or a comment written in particular languages drives his thinking to implement these languages.

Both Lisette and Mahy quote seem to highlight that the language(s) that is chosen by the audience is the one that direct their choice of languages. This indicates the priority is given to the audience in which saving the face will be maintained. Moreover, the use of this is considered as a tactic for pragmatic communicative purposes.

James: “yes, it is always up to the other person that I am writing to. For instance, Arabic is the dominant language, if the person speaks Arabic, I will use Arabic as I have already told you that I can speak Arabic, if he understands only French, I will use French, if English I will use English. Thanks that we are multilingual @”

Here, James also stressed the idea that the audience plays an important role in determining his language choice. He emphasized the point that the intended audience is the one who dictates which language to use. He mentioned the example of the Arabic language, as a dominant language in Algeria and commented that he will use it if the person he is interacting with uses it first, the same thing applies for the French language. James mentioned these two languages as an example because they are the most used languages in Algeria, and also to express that he masters the Arabic language although he has Kabyle as his native language, and this is because he considers himself as a multilingual user of language who belongs to multilingual community. James’ interview expert goes with the same line with how he used his linguistic practices on the group.

Lisette, Sid Ali, and James showed an explicit awareness of the other person whom they are interacting with. Their online posts that I observed, and interview answers revealed that their linguistic repertoire is shaped by audiences in a sense that an audience is the one who drives language choices. These results attuned with previous sociolinguistic studies on language choice and audience by Tagg and Seargeant (2014) who claim that audience is considered as an important factor that influences language users’ choice. This also means that that these participants shared a common politeness strategy in a form of

The following subsection will discuss the other factor that shape participants use of languages when posting and commenting in their online Facebook group.

7.1.2 Subject

The nature of topic being discussed in Facebook posts seems to affect participants' own choice of language. A subject, according to Sari and Fasya (2021), is a sociocultural factor that dictates which language to use. Ekoç (2014) also points out that the subject in Facebook posts influence the level of interaction, for instance, it is argued that humours posts attract participants' attention, the thing that leads them to be more interactive. However, the focus of this study is on the language choice and not the frequency of interaction. How frequently people interaction is significant as it affects their social relationships, and it affects their social relationships, it will affect the choice of language . Interestingly, four participants believe that the factor that determines their language choice is the discussed subject.

Data emerged from both the online observation and interview answers also revealed that the language choice is associated with the content of the post in terms of the subject being raised in a Facebook post and/or comment. This can be supported by several students:

Efuru: yeah! Exactly on the topic. For example, when I write about something like, very serious and something ... for example when I am sad, I just want to speak using my mother tongue

Efuru seems to believe that the choice of language depends on the nature of the topic being raised/discussed. She expressed that when she wrote about serious concerns, she selects the Kabyle variety from her linguistic repertoire. Indeed, for Efuru, the choice of codes depends on the topic and its seriousness. For this, using one code, which is her mother tongue is the best choice to express her emotions.

This suggests that the code choice is linked to the field of practice, which affect language and its choice.

Nina: For example, as I am a student of literature, in groups that I follow, like groups of poetry, I always comment using English, that is because the content there is fully in English. But, when commenting to my friends' pictures and their posts, I use French.

In the example above, Nina highlighted that as she is a student of English literature, she also joined groups of poetry, the thing that dictates her choice (English in this case). However, choice when commenting to her friends' pictures is French because Nina, in some point of

the interview mentioned that French gains the linguistic capital in her online communication. They adapt themselves effectively to the

In another example:

Emy: yes, for example when tend to discuss with my friends about the English language itself we generally use English [...] when we discuss religion we use Arabic because it is the language of religion so the choice depends on the subject and people as well. These are the ones that determine your use of language.

It is evident that Emy associates her choice of language with the nature of the topic. In this regard, she specifies that when the topic is related to the English language, she uses the English language. When the topic is about a religion, she uses the Arabic language because it is the language of religion. Emy, besides mentioning the subject as a factor that determines her choice, she also, as noted previously, referred to the audience themselves as they influence her choice of language as well.

This suggests that female participants appear to be tied to the field being discussed.

With respect to the results highlighted above, it is evident that the choice of the language according to participants depends on two varied factors namely, the audience and the topic discussed on a certain Facebook post and/or comments. What is interesting though, is that this latter, the topic, was mostly highlighted by female participants while the former is related to male ones. If we go back to section (6.3.1.1), male participants asserted that their code-choice is bounded their audience and their linguistic repertoire except for Lisette who is a female participant who also agreed on audience as a factor that shapes her choice. However, the majority of the other female participants showed an awareness of another factor that was not raised in males' opinion. This factor is the topic discussed in students' posts and comments. Female participants constitute their choice based on the topic that was raised by other users. As a matter of fact, when it comes to participants' linguistic practices, the choice of language among males is not the same of females as each gender's choice is governed by a different factor.

7.2 Male vs. Females' Language Choice in online Communication

Data obtained through both the observation and the interview data suggested that the linguistic choice seems to be different between males and females. This is can be referred to gender segregation in language choice. Women are much more inclined to use more than one

linguistic choice, and this is because they have been described as less powerful gender in many fields, politics, society, and even economic. What is interesting in this study is that the differences are also showed in relation to the choice of language, which is considered as a source of empowerment of women. This is was expressed by Sadiqi (2003) who claims that gender performance of languages is determined by the availability of the linguistic choice, i.e. whenever there is a great access to more languages, women are much more likely to be empowered by choice.

7.2.1 Code switching

One of the linguistic practices that emerged, code-switching was the most apparent, and accounted for 150 posts and comments among males and female students. This section examines the code-switching practices selected by participants in their Facebook posts and/or comments in the group. The results show that all the participants exercised code-switching this is revealed in their online practices, throughout the online observation and their interviews. This commonality of using code-switching on Facebook platforms was also the case in Karan et al (2015) research, which showed that students who have different linguistic resources, use code-switching in their posting and commenting.

The following sections present the findings from the online observation in relation to participants' perspectives during the interview. Any script with other language than English will be translated. The first two examples were selected from Sid Ali and Midou's posts on the group. Their examples demonstrate a language shift between French and Kabyle. A reflective comment on this shift was expressed in the interview and it will be discussed after discussing the screenshots. (Sid Ali's example)

Admin Group expert +2 · 9 April at 22:18 · 🌐

Les étudiants du département d'anglais sont appelés à une assemblée générale qui se tiendra le lundi 11 Avril 2022 à 10h30 à l'amphithéâtre Matoub Lounes.

Les plus concernés sont les L2, L3 et M1 puisque leurs examens sont proches.

S tezmart nwen et passez une agréable soirée.

**Azul tt le monde
Je cherche l'Email n Mlle Oualiti prof de
français
Urgent**

Considering the data from the online observation, screenshots above illustrate Sid Ali' and Mido's code switching practices. Their written post was direct to the point, neither multimodal features nor emoji were used. Sid Ali used French and Kabyle to inform the targeted students that they have to gather in the Amphi theatre. His post was divided into two sections. He used the French language, and at the end, he added a sentence in Kabyle (*S Temzmart nwen*), followed again by French. Sharing in French, with some Kabyle words, makes all the other students understand what is written. Similarly, Mido in the second example greets his fellows using a Kabyle code "Azul", meaning Hi, in English and then he proceeds his switched to French to ask his question.

It can be seen that when participants use more than one language, they usually divide their status update into two sections, beginning with one language, greeting, using a mother tongue and switching to another preferred language, French in this case. The two examples above illustrated code-switching in which French is prominent and combined with Kabyle. Sid Ali made it clear in the interview that he used French and added some end- discourse sentence in Kabyle to make everyone understands what he is writing. In this regard, Sid Ali declares:

Sid Ali: *“when I want to comment or write a post, I usually use French and English. Because since we are a francophone country and the majority of Algerians do not speak Kabyle”*

The participant’s choice of French, as the frequent code-switched language for posting is because of the audience, who are also Facebook members on the group, and they are all from a francophone community where French is the second language, thus all student members in the group would understand it. By all, I mean, both Kabyles and Arabs because in the group, there are some students who study in Kabyle, but their ethnicity is Arab and not Kabyle. Thus, they found some difficulties understanding Kabyle. Therefore, by sharing the most important information in French, with a Kabyle ending, both participants tended to offer the information (Sid Ali) and ask a question (Mido) to their friends who also use and understand the French language. Interestingly, Sid Ali’s answer in the interview revealed an important factors that shape individuals’ choice of language which are the society and the culture. The fact that Algeria is a francophone country makes Ali to use it when writing a Facebook post because everyone in Algeria understands French, and also because of the French colonisation, French was presented in schools, the fact that leads Sid Ali to learn it at an early age:

Sid Ali: *“I have learnt the French language very soon, when I was a little kid, I learnt French quickly at a very early age. Since I watched anime and cartoon in French so I did learn it very fast. I was using French more than other languages”.*

What Sid Ali is insinuating in this extract is related to the Algerian history. The country has been an object to the French colonialism for 132 years, which resulted an influence on agents’ utterances. The participants assert their Kabyleness through greetings.

What is interesting in the online written posts of the male participants, Sid Ali and Mido, is that when it comes to greetings, they both use their native dialect, Kabyle. This is because greetings according to Duranti (1997) are considered as the product of individuals’ cultural competence which reveals information about the speaker. Inserting codes from Kabyle in this

sense, is a cultural competence participants use to disclose their identity. Findings suggested by Weirzbicka (1985), revealed that the greeting choice, in Polish and Australian English, is tied to language and culture. In contrast, Moradi (2017) studied the greeting behaviour in Persian and English discourses. His findings revealed that the greeting behaviour is influenced by the age and gender of the speaker.

Cultural capital is defined as the accumulation of knowledge, behaviours, and skills that a person can tap into to demonstrate one's cultural competence and social status (Bourdieu, 1986).

These studies were mainly centred to the pragmatics field; in a way that both of them focused on the speech acts of individuals when making greetings. The differences however, were in the factors that shape the greeting choice. Language and culture were the main factors that influence individuals' choice of greeting in Polish and Australian English, whereas, age and gender were fundamental aspects in greetings among in Persian and English. Moreover, these studies focus on the verbal and non-verbal greeting, yet, reflecting back to the current study, the main focus is not on greeting, but in the linguistic practices of participant in their online interaction. In the above examples, online observation data showed that participant started writing a post, using greeting in their native language, Kabyle and they switch to French. Greeting in this sense, is an identity marker.

Identity Tags: A Form of positive politeness

At the level of habitus, Kabyle was chosen as identity marker in participants posts, under the form of greeting. A key finding echoing a previous research (Prayitno, et al., 2019) is that greeting was used as a positive politeness strategy to show identity in Jokowi's Instagram followers when they comment. In terms greeting in posts, the findings of this study agree that greeting in students' posts, using their mother tongue, is a cultural competence. This cultural competence is expressed via a positive politeness strategy, greeting in this case, to show participants' identity and belonging. The following illustrate part of his explanation:

7.2.1.1 French with English

The use of French and English was also used by the participants, both males and females. However, data from the online observation has shown that the way males and females write the status update differ. This is in terms of emoji's use (*See chapter 3, 3.1.1*) and also in terms of the content. Examples, analysis and discussion of these elements will be presented as the following:

Emmy brings two new features to post, which are the use of emoji and the internet meme. The meme contains a French language. However, when she shares that post, she begins by locating herself as a humour person by using this emoji 🤔 (a face with tears of joy) and she wrote, “*Voilà how we can describe the situation*”. [Translation: “This is how we can describe the situation”.] It is possible that this way of writing, using emoji in posting brings a way of expressing humour (Bakir and Haji, 2019). Another possibility of the participant use of emoji

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is that it indicates their familiarity with the Facebook space and its affordance, meme and emoji in this case.

Emmy's switching suggests that she found it more appropriate to switch back and forth between French and English, using emoji. Another possibility of the use of emoji in status updates is that emoji could be used to present ones' identity as a humour person based in their posts (Ge, 2019; Li, et al., 2020). In other words, the participant is constructing her identity as a humour person by using emoji.

Similarly, but in a comment section this time, Massy used emoji that consists of laughing face, French and an English word. [**Translation:** "you see high level of stupidity"].

Massy used emoji 🤔 (a face with tears of joy) with a written language in French and English to indicate that he was truly laughing and the tone was not serious. According to Herring and Dainas (2017), using this emoji (face with tears of joy), transmit a physical action, which is laughing.

Another example was illustrated in Soumya's post where she also comment to a written using and English word (true), a French word (mais = but) and English again (don't know this), and she concluded with an emoji 🤷 (woman shrugging).

Soumia's reply was also portrayed through written language and an emoji (woman shrugging) to express a feeling of confusion as a lot of people do not know about the discussed subject in the post. I did not screenshot the written post that Soumia replied upon because the student who wrote the post was not among my participants. I therefore focused on the linguistic practices of the participants who agreed to take part in this study only, and Soumia is one of them. I asked her about this post and she replied:

Soumia: “@@@I used different language because those who comment above use the different languages too. I found the emoji is expressive as it expresses my feeling of confusion”

Soumia's reply indicates that using French and English was influenced by other Facebook users who commented in this post. Her use of this emoji 🤔 was portrayed to express a confusion. On saying that, it is questionable if Soumia would have received an answer to her “confusion”, by using this emoji 🤔 because emoji as it helps to convey our feeling expressively, it can also break and hinder the interaction by causing a mis-understanding among users (Tigwell and Flatla , 2016; Tigwell, et al., 2020; Anon., 2018).

However, a question that might spring to one's mind is the interplay between users use of emoji and their gender. That is, are emojis gendered? This issue is addressed in the following subsection. Thus, based on participants' observation and interview answers, it can be argued that the use of emoji in Facebook updates is akin to female participants.

7.3 Gender segregation and Emojis

This sentence is a mix of French and English, showcasing bilingual language use. Here Sid Ali used French and English to wish a happy new year to his freinds and teachers. The message conveys respect and positive wishes, making it appropriate for its likely social context. Further

more, addressing addressing both "enseignante et administrateur" shows attentiveness to the audience.

Unlike the first screenshot, in which the participant used French and Kabyle, the online practice written above indicates that the participant has changed the code-switching pattern and uses English and French, This is because the nature of the quotation is originally written in English by the American Martin Luther King. This is supported by a statement Sid Ali made in the interview when asked about the reasons that drive him use these two languages:

Sid Ali: I wrote the quotation as it in English because it is originally from the English and because it is expressive too. Then I added Bonne soiree camarades

R: why did not you finish the sentence in English as you started it in English?

Sid Ali: unconsciously. I just enjoy using more languages. I usually use French as the code switched language when I write in English, sometimes I use French without knowing that.

Interestingly, Sid Ali's examples show a dominance of the French language on his linguistic practices. This indicates the French dominance over the other language. His answers above reflect that his linguistic practices are shaped by historical and sociocultural influences (ethnolinguistic factors). For instance, Abdelhamid (2019) found that French gains a strong linguistic presence in students of English posts/ comments due to the French colonial period that lasted for 132 years. Being a linguistic form of capital, French gains an asset or a linguistic capital as a dominant language in online written posts. Surprisingly, the use of French, as a code-switched language in Sid Ali's online posts is also demonstrated in his oral communication. When I interviewed him, he raised an important point towards his use of French, using a code switching to French, the following extract illustrate Sid Ali's own view towards the use of French:

Sid Ali: I am not the kind of people who perceive that if for example I speak French means I am intellectual, quelqu'un qui a un certain grade de connaissance et tout (somone who has a certain degree of knowledge or so) I only see French as a language as the other language. A normal language that we can use daily

Here, Sid Ali raised an interesting point about the French status in Algeria and how it is perceived. This indicates that the participant is aware of his own choice. Besides justifying his use of French as the preferred language in his online linguistic practices (see section, 6.4.1), he also explains that choosing French is not a symbol of education; it does not reflect his

educational level, but he uses it because it is a language that is used in a daily conversation and it is considered as a legitimate language.

The second example is taken from Mido's post,

7.2.1.2 Kabyle French Arabic

The observation of the participants' practices demonstrated that in addition the use of French and Kabyle, French and English, some participants move beyond to use the Arabic language with its variety, the Algerian Arabic. Interestingly, some other participants associated their use of Arabic language as the "*language of Religion*".

The online linguistic practices of participants and their interview data will be presented and further discussed in the following examples from Lisette and Mido

[Translation: “like I said this morning, you are the pillar of this department, honestly this is my 3rd year in the university You have helped students as can be and I am among those students. Besides, you did more than enough, thank you for everything my brother, good luck...].

[Translation: "if we create a revision group of 1st year student of phonetics, would I better? Emoji" 🤔: Thinking face].

Lisette's comment and Midou's post revealed a certain level of a wide range linguistic diversities. These diversities of language suggest that participants seem to be appreciating their own linguistic habitus. In Bourdieu's word, "Habitus is both a system of production of practices and a system of perception and appreciation of practices" (Bourdieu, SSSP, p.19). In this regard, Lisette and Mido explain in the interview the purpose behind inserting these different linguistic resources, elucidating:

Lisette: *"Okay! I will tell you why. It is actually we got influenced by the French society which is actually got influenced by the American society and because of our family and cousins who lived there, we got these expressions, so this is actually let's say a French influence".*

Mido: *"it comes unconsciously honesty because Algeria is a multilingual country so using these languages is a normal thing".*

This explains that participants' use of different linguistic repertoire has stemmed from their socio-cultural environment. While Lisette justifies her use of French, Kabyle, Arabic and English by referring to her family's use of these languages, Mido related the use of these languages to the cultural status of Algeria being a multilingual country. This, again, indicates that factors like family and culture are factors that shape participants' code-switching practices. These factors were varied at the level of gender. Females for instance tend to use the same languages that their family uses. This is because females tend to be closer to their families that is why, in most of the cases, their language use is shaped by their families (

Tannebaum and Berkovich, 2015). Male linguistic preferences, on the other hand were related to the culture as multilingualism is a common practice in the Algerian culture. Additionally, it seems that inserting French, Kabyle, English, and Arabic codes simultaneously was only common in Lissette and Mido's online linguistic practices. This combination of languages in a same post were not highlighted by other participants. The question that may arise in here, is why? Well, this might be because they are bounded by their social and cultural capital in which the use of such four languages at the same time was not supported.

Therefore, the social (family) and the cultural (multilingualism) atmosphere seemed to influence participants' linguistic practices. The relationship between participants' and their own linguistic performances (practices) tend to be correlated with sociocultural factors, including beliefs, values, practices, and language use at home (González , 2001). Participants' cultural capital in this case, is gained through their families and their cultural milieu. This unconsciously will also impact their habitus.

Arabic

Across the whole data set, only male participants use Arabic, both the modern standard Arabic and the Algerian Arabic, in their online written posts and comments. For example Massy commented to his friend by using the Modern Standard Arabic and emoji [a laughing Face]. To express that he was laughing. This correlates with his interview answers when I asked him about his attitudes towards using MSA in this context.

Massy: “here I use Arabic as a humour, or in sarcastic way”.

It is notable that Massy's comment and interview answer develop a sense of humour through the Arabic language and the emoji he inserted at the end of the comment. The participant choice of modern standard Arabic to express humour and sarcasm might be because what he wants to transmit to other Facebook users has no counterparts in other languages. Therefore, in Massy's comment, the use of modern standard Arabic in this case is a strategy to express humour.

However, the use of modern standard Arabic is not restricted to express humour among female participants. Female participants use it to express religious expressions and encouragement to their peers. For instance,

Algerian Arabic (the dialect)

The Algerian Arabic was used as an entity to express cultural and religious fields. In example of this, the participant was wishing everyone “a happy Iftar” because, at that time, Algeria was celebrating the Holly month of Ramadhan. In this sense, Midou commented:

Translation: [“my dear, happy Ramadhan”]

The writing in Algerian Arabic performs a cultural function. Wishing the audience, a ‘happy Iftar’ using the Algerian dialect is a form of a linguistic habitus among Algerians to express cultural wishes. This function is controlled through norms that are made in the society. In addition, at the end of the sentence, the use of a red heart emoji (❤️) performs an emotional function to express love and wishes to his audience.

7.3 Gender Segregation in Participants Online Linguistic practices

Data findings of this chapter relates to the third research question, which looks at the differences between males and females code-switching practices. My rational behind not combining this section to the previous chapter is mainly for clarity reasons. I do not want to

“disturb the reader” with blocs of writing. Deriving evidence from participants’ interviews and online observation allowed for categorising participants’ linguistic practices in terms of gender variation. Therefore, data in this section will be used as a continuation of the second theme (research question 2). The data generated indicated distinctive use of linguistic practices among participants who are students. This heterogeneity of practice was related to language choices, habitus, and the emoji that each gender uses. These dynamics are observed when participants write a post on the group or when they reply to someone.

7.3.1 Male vs. Females’ Language Choice in online Communication

All participants seem to exercise code switching in their posts and comments, yet data revealed that there are differences between males and females practices in language use. This heterogeneity lies in the code-choice used by each gender, factors deriving these choices; Audience (6.1), topic (6.2), and the use of emoji (6.3). If we go back to section (6.3.1.1), male participants asserted that their code-choice is bounded their audience and their linguistic repertoire. However, female participants showed an awareness of another factor that was not raised in males’ opinion. This factor is the topic discussed in students’ posts and comments. Female participants constitute their choice based on the topic that was raised by other users. As a matter of fact, when it comes to participants’ linguistic practices, the choice of language among males is not the same of females as each gender’s choice is governed by a different factor. In this chapter, I argue that this heterogeneity occurred because men and women have different roles in society. Social role is one example of these roles as it depicts the differences between men and women in terms of thinking and actions (Krais and William, 2000). Additionally, this also highlights that women have historically been considered the "less powerful gender" in various spheres like politics, society, and economics. Feminist theory often argues that gender roles and power dynamics are socially constructed, and language plays a significant role in reinforcing or challenging these roles. Women’s inclination to use more than one linguistic choice could be seen as an act of navigating and potentially disrupting the rigid gender norms and power structures that limit their voice and agency (Lakof,2003; 2004)

The linguistic choice seems to be different between males and females. This is referred to

gender segregation in language choice. Women are much more inclined to use more than one linguistic choice and this is because they have been described as less powerful gender in many fields, politics, society, and even economic. What is interesting in this study is that the differences are also showed in relation to the choice of language, which is considered as a source of empowerment of women. This point supports Sadiqi (2003), who claims that gender performance of languages is determined by the availability of the linguistic choice, expressed this. However, these choices are varied and bounded by factors that again differ from each gender. That is, whenever there is a great access to more languages, women are much more likely to be empowered by choice. Language choice suggests that men code choice seems to be related to their identity. That is, their use of Arabic, with its varieties, Kabyle, and French. Women, on the other side, choose prestigious languages such as French and English.

7.3.2 Males' choice of language

Relying on Arabic, French, and Kabyle to post and/ or to comment seems to be tied to male participants. Kabyle and Arabic are used because they are two official languages in Algeria. Concerning the French language, its legitimacy in Algeria becomes a must to the point that everyone uses it. Males' use of official and legitimate languages suggested that they are shaping their personalities through these languages. Moreover, these languages are attributes to transmit and save participants' identity (Dastgoshadeh and Jalilzadeh, 2011). Put it differently, the choice of mother tongue between male participants is linked to the preservation of their identity from any loss. They believe that for their identity to be protected, they need to use their mother tongue. For instance, James asserted that using these languages is a part of his identity and that is he feels comfortable using them. In this regard, James agrees, ***"I mean I am more fluent in these languages. They are our official languages and a part of my identity. So, I use them fluently without being afraid of making mistakes"***. This demonstrates that that the use of the mother tongue is related to identity and as a tool to dispose of any kind of face threat, as the participant will not "make mistakes" because he considers himself as "fluent". Similarly, Ayman adds that ***"I usually use both my mother tongue Kabyle and Arabic, especially Kabyle because we are struggling if we don't use it will disappear"***. This probably because Kabyle is not spoken among Algerians. The majority of Algerians are Arabs and they rely on the Arabic as Kabyle, as a region, presents

the minority of people who speak Kabyle. Thus, using this language will save their language from being dead.

The other dynamic that distinguishes males' linguistic actions is the use of internet memes. The memes in this study are collected from males and females' participants linguistic actions when posting on the group and therefore focus on gender dynamic based in these practices. Based on the findings of this chapter, I argue that internet memes are female-dominated. The only expectations were Leo and Massinissa. These two male participants do use memes in their Facebook walls. Interestingly, the use of memes differs not only in terms of gender, but also in terms of the purpose. That is, according to what the data revealed, males' use of memes is related to cultural use (identity), whereas females' use is linked to pragmatic use (humour). These dynamics are discussed below

7.4 Gender Segregation in the Use of Internet Memes in Males' Linguistic Practices

This section focuses on the use of internet memes that are shared by participants. An internet meme is "a unit of cultural transmission" (Haig, 2006, p.51). Particularly, this section discusses the sharing of memes as a product of participants' social practices. The analysis of online posts in males' participants depicted that memes are associated with females use as opposed to males. This however, does not mean that males do not use memes at all. There are some rare cases in which males use memes, yet this use is related to serious concerns and not to humour, as it is the case in females' memes posts. This is line with Mahfouz (2021), who concludes that men, when sharing memes, appear to be pragmatic and less emotional as it is the case in woman's' memes. By serious, I mean that they use memes as a reproduction of their identity; males' participants tend to use memes in the group to refer to their identity as being African and Kabyle. Therefore, this section is organised as follows: Section 1.1.1.1 delineates males' use of memes in the group; section 1.1.1.2 describes females' memes practices.

7.4.1 Internet memes as a Product of Cultural Transmission in Males' posts

Sharing memes among males' participants is an online representation that is related to the concept of cultural reproduction. Kallunki (2022) refers to cultural reproduction as "the intergenerational transmission of cultural practices" (p.2). These cultural practices are the

outcomes of both the cultural capital and habitus (Bourdieu, 1984). Males seem to share memes in order to represent identity contents, this is why I linked their memes sharing practices to cultural transmission concept, that appears to be the main reasons of sharing memes among them. In this respect, the online observation depicts that the situation where males' use meme is related to cultural concerns, that is history and identity. Below are some screenshots taken from males' practices in the group that are taken from Leo and Massinisa. This aligns with feminist theorists like Hooks (2004) and Butler (1990) who discuss how cultural practices, including humour and media, can be spaces of resistance. While meme sharing often reinforces traditional masculinity, it can also become a space where men question or satirize their own roles in society, potentially destabilizing hegemonic notions of what it means to be "a man (Butler,1990).

Yacine and Massinisa seem to use internet memes to transmit cultural aspects of their identity. The screenshots above of the African map, and the YouTube of Berber (Tamazight) people are indeed symbolic. In this sense, they symbolise the Kabyle ethnicity and identity. My argument therefore is males, in their sharing, seem to be conservative in a way that each multimodal feature they post in this group is related to their identity. As shown in the screenshot of Leo, the map of Africa is an identity marker in which he discusses how the president of Russia describes Africa. When asked (during the semi-structured interview)

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about the purpose of sharing this meme, he points out:

“it is a topic that I wanted to discuss and see my friends’ opinion about this matter. C’est ... c’est une pire vérité. It is so disappointing to see a powerful continent like Africa perceived as nothing but un cimetière, c’est pour ça, j’ai aimé de discuter ce sujet avec mes camarades”.

Leo’s words depict his familiarity with his cultural capital in the African/Kabyle society. His interest in sharing with his audience (his friends on the group) seems to be embedded within his dispositions- habitus (Bourdieu, 1993; Bourdieu and Passeron, 1990). By saying that **“I wanted to discuss this subject with my friends”**, Leo appears to refer to another dimension of the Facebook group, Département d’Anglais officiel, which is the cultural dimension. This adds the fact that the Facebook group is not used for educational skills, but also for cultural practices. Cultural practices are the production of the different cultural skills and activities (Stevenson, 2017; Claro, et al., 2015). One of these skills is the internet memes (Iloh, 2021; Wang and Wang, 2015).

Similar to Leo, Massinisa’s screenshot illustrates a Youtube video about Berber people and ethnicity. Again, this implies that the participant manifests his cultural habitus by this sharing. This is mainly because he wants to contribute to the transmission of his culture through using the online platforms. When asked to comment on the video he shared, Massinisa expresses: **“@@@ there are people that may need this video. I am kind of shouting at those who are Kabyle and they use other languages in streets and all. This is insulting but not in a racist okay, I just wanted to say that Berber or Tamazight language is the native”**

A glance at Massinisa’s words can depict that defending the culture through sharing YouTube videos contributes to the renaissance of the Kabyle dialect and Berber-Tamazight language. Using Tamazight can protect the culture and the language from disappearance. This point was actually raised by Sid Ali:

“I would write in my post or comment: la langue Tamazight est la langue natale du nord Africain. L’Algerie a été toujours Berbers il n’a jamais été Arab. So I write it in French because all Algerians will understand it. So I usually use French to defend Tamazight in order to make the other Algerians”.

Sid Ali quotes seem to have a complementary relation with Massinisa’s claim. Massinisa’s cultural practices appear to be transmitted through multimodal features (the use of memes and Youtube videos). However, Sid Ali statement seems to be revolved around the use of linguistic practices, using the French language to defend their Kabyleness. Based on that, I argue that the linguistic cultural capital of males

To sum up, Leo and Massinissa seem to develop a sense of self-awareness in a way that they are constructing their identity through sharing memes. This result aligns with the study of Drakett et al. (2018), concluding that internet memes are features that lead to the construction of gendered identity through humour in the online milieu. Nevertheless, their study related the gendered online identity to humour dispositions, whereas, the present study revealed that it is related to cultural, mainly identity behaviours. This implies that gender does not only shape the body, but also it shapes the way individuals express their identity through the use of multimodal features. They feel at ease because they are familiar with the cultural milieu and also with the online platform, the Facebook group. Men appear to apply what they learnt from their social capital Livingstone (2008, P. 394), “creating and networking online content is becoming an integral means of managing one’s identity, lifestyle and social relations”.

Now that we have discussed males’ meme sharing in the group, that is highly related to identity, in the following section, I present the findings of women’s memes in the group.

7.4.2 Humour as a fundamental Mechanism in females’ Memes Posts

Female participants seem to associate their use of memes to one central aspect of pragmatic. This aspect is humour. Female participants, unlike males, share memes under the guise of humour or sarcasm. According to Knobel and Lankshear (2007), the concept of humour itself is associated with Internet memes. However, not all memes are intended to convey humour. This idea is supported by the data found in males’ memes (*see section 7.4.1*), in which males share memes to express identity. Female participants in the group appear to share memes for affiliative purposes. That is, their main aim of sharing memes is to amuse others (Martin, et al., 2003). Examples of these have been collected through the online data from Emy, Lily, and Tizi’s screenshots:

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copyright restrictions

Emmy seems to express her sense of humour to the group through inserting images and relating them to the exam situation. The screenshot includes two pictures one which is a triangle which is “le cours” (the lesson) and another messy picture which is “l’examen” (the exam). This is to indicate that the lesson is less complicated than the exam. Humour practices according to this example can be claimed to be a source of engagement among participants to demonstrate a jocular behaviour, which subsequently leads to a social interaction. This interaction will open the access to other participants to employ different speech acts, which includes pragmatics.

Another aspect of pragmatics in females’ memes post is Sarcasm. For instance, Tizi’s humour practice was embedded under a form of sarcasm. According to Taecharungroj and Nueangjamnong (2015), sarcasm is considered as one aspect of humour too. Another instance of sharing memes as a source of humour among female participants is to reinforce solidarity among members and build community. It is also used as a means of solidarity in helping students to cope with issues and feel relaxed (Sandberg and Tutenges, 2019; Newton, et al., 2022).

To sum up, gender appears to be presented differently, not only when interacting linguistically, but also when sharing memes, because memes are considered as multimodal. Multimodality in this regard, is defined as an interdisciplinary approach drawn from social semiotics that understands communication and representation as more than language and attends systematically to the social interpretation of a range of forms of making meaning” (Jewitt , 2013). This means that internet memes are considered as a form of communication that deals with the process of meaning making (semiotics), using natural language in communication (pragmatics). Meaning making and pragmatics in this sense are considered as social practice in which individual differences are negotiated through power. Individual

differences among males and females seem to be a key point in discussing the nature of power among participants. Transmitting identity in male's meme posts plays an important role in exercising power. This is because males, in their posts in the online group, tends to be "conservative". This idea has been supported by (Kerry, et al., 2021); according to them men possess a politic power and that their conservative behaviours are meant to support their social status in a society. Sharing identity-related memes is a form of social capital among male students. On the other hand, the production of humour is associated with females. Women, are portrayed as humorous to self-present their social status in the group. The next section of the finding discussion discusses power relation among gender.

7.5 Power of Memes in Participants Practices

Having briefly discussed the ways males and females produce their social practices on the Facebook group, in this section I explain how power is manifested in online communication. A meme "an idea, behaviour or style that spreads from one person to another in a culture" (Gumilang and Unikom, 2018, p.135). "Internet memes showcase a new kind of understanding of the world, and a new kind of creative and social outlet" (Börzsei, 2013, p. 24) Memes are regarded as a tool that symbolizes power. I examine how females use memes to express humour. Females use memes as a means to humour. However, the question that might be asked is why females do not seem conservative as males, why they do not use their mother tongue in their posts and comments.

7.6 Emojis in Data

Based on participants' observation and interview answers, it can be argued that the use of emoji in Facebook updates is associated with female participants. The use of emoji among participants is akin to females.

7.6.1 Emojis

As observed by participants, the use of emojis has been identified as a significant area of heterogeneity between males and females, serving as a distinctive feature of their online communication practices. As observed by participants, emoji usage appears to be more prevalent among females than males, highlighting a potential gendered pattern in digital expression. Crucially, this aligns with Herring and Dainas' (2018) findings in their sociolinguistics and digital communication studies. Herring and Dainas (2018) noted that

women are more likely to integrate additional cues, such as emojis, in their online interactions to add a layer of emotional nuance or clarify intent, which suggest that females are more inclined to enhance their written outputs with expressive elements to convey tone and emotion.

Furthermore, from a feminist lens, the use of emojis can also be seen as a form of resistance or empowerment. In spaces that often prioritize straightforward, "masculine" communication—such as the online world where assertiveness and brevity may dominate—women's use of emojis to add emotional depth or soften language can be a way to assert their voice and style within a system that might undervalue relational and expressive communication. This could be viewed through Butler's (2009) lens of gender performativity, where women (and other gendered individuals) perform their gender through communication practices, including digital modes like emojis.

Again, this trend is tied to the idea proposed by Lakoff (2004), who argued that women's communication often emphasizes relational and expressive elements., when used alongside text, serve to soften statements, add humour, or enhance understanding, which are communicative strategies more commonly associated with female users. Thus, I should argue This gendered divergence in online communication strategies underscores the complexity of how individuals adapt digital tools to align with their social and communicative preferences.

7.7 Students' attitudes towards using code switching

The previous step of the analysis focused on the "how question"; how participants' use their linguistic dynamics on their group. The findings of this section relate to the third research question (what question), "what participants' perceptions and attitudes towards code-switching as a strategy are. This section drew on participants' perceptions toward code switching by presenting extracts from their interview answers. Doing so will address a fair awareness of participants' own understanding of their linguistic behaviours and code-switching actions. While all participants utilise code switching in their posts and comments, their perceptions towards this linguistic practice were distinctive. Data in this section illustrates that participants' views towards code switching differs as their perceptions is influenced by many factors including gender, personality traits, and social skills and even educational background.

Overall, this section discusses participants' perceptions based on two perspectives, positive attitudes (section) and negative attitudes. However, dividing this section into these categories (positive and negative) does not necessarily mean that students did or will not use code switching in their online written outputs, if their attitudes were negative. This may mislead the reader and may drive them to ask if they have a negative perception towards code switching, then why participants' use it. This is not the case of this research because code switching is perceived as a natural phenomenon among bi/multilinguals (Villanueva and Gamiao, 2022; Halim and Maros, 2014) these perceptions might be the focus of future research. This denotes that participants code-switch and meanwhile they are aware of its pros and cons.

7.7.1 Code switching as a bridge: Positive views of code switching

Besides seeing code switching as a barrier to language development. Some participants also acclaim its merits. This demonstrates that their perceptions and their actions towards code switching are the same, i.e., they practice code switching and they possess a positive solid base towards it, the thing that helps them to confidently use it in their online practices. This suggests that participants' thoughts about code switching give them "*le sens pratique*" or the "*feel of the game*" to produce different linguistic habitus (Bourdieu, 1991, p.30). That is, their perceptions in this sense shape their linguistic habitus in producing different linguistic resources. Therefore, the bond between holding a positive impression towards code switching and practicing it seems to be powerful as agents' cultural capital, including their perception, is linked to their habitus, embodied dispositions. These dispositions or attitudes are influenced by the cultural capital (d'Almeida, 2016). For example, Dihia clarifies that:

Dihia: "Yes a lot there are some words actually that are not available in the Kabyle language nor in the Arabic language so we tend to code switch to French to express easy especially the scientific words. Especially with the new technology with the internet, books and globalization, the Kabyle language becomes old somehow that is why in ancient times some people believed that it doesn't exist. for instance the computer we don't have its name in Kabyle so I am obliged to shift to the French language which is "ordinateur" or sometimes to English language "personal computer" but in Kabylia there is no synonyms. These words don't exist at the time of our ancestors that is why they don't have equivalent in Kabyle. So we are obliged to switch to the French language as a facility to understand more and to express what do you mean".

Dihia's response suggests that code switching is valued because there are some words that cannot be expressed using the two official languages. Additionally, the participant seems to

know the rules of the game by showing awareness that certain fields require language alternation. She brings the domains of “technology” and code switching to French in this case is a necessity to fitting in like “a fish in water” to transmit the meaning clearly (Bourdieu, 1990).

In addition, code switching can save the face of the user’s face, i.e., in case the person loses the word in a particular language, he will shift to another language from his linguistic capital. This strategy is commonly used by multilingual agents, as can be understood by Mahy’s quote below:

M: “It is very helpful for me for communication sometimes you don’t find the word in a particular language and you have the exact word in another one so it is good so it is a source of pride somehow to have the access to many languages this is because we are multilinguals (February, 2022)

This extract highlights that Mahy was aware that code switching preserves his face from any threatening acts when he cannot find a word in a certain language. This suggests that possessing different linguistic repertoires to code switching to, helps protecting the face when it is at risk (Su, 2009). This is the case of Mahy when he tries to fit in by code switching to another language word. In addition, Socarraz-Novoa (2015) maintains that one of the main reasons of code switching is to save the face. Therefore

However, the above-mentioned perspectives might call for the following question: “can code switching be an obstacle. Are there not any obstacles?” This issue will be addressed in the following section.

7.7.2 Code Switching as a barrier: Negative attitudes Towards Code-Switching

Some participants argue that despite it sometimes facilitates the communication process; code switching can be hinder the process of language learning. This implies that for an effective language development, it is better to finish a sentence using one language. These participants believe that code switching might be an obstacle for “the new generation” who use social networking sites. Some participants seem to do not have the appetite for switching languages.

Efuru: “okay ... I think that, especially for the new generation. I think when writing something ... like if you start a conversation in Arabic, just complete in Arabic, if it in French just complete it with French. Because this affects the new generation, the ones who are reading comments on Facebook. Supposing that a 10-year-old child is seeing comments on

Facebook, how can he learn a language when the full comment is written in many languages. I think this is the negative side of code switching” (November 2021)

Efuru justified her negative view of code switching by relating it to the language acquisition and development of a child. According to her, seeing various linguistic capitals produced by other agents, whether in posts and comments, might be perceived as a habit for children who are still at the language acquisition level. This habit will influence their linguistic performance and behaviour in a negative way, as children will be confused because they cannot separate languages and hence this could be perceived as a disability and lack of competence (Espinosa, 2010; Paradis, et al., 2021). However, bi/multilingual children, from birth, possess a system that can differentiate between two separate languages (Byers-Heinlein, et al., 2010). Likewise, James seems to share the same point of view as Efuru, claiming that:

James: “in my point of view, it is a good strategy because it helps us to express ourselves, and get rid of any face loss. The negative idea is that we cannot develop our level using code switching. If we adopt using code switching, we cannot develop our language. I see it as (...) yes it is helpful and not bad, but it struggles us. If we use it everyday, we cannot develop ourselves in learning other languages” (November, 2021)

Analogous to Efuru, James’ words suggest that code switching can serve as a barrier to language development not only for children as Efuru believed, but also for “us”, adults, as code switching “struggle us” to communicate effectively. This indicates that this participant appears to be aware of the disadvantages of code-switching usage.

These adopted perceptions can seemingly give the negative influence of code switching on both children and adults, in terms of language development. However, as I contend in this section, this does not indicate that participants are not happy with using code switching because if this were the case, none of them would use it in their Facebook status and comments. Therefore, I am using this section not to discuss the negative outcome of code switching, as there are also positive attitudes (see section), but also to explore their awareness of this phenomenon.

Although some participants might find this “strange” that participants who practice code switching looks at it as an obstacle to language learning, this does not seem to be a contradiction, in contrast, it shows that code switching is natural among multilinguals and its occurrence happens subconsciously. Furthermore, the fact that participants the

It can be argued that participants’ cultural capital plays an eminent role in shaping their habitus and practices towards code switching. This type of capital is different from one person

to another. This suggests that practicing and holding a positive or a negative view towards code switching is natural since perceptions are varied. In addition, possessing a negative attitude does not mean that participants do not switch languages in their written online practices, yet it means they appear to be aware of their perception. Likewise, participants who alternate from a language to another seems to be confident in their use. Their feeling of confidence seems to help participants in voicing their perception of code switching through practicing it. In addition, participants who have a positive intention towards code switching believe that it helps them to save their faces when they lose a word in another language. In addition, alternating languages demonstrates that participants know “the rules of the game”, in a way that they code switch to certain languages that they do not exist in their native language to fit in.

Chapter Eight: Further Discussion and Recommendations

8.1 Introduction

The preceding section covered the pertinent literature, methodology, methods, research findings and discussions. This final chapter revisits the three research questions and builds on drawing conclusions based on the analysis and discussions presented in chapter six and seven. Yet, it is worth noting to mention that these conclusions were influenced by my own interpretations of the data, which in turn shaped by the existing literature and theory concepts, which are discussed in chapters, six and seven. Consequently, my argument based on this point would be if the study will be conducted in different contexts, then careful interpretation needs to be taken into consideration. Secondly, the research’s unique contribution to practice and theory will be highlighted. Moreover, this chapter points out suggestions for future research. To ensure comprehensive understanding of the research

process, it acknowledges the limitations of the study across various dimensions. Last, but not least, the chapter reflects on the research process by providing reflective thoughts on the research design and findings, in addition to my positionality as researcher in the field.

8.2. Findings Summary: Visiting and Answering the Research Questions

8.2.1 Research Q1: What roles does the Facebook group?

Findings in relation to the first question revealed positive dispositions among students vis-à-vis the use of Facebook group as a learning platform. Participants normalise the Facebook group being a shelter where they find their learning resources and collaborate with their peers in sharing the Information, seeking it, and contributing to it. The group also serves as an educational channel for students to share and exchange course-related materials. Participants reveal that the Facebook group is a shelter for the student, especially during Covid-19 pandemic, when all institutions have shifted from the offline-learning to the online- mode of learning. This openness and positive attitudes among students demonstrate the can reflect the evolving nature of education and the growing integration of technology in the pursuit of student's academic goals.

Participants in both the online observation and interviews focused on treating the Facebook group as an exam factory where they can revise via exchanging notes and asking/ answering questions. This use was not explicitly highlighted in the existing literature on the use of social networking sites in learning. However, the reliance on Facebook for exam preparation may discourage students from thinking critically. Students passively rely on a dependent learning, rather than being actively engaging students' critical analysis and innovation. Therefore, I shall argue that by striking a balance between collaborative and independent learning, Facebook groups can be a valuable resource to collaboratively revise for exams by engaging in educational/ institution related discussion to develop their skills alongside collaboration with online communities. The reason for this perception is explored in the following paragraph.

One important fact to note is that the state of critical thinking in the Algerian institutions is often absent. This absence is due to the traditional teaching approach students become passive recipient where they merely receive the knowledge. Data presented in Chapter 6 indicates that Facebook group encourages collaborative work and boosts critical thinking skills

among Kabyle students of English, supporting research by Abdul Majid and Abu Bakar (2021) among accounting students who study financial analysis courses.

Students have come to appreciate the value of Facebook groups as a complement to traditional classroom learning, recognizing their potential to foster a supportive and dynamic learning community.

This question was explored from Bourdieu's (1979) Forms of Capital lens. By exploring how the Facebook group plays as a *social capital* to gain *symbolic profits* among students, which is passing the exams, I attempted to highlight their limitations about the problem they may pose in degrading the educational system within the Algerian context. However, participants common perception about the use of this educational Facebook group is only linked to quantity rather than quality as their main objective was to revise from the educational resources that are available on the group, by their peers. It indicates that students are involved in a culture of knowledge exchange, or a culture of gift-giving (Mauss,1999). Mauss's concept of gift can be related to the sharing practices of educational resources in their online Facebook group. That is when students share their course materials, comment to others, they are giving the gifts of knowledge (Bergquist and Ljungberg, 2001). Therefore, the gift in this context is part of the educational resources that create this "microcosmic learning society". Where it offers a strategic learning outside of the higher educational institutions.

Sharing practices

The reliance on the Facebook group for exam preparation may discourage students from exploring other.

8. 2.2 Research Q2: How do students harness their symbolic capitals on Facebook?

Responding to the second research concerning how students use their symbolic linguistic resources in the Facebook group, the research findings affirmed a complex and constantly dynamics in terms of the linguistic capitals that are practised among students when interacting the Facebook group. Additionally, the research findings lend further support to Bourdieu's forms of capital theory which serves as useful framework in understanding the way students practise their symbolic capital linguistically. To reiterate, symbolic capital according to Bourdieu (1986), is inextricably intertwined with an individual or groups' credibility, reputation with and acknowledgement within a certain social environment. Moreover, Archer

et al (2015) and Hall (2003) represents a synthesis of three main forms of capital that are previously identified by Bourdieu (1986), this includes cultural and economic capital.

Interestingly, the findings from Kabyle participants' linguistic habitus revealed that Kabyle and Algerian Arabic seem to be a part of their identity.

Interestingly, from participants perspectives, English capital seems to be used as a professional language that enables students to explore their knowledge by commenting on a particular posts or content. Importantly too, using English to interact in a Facebook group among students of English is typically perceived as a valuable practice for improving language skills. It provides an informal environment where learners can engage with each other, practice writing and reading in English, and develop their communication skills in a real-world setting. It also encourages peer interaction, collaboration, and exposure to various writing styles and vocabulary. Importantly too, the choice of language appeared to be related to participants symbolic capital of language. when they interact with each other.

This also suggests the paramount importance of gaining a linguistic capital, not only as a mere ability to interact, but also as an embodiment to knowledge, identity, and culture.

8.2.3 Research Q3. How do students' dynamics in the group differ from males to females?

Communication dynamics in the group often exhibit significant differences between males and females, particularly in audience language politeness strategies, the use of memes, and identity expression. Males frequently adopt a direct and assertive communication style, which aligns with societal expectations emphasising dominance and confidence. This approach often manifests in straightforward language use and less reliance on politeness strategies such as hedging. In online interactions, males tend to use memes as products of cultural transmission, influencing them to share subcultural knowledge and reinforce group affiliations, such as those centred on humour. Memes in this context often reflect broader cultural narratives that validate or celebrate stereotypical masculine traits, such as competitiveness or self-reliance.

Conversely, females are more likely to employ polite and empathetic language strategies, fostering an atmosphere of inclusivity and relational bonding. This tendency is shaped by social norms that encourage women to prioritise harmony and emotional connections in interactions. In their online communication, memes shared by females frequently centre on

humour as a fundamental mechanism, often addressing themes such as shared struggles, societal expectations, or personal empowerment. These memes serve as tools for emotional expression and community building, creating a sense of solidarity among viewers. Furthermore, females' communication is often marked by a heightened use of emojis, demonstrating their preference for expressive and nuanced interaction. Emojis function as a visual extension of emotional expression, helping to convey tone and meaning with greater clarity.

These patterns highlight the ways in which gendered norms influence not only verbal but also visual communication styles, shaping how males and females interact within groups. While males may focus on establishing status or asserting individual identities, females often prioritise fostering connections and shared understanding. These dynamics are evident both online and offline, showcasing the interplay between societal expectations and individual communication choices in shaping group interactions. By examining these trends, we can better understand the broader implications of gendered communication in cultural and social contexts.

8.3. Research Contributions

This study aimed to address a gap in the literature about how Facebook groups can be a source of learning and collaboration among students. Additionally, this research focused on how Facebook groups can be used as a factor for language gain practice. Henceforth, this research has drawn on some pragmatic aspects to provide practical understanding of how Facebook groups are used to share learning materials and practice their language. to contribute to the existing body of literature in the realm of online learning and linguistic exchanges, among males and females, in the Kabyle context. Moreover, the results of the study contribute to the knowledge by generating interesting insights in relation to sharing the learning resources and practising the linguistic capitals, in social networking sites. Significantly too, in order to attain this goal, a theoretical/ conceptual framework is adopted to understand how users demonstrate their linguistic capital and habitus, their learning resources, including sharing notes, exchanging knowledge, contributing to this knowledge, and gaining skills through the

interactions they have on the Facebook group. Their interaction can be shaped by users' habitus and their individual dispositions.

While students engage in online social media, there has been a lack of in-depth qualitative research exploring the ways students use these platforms to enhance their learning experiences and manifest their discourses.

The research contributes to knowledge about the use of linguistic and learning resources on digital settings. The findings are of use not only to researchers in digital language dynamics and learning dispositions withing social networking sites, but also it helps teachers and students to understand the process of exclusion and inclusion in a society. Because, based on the research findings, there is a democracy that is excluded. But, again, then students are included; their inclusion is more shallow but they still get educated and get a qualification. The impact on society thus, can be seen through the dilemma of inclusion and exclusion, and these are things for policy to look at. My contribution to the national policy discussion is that creating Facebook group for educational purposes can have several potential benefits. For one, Facebook is widely used social media platforms, so incorporating it into educational policy could provide an opportunity to engage students in a platform that they are already familiar with and comfortable using it. Secondly, Facebook can be a useful tool for collaboration among both students and teachers. It can allow for easier sharing of learning capitals and hence create an online community of learners. However, it is also important to raise that using Facebook in education policy also raises concerns about confidentiality and credibility. Therefore, any implementation of Facebook should be done thoughtfully and with appropriate guidelines in place.

At the level of habitus, it needs to be viewed as they are formed through our socialisation experiences, and cultural backgrounds. Since the Facebook group market includes males and females' users, this research also contributes to knowledge about how gender differences, in terms of language habitus and learning dispositions, can be depicted in social networking sites. During my initial research for this study, I discovered that there was a relatively amount of existing literature on this topic. Furthermore, when I searched for research that explored the intersection of Bourdieu with topics such as online learning, language use, and gender, I found very little that addressed all of these areas, and none that fully answered the questions I had set out to investigate what role does the Facebook group play, what type of learning is there, and how does males sharing differ from females' ones; this is in terms of the linguistic

and learning resources. Hence, in the literature review chapter, I consider work that falls into the three separate areas of these study.

8.4 Recommendations for educational practitioners, curriculum designers and language teachers

Drawing on the data of my current research and on the study contribution that were discussed earlier, I would argue that educational practitioners, curriculum designers, and policy makers should make substantial efforts to help students who use Facebook groups for educational purposes in becoming proficient at navigating in such online spaces.

Referring back to the data obtained, Facebook educational groups offer a dynamic space among students who are also members in such groups, by enabling them to actively participate in discussions, share educational resources and assist each other in their studies. This led to encourage collaborative practices withing students. However, the effectiveness of these collaborative practices relies heavily on educators. Educators need to effectively raise awareness about the use of Facebook groups as a valuable tool for exchanging ideas and collaborating among students.

This study found that students perceive their Facebook group as an informal platform that offers students opportunities to exchange ideas in a collaborative way. Importantly, educators can use this idea to acknowledge the use of this informal learning space to supplement formal education. A practical approach to achieve this, educators should conduct orientation sessions at the beginning of the academic term to introduce students to the concept of using Facebook groups for academic purposes, explaining the benefits, expectations, and guidelines. During class time, educators could emphasise the benefits of using Facebook groups for collaborative activities, to enhance the opportunity for peer support. Although students are not instructed how to use Facebook groups for educational purposes, they were actively participating in expressing concerns, asking questions, share notes, and provide feedback to their colleagues, who are also members in the dame group. This idea could inform studies to explore the benefits and challenges for using the Facebook groups for academic purposes, enhancing our understanding of the structure and the dynamics of online learning communities. Moreover, conducting observational studies on Facebook groups that are used for academic purposes

among students would reveal data to understand how students interact within Facebook groups, identifying patterns of their behaviours, resource sharing, and collaborative learning. Significantly, too, the findings of this study revealed that there is a type of inclusion that is happening in the Facebook educational groups. Students' inclusions appear in the way they contribute to the shared knowledge and engage in discussions. As such, it seems imperative for researchers interested in the process of inclusion that occurs on Facebook academic groups among students, to explore the inclusive nature of knowledge sharing among students without the fear of being excluded. This could be carried out by conducting a survey distributed to students who are active members in different Facebook groups, where academic resources were shared, seeking their perceptions of inclusivity within these Facebook groups, and their experiences in sharing and contributing to the shared notes.

The dynamic between formal institutions and student-driven initiatives can be similarly observed in the use of Facebook groups for student projects or communities. On the one hand, Facebook groups can offer significant benefits in terms of structure, reach, and organization, making it easier for students to coordinate activities, share resources, and communicate with one another. If a formal institution supports or promotes a Facebook group, it may provide additional legitimacy, resources, and access to a wider professional network, much like the resources and stability mentioned in the original example.

However, when a Facebook group becomes institutionalised or formally endorsed by a university or organisation, it may start to lose the informal, student-driven energy that typically makes these groups vibrant and dynamic. As with student spaces, the introduction of institutional oversight might limit the kind of content and interactions allowed in the group. Formal guidelines, rules, or monitoring may constrain the freedom students typically have to discuss or organise without restriction. Moreover, institutional involvement may shift the group from a space of spontaneous student-led creativity into something that feels more top-down and regulated, thus diluting the original student voice and sense of ownership.

The challenge thus, similar to the student space example, lies in striking a balance between the benefits of institutional support (such as resources, and professional networking) and the need to preserve the group's organic, student-driven character. Ensuring that the group

retains its authenticity while benefiting from institutional resources is key to maintaining its value and appeal to students.

Drawing on the data of the present study, curriculum designers should emphasise the importance of integrating digital literacy education in the curriculum to equip students with the required skills needed to navigate social media platforms for educational purposes. Moreover, a particular emphasis should be on acknowledging the role of Facebook educational groups in supporting multilingual education where the use of different languages can contribute to linguistic diversity through peer-to-peer interactions. Relatedly, the data of this study indicated that creating Facebook groups among students could immensely increase students to improve their motivation to learn, share resources and knowledge, collaborate, and develop their linguistic skills.

Languages teachers should understand the linguistic diversity among students in online interaction, so as to improve online users' multilingual competencies in today's digital world. Also, this could be done by spreading awareness of the potential for language bias and the exclusion of certain groups. Thus, I would recommend that language teachers shall design activities that encourage students who use social media platforms, to use different languages. These activities may therefore foster not only the linguistic proficiency among multilingual students, who use online social media platforms, but also the cultural awareness and communicative skills in congruence with the evolving communicative needs of the digital world. Importantly too, the findings of this study unveiled participants' awareness of the natural occurrence of code-switching between languages, when they communicate. Yet, providing guidance on appropriate code-switching, could help students understand when and how to effectively code-switch. Equally, although participants in this study showed an awareness of accommodating their audience, when communicating on the Facebook educational group, language teachers should consider taking into their accounts sociolinguistics principles, including the diverse social contexts of the students, and the targeted audience, and the linguistic variation when designing language-related activities. This would ensure effective engagement among students and lead to an inclusive and supportive learning experiences.

Significantly too, this study found that the online practices that are manifested by both males and female students on the selected Facebook group are different. These differences appear in the way students, males and females share content and use language. In turn, this could help Facebook users themselves to identify patterns of their communication styles and reflect on their own practices. Again, this allows policy makers and curriculum designers to integrate technology in education, ensuring that gender studies could be integrated in online learning. This could be done by integrating the concept of 'digital intersectionality' into the curriculum, and thus improve the gender-related challenges in digital age, in general, and in social media platforms in particular.

Moreover, it is essential to allocate more attention to the recommendations regarding code-switching in educational settings. Code-switching, which involves alternating between languages in communication, can be a powerful pedagogical tool if properly understood and managed. For instance, educators and policymakers should explore and establish clearer guidelines on when and how code-switching can be harnessed to support learning, particularly for students who code switch.

Additionally, educators should receive professional development on how to identify situations where code-switching can enhance understanding, foster inclusivity, and encourage students' confidence in their linguistic abilities. Hence, policies could be introduced to support flexible language use, especially in multilingual classrooms, while maintaining high academic standards.

Importantly, policymakers can play a crucial role by developing frameworks that recognise the value of code-switching as a resource rather than a hindrance. This may include creating teacher training programs, revising language policies to accommodate diverse linguistic practices, and conducting further research to monitor the outcomes of code-switching in educational contexts.

this study also carries a number of implications at several levels. These implications are discussed in the next section.

8.5 Limitations

Despite the valuable insights uncovered in this study, it is crucial to acknowledge the existence of some limitations. I am fully aware of these constraints and in this section, I will explicitly address them. The aim of these explaining these limitations is to provide a comprehensive understanding for fellow researchers and interested readers. Moreover, limitations help readers to engage with the research in a thoughtful way and draw conclusions based on a realistic grasp of the study's scope.

To reiterate, this study focuses on the way Kabyle participants' harness their sharing practices and how they use their language dynamics in their Facebook groups that is created mainly to share educational materials. As such, one limitation could be it is a way challenging and difficult to assert that all these students use the same practices in other social networking sites, such as WhatsApp groups. However, as I clearly state in chapter one, Facebook has been selected due its familiarity and popularity among Algerian students. It would be more relevant for other researchers interested in the field to choose others social networking platforms that are more popular with their target population. Significantly too, researchers who choose to select other social networking sites could use this idea as an opportunity to compare and contrast their findings with the results presented in this study.

Relatedly, further limitation could be related to the study scope and context. This study focused mainly on the online practices, paying no attention to the offline practices that occur in the physical world, or face to face contexts. However, the findings of this study highlight those participants demonstrated a significant engagement and awareness in using Facebook groups, by showing how interdependent social learning occurs on social networking sites.

In addition, the increased engagement of participants leads students to actively contribute and participate in their Facebook groups, providing a deeper understanding of their sense of belonging, autonomy, and also competence, including not only the linguistic competence, but also the online communicative competences. Hence, studying participant dynamics in the offline world, in a classroom could be considered as a further study for researchers to study participants' engagement in the actual classrooms and compare the findings with this research findings.

The other possible limitation of this study could be related to the choice of the methodology employed. This study adopted an online ethnography, using online semi structured interviews and online participant observation to capture participants' dynamics, experiences, and social interaction in the field, herein Fakebook groups (Hammersley and Atkinson, 2007; Hine, 2017). This was through observing participants' practices via posts and comments and then interview them about these practices. Some students that I have firstly recruited to be participants of my study felt reluctant about their sharing practices to be screenshotted. Moreover, a few of them expressed that they feel shy to be interviewed, although I explicitly emphasised that there is no right or wrong answers. As such, while I only explored participants' online dynamics through using semi-structured interviews and participants online observation others could be able to present insightful data using mixed method approaches that carries the use of questionnaires to analyse interaction patterns, including the frequency of interactions such as post-sharing and comments, as well as the frequency of each language used. However, considering the scope and the setting of this study (see chapter 1), the study does not aim to quantify the patterns of interact, but rather to analyse and examine students both resource-sharing and language that they demonstrated through their posts and comments. In this regard, Lee (2011) asserts that because posts are shared with an audience and unveil decision making moments concerning language choice and audience design, they -posts- represent a sort of interaction. Crucially too, using qualitative ethnographic approach helps me to immerse myself in the field and remain attached to the research setting, the thing that quantitative approaches often neglect. In this regard, Oxford (2003) claims that quantitative research methods isolate the researcher from their context. Therefore, I would invite researchers to use questioners or surveys to study the sharing practices and the linguistic patterns among students in the same context to measure the frequency of certain types of languages and communication patterns. This would provide different interpretations that could also contribute to the existing literature in the field.

In this study, I used a small-scale study to examine multilingual students' practices on their Facebook group, and I am aware that is choice might be perceived as a limitation. However, as stated in the earlier paragraph, this study embraces a qualitative approach that is related to the quality of the depth data and not the quantity. As I aimed for thick description and focused on a minority people in Algeria, (the Kabyle students), the current study does not aim at generalising its findings to all Kabyle students who use Facebook for educational purposes

in the Kabyle context. As a result, there are restrictions on how the generalisability or transferability of the findings may be used, since conducting similar studies carried out in diverse settings would undoubtedly provide different findings. However, there is a potential for transferability based on the level and the nature of similarities to various contexts (Guba and Lincoln, 1985). Therefore, to enable replication by a broader research audience and enable them to identify similarities with their own contexts, the present study includes comprehensive descriptions of the research participants under investigation.

Hence, the scope of this study, focuses specifically on the sharing practices and language dynamics of Kabyle participants within Facebook groups created for educational purposes, has several important implications, both for the current research and for future studies in this field. The implication of such a scope can be understood in terms of the findings' contributions to the academic community, the limitations that guide how the findings can be interpreted, and the potential areas for future exploration.

Implications for Understanding Language Dynamics in Digital Spaces: The focus on Facebook groups as a space for educational resource-sharing and interaction provides valuable insights into how students use their language skills in an online context. By focusing on Kabyle students in Algeria, the study contributes to the understanding of how multilingualism operates in digital spaces, particularly in the context of educational settings. It reveals how participants navigate language choices, negotiate meaning, and engage with one another in a shared online environment. The implications of this scope suggest that language use on social media platforms like Facebook is influenced by both educational goals and the social dynamics of the participants, making it an important area for researchers interested in digital literacy, online communication, and language practices.

Implications for social media as an Educational Tool: The findings emphasize the role of Facebook groups as a valuable educational tool that fosters a sense of belonging, autonomy, and competence among students. This study highlights how students use social media not only for academic purposes but also as a medium for building relationships and engaging in social learning. The study's scope implies that future

research can explore how other platforms, such as WhatsApp or Twitter, are similarly utilized in educational contexts, potentially offering a broader understanding of how different platforms impact student engagement and learning outcomes. For educators, the study suggests that leveraging social media in educational settings can enhance collaborative learning and create opportunities for students to engage with the content and with each other outside the traditional classroom.

Implications for Methodological Approaches in Online Research: By using a qualitative ethnographic approach, the study provides a rich, contextually grounded understanding of student practices in Facebook groups. The study's scope implies that a qualitative approach is particularly well-suited for examining the complexities of online behavior, as it allows for deep immersion in the participants' digital interactions. However, the limitations of using only qualitative methods (such as the inability to quantify certain behaviors) highlight the need for mixed-methods approaches in future research. Researchers could extend this study by incorporating quantitative tools, such as surveys or questionnaires, to explore patterns of interaction, language use frequency, and other measurable aspects of online communication. This would allow for a more comprehensive understanding of how social media impacts student behaviour in educational contexts.

Implications for Transferability and Contextual Relevance: The study's focus on a small, specific group of Kabyle students in Algeria carries implications for how its findings can be applied to other contexts. While the study does not aim to generalize its findings to all Kabyle students or to students in other regions, it offers a framework for understanding similar dynamics in other educational settings. The implications of this scope suggest that, although the findings may not be universally applicable, they can be transferred to other populations that share similar characteristics or contexts. For example, future research in other multilingual communities, or among students in different parts of the world, could examine how online resource-sharing and language dynamics operate in their own specific contexts, offering comparative insights.

Implications for Future Research on Online and Offline Practices: One of the key implications of this study's scope is the recognition that it focuses exclusively on online practices, while offline interactions were not explored. This suggests that future research

could explore how students' online behaviours correlate with or diverge from their offline behaviours in face-to-face educational contexts. By comparing the online and offline dynamics of student engagement, researchers could gain a fuller understanding of the role digital tools play in shaping student identity, communication, and learning. The implications of this scope invite further studies that could bridge the gap between online and offline educational experiences, potentially leading to a more integrated approach to studying student engagement in the digital age.

Implications for the Concept of Generalisability: The study's small sample size and focus on a particular group of Kabyle students limit the generalizability of its findings. However, the scope of the research suggests that the value lies not in broad generalization but in providing a detailed, contextualized understanding of a specific group's practices. This approach emphasizes the importance of qualitative research in capturing the nuances of individual and group experiences. The study's findings could serve as a reference point for researchers examining similar groups in comparable settings, with a focus on understanding particular social, cultural, or linguistic dynamics that may be shared across different populations.

In summary, the implications of the study's scope extend to various areas, including the role of social media in education, methodological considerations for online research, and the contextualized understanding of language dynamics among specific populations. While the scope of the study limits its generalizability, it provides valuable insights that can be applied in similar contexts and inspire future research that explores the intersection of online and offline learning, social media practices, and multilingualism.

8.6 Final Reflections on Doing a PhD

My doctoral experience has been a life-changing intellectual adventure. It was characterised by curiosity, rigorous research, and the resilience to overcome challenges and obstacles, which has finally resulted in a noteworthy contribution academia.

Throughout this journey, I have been seriously thinking about my own thinking, when discussing issues, ideas, and concepts that I want to explore in my research. Simultaneously, I have been mindful of the boundaries that might define its scope. Equally too, I have been more conscious about the suitable methodology that could be employed in probing my research questions, and fulfil the study objective. Additionally, my PhD journey was a reflective one in a sense that it makes me question not only the appropriate methodologies that I can use, but also my own assumptions, my roles as a researcher, and my own biases. Therefore, I have been pivotal in ensuring the integrity and transparency when choosing the methodology, collect the data and interpret the findings. Significantly, too, doing qualitative research has immensely broadened my perspective to embrace the existence of the multiple realities that exist in this social world. Crucially too, being an ethnographer who navigates in the online space has significantly shaped my understanding of the dynamics of virtual communities and the digital interaction. Consequently, this enables me to unveil the complexities of the digital world, providing insights into the ways in which individuals communicate and construct meaning. Moreover, this has provided me with a lens through which I observe and interpret individual online behaviour, including my own.

Embarking in a PhD journey has greatly contributed to both my personal and academic growth. At a personal level, this journey has been a voyage to of self-discovery. It helped me to be more confident, more disciplined and committed to my work. Moreover, embarking In this PhD journey made me has sharpened my critical thinking skills. Additionally, throughout this PhD journey, I have developed my communicative skills. As an Algerian speaker, English is not my native language, but my third language.

At a professional level, I have been actively engaged in participating in academic conferences, seminars, research colloquiums, as well in discussing my research with colleagues. Doing this has enhanced my ability to articulate ideas and be an open minded to receiving constructing feedback that contribute to the richness of my study.

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Appendix 1 : Consent Form

School of Education
Paisley Campus

Consent Form

Title of the research project: Using Online Practices on Facebook: A study of Males and Females Use of Online Linguistic and Learning resources on a Facebook group, a Bourdieusian Theoretical Lens.

Name of the researcher: Abir Benseitita

- 1- I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the above project and the researcher has answered any queries to my satisfaction.
- 2- I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from the project at any time, without having to give a reason and without any consequences.
- 3- I understand that I am going to:
 - a- Complete an interview form.
 - b- Participate in an individual interview
 - c- Be audio-recorded during the interview.

4- I understand that any information recorded in the investigation will remain confidential and no information that identifies me will be made publicly available.

5- I consent to being a participant in the project

Name of the participant: _____

Date: _____

Signature: _____

Appendix 2: Participant Information Sheet

Participant Information Sheet

Study Title: Using Online Practices on Facebook: A study of Males and Females Use of Online Linguistic and Learning resources on a Facebook group, a Bourdieusian Theoretical Lens

Researcher: Abir BENSETITA

What is the research about?

Hello!

I' am Abir, a PhD student from the school of Education and Social Science, University of The West of Scotland. I am interested in finding out the multilingual practices, particularly the code switching practices on Facebook and how the use of these practices differ from males to females.

Why have I been chosen?

This research focuses on Kabyle students of English. You have been chosen because you are an active Facebook user and a multilingual speaker who is equipped with high experiences and possibilities to use code switching while posting and replying to others.

What will happen to me if I take part?

If you are willing to participate in this study, a consent form will be sent and hence signed by you in order to confirm that you are happy to participate in this study. The duration of the data collection period will last from 5-6 months The online interaction of those who signed the consent form and send it back will be observed. For the observation, I would also ask you to screenshot the post and the comment you share with other participants, the screenshot will be blurred, and your name will not appear in the findings. For the interview, participants' names will be kept anonymous. The interview will last from to 45-60 minutes and it will be conducted in an audio or a video form (whatever your preference is). This is to facilitate the process of analysing the data for this study. The researcher at this stage will ensure that their data (including audio/video recordings) will be secured and password-protected and merely the

researcher who can access it. Still, participants will be informed that they have all rights to withdraw at any stage of the research and any sort of data could be removed permanently.

Are there any potential risks to you in taking part?

This study does not involve any psychological or physical foreseeable risks.

Are there any benefits in taking part in this study?

Your participation will be helpful not only in adding knowledge to the field, but rather, it will also serve as a way to understand your linguistic and the sharing practices in the Facebook group

Will my participation will be confidential?

As I mentioned earlier, your participation will be completely confidential. Your name will not be revealed publicly. Instead, a pseudo name will be used. The same strictest procedure will be applied for the screenshots; your name will not be disclosed anymore and it will be blurred to ensure that your anonymity will be respected all the time. To remain confidential, the collected data will be compatible with the University Policy and it will be saved on a password computer.

What happens if I change my mind?

Whatever the stage of the fieldwork is, you have the total right to withdraw. Hence, the provided information will be removed.

What happens if something goes wrong?

If something goes wrong, you can contact the chair of the Faculty Ethics Committee. His email address is shown below:

Where can I get more information?

If you have any further questions or comments concerning this research, please do not hesitate to contact me via email: [REDACTED]

Appendix 3 : Ethical Approval

05/07/2021

Dear Abir Bensetita,

Your application 16510: An analysis of the online code switching practices among Kabyle males and females students of English Facebook through Bourdieusian social practice and Brown and Levinson theoretical lens., submission 13786, has been approved by the Education and Social Sciences SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them. The following comments are intended to form discussion with your supervisor.

Title	Comment
Please give a full summary of the purpose, justification, design and methodology of the planned study: (word limit 1000 words)	While this is a novel way of identifying and recruiting a sample, describing interacting with Facebook as observing individuals in a natural setting is potentially at odds with the persona individuals use in an online 'world'. That said, this is not an ethical issue..
Please explain/justify your intended sample size:	The limitation of this type of recruitment can be discussed with your experienced supervisor.
Please provide details of how you will recruit participants to your study:	the limitations of generalising from this sample are not fully described. However this is not an ethical issue.

Good luck with your research.

Dr Iain McPhee

Appendix 4: Interview Guide

Areas of Exploration	Interview Questions
<p>-Participant’s personal information and background (ethnicity, gender, level of education).</p> <p>-Students’ linguistic repertoire (language access, bi/multilingualism).</p> <p>Student’s attitudes in relation to the offline and the online communication.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Could you please tell me about yourself, where are you from, and what level are you studying? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What does being a Kabyle mean to you? - Tell me more about your province? 2. How many languages do you use? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Which language(s) do you use most? -Do you use them at home as well? (face to face) -are there the same languages you use on online communication? 3. Do you have any difficulties using a language that is different from your mother tongue <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -what is that language? 4. Do you think that your choice of language on online communication differ from your language choice on offline interaction (Face-to-face)? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -in what way it differ? 5. When you interact (online) with others, who do not belong to your same gender (a male or a female), do you think that you need to control the language you alternate to? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Is it the same language you use when interacting with a female/male?

Students' use of Code-switching

6. What does Facebook mean to you
-How does it fit in your life?
-Is it Typical for your life?
7. Do you tend to code switch on Facebook? (while writing a post/comment)
8. Are you an active user of Facebook?
-An estimate average about many hours do you spend, daily?
9. When do you first join the Facebook group (***Département d'Anglais Officiel UMMTO***)?
-What does this group mean to you?
10. What is the reason of joining it?
-What do you usually share?
-What kind of posts you share?
11. When posting/ commenting on Facebook, do you take into account your social and the cultural values?

Appendix 5: Interview Transcript

Sid Ali Interview Transcription

(Minutes: 58:54)

Participant: S= Sid Ali, R= Researcher

R: Hello Sid Ali! I hope you are doing well. Thanks so much again for accepting to take part in my study. Um, I am just going to ask you if you had the chance to look over the documents that I have sent.

S: yes! I did review them

R: ok great! I am going to go through explaining once again my research.

S: ok

R: briefly my research is about understanding students' linguistic practices, particularly the code-switching practices. It looks also at males and females differences based in these practices. I may need to take screenshots of your own practices, are you okay with that?

S: yes sure

R: thanks, your Facebook name on the screenshot will be blurred, and your name in the interview will be replaced by a pseudonym. ok

S: ok yes

R: for the time, the interview will last for 45 minutes. If you want to stop by anytime, just let me know. Remember that there is no right or wrong answer. Just fell free to express your perspectives and your experiences.

S: alright. Let's start

R: my first question is to

S: Hello! I am a Kabyle student of English. I'am 22 years old. I am a master 2 student of English speciality literature and civilisation. I am exactly from Walia in Kabylie in Algeria of course. Churfa. It is a small village about 500 people who live there. For myself I got a tween @@ in case you would need it. He is studying French at Mouloud Mammeri University. My dream project is to create of private school of languages.

R: why? A school of languages in particular?

S: because my brother studies French language and I am studying English we thought that we will share the same goal.

R: so you think that studying/learning languages is important nowadays

S: in my opinion it is important that every language should be taught or ... because as you know you cannot express yourself or explain something without language. When I was a kid, I have learnt the French language very soon, when I was a little kid, I learnt French quickly at a very early age. Since I watched anime and cartoon in French so I did learn it very fast. I was using French more than other languages.

R: more than your mother tongue too?

S: no! Except my mother tongue of course. You know this because of our country and its history. Algeria is a francophone country. And the Kabyle people use the Kabyle dialect with French to express themselves. And honestly when I got my baccalaureate exam I did not want to study English because I was more comfortable with the French language

R: ok and then how did you change your mind?

S: but right now, if I have to choose between these languages of course I have to choose English because you know I struggled a lot at the beginning since we have the oral module when the student has to speak and express themselves and I did not have the courage neither the capacity to express myself in English so I have struggled a lot, but I loved this language even I make mistakes in English in writing or speaking, I am always trying to ameliorate my

skills in English ...sometimes I was thinking of writing a book in English not a book but a short story because I have a friend who writes similar thing in English.

R: you said at the first time you were facing some difficulties in speaking the English language, what about writing. Is it the same thing?

S: you know what! I did not know anything about English. I found myself that I have to translate from French to English. For example, when introducing yourself. In French you have to say ***Bonjour je m'appelle ... j'ai 22 ans.*** But if we translate this sentence in directly English, it is ***hello my name is ... I have 22 years old.***

R: Yes this the translation from French to English is misleading especially when it come to grammar

S: oh yes that is why we call the French and the English language are des ***même soeurs*** so this is my problem I always tend to translate from a language that I know to the other one that I want to speak or write.

R: speaking about languages. How many languages do you use and what are the languages you use most?

S: I speak Kabyle of course, French, English and Arabic language.

R: is it the modern standard Arabic you learnt at schools or the Algerian Arabic?

S: no! Is it the modern standard Arabic we learnt at school, not the Algerian Arabic. I remember I always got bad marks in the Arabic language. I know that we are an Arabic country but I did not used to interact using the Arabic language.

R: so these are the languages you use?

S: I know a little bit of the Italian language because when I was a little boy, I used to watch a lot of cartoons using in Italian language. I don't master it like French and English... I only know some few words. So, since I was a kid, I did not have any difficulties in learning a language, every language except my mother tongue, I learnt them via cartoons and Netflix.

R: that is a smart way to learn a language and a new culture as well.

S: that is true! ***Dessah !***

R: do you use these languages with your family also?

S: my father speaks French and Kabyle. In my family when it comes to serious communication, we often use French to communicate.

R: and what about the online communication. I mean on Facebook, when you share and comment?

S: it depends on the context. When I interact with my friends I use French and code switch to the Kabyle language. However, when I see a post in English or Arabic I will respond in English or Arabic.

R: huh! Makes sense... and don't you find any difficulties in using a language that is different from your mother tongue? in online communication I mean

S: ... sometimes I feel conformable in using French and English than my mother tongue. Because we did not learn how to write it. In schools, I did not study Tamazight in its written Form. Unlike French. I started to study French in third year primary schools and English in first year in secondary schools.

R: great and do you think that your choice of language on Facebook differ from your language choice on offline communication or face to face communication.

S: when I speak face to face I usually use Kabyle my dialect with French because as I told you before we are a francophone country, because if I use English the majority will not understand me. so I use French with Kabyle in your face to face communication and in my online communication you use English with French and Kabyle

R: Ok interesting and did you find it interesting when switching from one code to another?

S: yes a lot. I enjoy learning languages are a real power.

R: ok and do these languages affected by the gender of the person you are talking to? I mean do you control your language when reacting/ commenting to females?

S: it depends on the context. For example when I interact with males I do not control my language however when I interact with females I have to respect them. My language has to be respectful and controlled.

R: in what way exactly. Could you give me an example? Or experience

S: actually you know it depends on the person whether it is a male or a female. For example when I interact with my girlfriend I don't feel that I have to control my language. She is not a strange she is close. But when it comes to a friend or a colleague I control my language. I am one of the admins of the UMMTO group, and I always got messages or comments usually from girls asking about something concerning the department and exams things like that. I respond with a polite manner in a respectful way. I use a formal way, you know there is ... *il y a quelque chose que j'aimrais ajouter* (there is something that I wanted to add) for example when a student contact me usually they use English so I would also use the English language, if they switch between languages, I will also code switch to the language they code switch to.

R: ok so your choice of language depends on the choice of the person you are communicating with

S: yes that is it.

R: ok perfect. Now let's move on the next part, you know a part of my study is about the use of languages and code switching in particular on Facebook

S: Yes

R: my question is what does mean Facebook mean to you, how does it fit in your life?

S: I use Facebook all the time to be in touch with the world. What is happening in the world, to inform people for example, I was a member of a committee in the department of English UMMTO. I usually use the group of department to give some information about the department, exams, timetable you know to the student. I use it also to stay in contact with my family, friends and strangers and also to give and receive information about the department.

R: I noticed that you are a member and an admin in the group. Could you please tell me when did you first join this group?

S: I joined it since my first year 2017.

R: so this was your first year in the university.

S: yeah

R: according to you, what was the reason that drives you to join that group?

S: when new students come to our department, when I was a member of the committee I usually tell them to join that group because they will be in touch with their colleagues. For example there are some lectures which we studies in classes and other students volunteer to share their notes and lectures in the group so it helps students to revise.

R: so the main reason is only for academic purposes.

S: yes this is the main reason.

R: okay. When you post or comment on Facebook , do you take into consideration your cultural and social values. I mean do you transmit your culture through language to show that you belong to a particular group?

S: yes I use Kabyle and French a lot while communicating. But when I know that a person does not use Kabyle, I use French and English. I cannot use Arabic, I'm too bad at using it. I cannot use it to comment or to share something.

R: ok moving back to other part of my study which is about the online linguistic practices and the code switching practices in particular. When I say code switching, how can you define it?

S: it is the switching from one language to another.

R: how did you see the code switching, is it something good for you or bad...

S: Umm it is in between you know because when I was in my third year I have studied about post colonialism. When for example there is a colonisation of a country, people of the country that was colonised will see the ... how to say it... ***quand par exemple le colonisateur vient dans un pays afin de coloniser. quand ils ont sort, les pays colonisés ou bien le peuples colonisés voient la langue de colisateur comme une langue superieure a celle qu'ils utilisent quand ils parlent. This is the case of Algeria,***

R: how?

S: For example in Algeria when you see someone speaks in French it means he is intellectual ... someone who is intelligent, who has a lot of knowledge. So I am in between I am always saying that learning any language would be great, because in the future you may use it. I am not the kind of people who perceive that if for example I speak French means I am intellectual, ***quelqu'un qui a un certain grade de connaissance et tout.*** I only see French as a language as the other language. A normal language that we can use daily

R: ok great! And do you see code switching as a process that facilitates the conversation

S: yes of course it will facilitate the communication. Why. Because there are some words that we don't use it in Kabyle language. For example scientific words, political ones. When you are in a political conversation you may need to use French more often to be understood. I think that we use the Kabyle language to share some ideas that are personal. It is not always using French language.

R: ok makes sense. And do you think that alternation from one language to another depends on the context you are in?

S: yes totally. As I told you

R: and does it depend on the person you are communicating with

S; yes for example as I told you when I was a member of the committee in my department, when I talk to the head of the department I usually use French to communicate with him

R: and what about your teachers, I mean you meet them outside the classroom but in the department.

S: in the department I use French and Kabyle, even them they use French and Kabyle outside the classroom, but inside they only use English.

R: okay! Do you see language as a means to express culture and ethnicity?

S: yes for example when I want to comment or write a post about the Kabyle language or culture, I usually use French. Because since ***we are francophone country*** and the majority of Algerians do not speak Tamazight. I would write in my post or comment: ***la langue Tamazight est la langue natale du nord africain. l'algerie a été toujours Berbers il n'a jamais été Arab.***

So I write it in French because all Algerians will understand it. So I usually use French to defend Tamazight in order to make the other Algerians.

R: ah okay I understand. This is helpful. I have some screenshots to show. It is all about your linguistics practices.

Admin

· 10 March · 🌐

"Our lives begin to end the day we become silent about things that matter"

[#MartinLutherKing](#)

Bonne soirée camarades.

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4 comments

S: I wrote the quotation as it in English because it is originally from the English and I added Bonne soiree.

R: why did not you finish the sentence in English as you started it in English?

S: unconsciously. I just enjoy using more languages. I usually use French as the code switched language. When I write in English, sometimes I use French without knowing that.

R: How?

S: There are some words in French that they look like English words. For example when I write Department, I write **Département** in French groupe instead of group. That is because of the interference between the French and English language.

R: oh yes I see. Actually, we arrived at the end of the interview, if you have anything that you want to add, or to ask about, just feel free to do so.

S: ok. No. actually I don't have anything to add for the moment. Just thank you for giving me the opportunity to participate in your study I really enjoyed that.

R: you are very welcome. It is a pleasure to know that. Have a great night ahead. Goodbye.

S: take care. Bye

Appendix 6: Coding

R: that is a smart way to learn a language and a new culture as well.

S: that is true! **Dessah !**

R: do you use these languages with your family also?

S: my father speaks French and Kabyle. In my family when it comes to serious communication, we often use French to communicate.

R: and what about the online communication. I mean on Facebook, when you share and comment?

S: it depends on the context. When I interact with my friends I use French and code switch to the Kabyle language. However, when I see a post in English or Arabic I will respond in English or Arabic.

R: huh! Makes sense... and don't you find any difficulties in using a language that is different from your mother tongue? in online communication I mean

Normal

202

Abir Bensefita

Parents use of languages (French and Kabyle dialect)

Abir Bensefita

The use of French depends on the context

Abir Bensefita

Context

Abir Bensefita

Online communication: French and Kabyle

S: ... sometimes I feel conformable in using French and English than my mother tongue. Because we did not learn how to write it. In schools, I did not study Tamazight in its written form. Unlike French, I started to study French in third year primary schools and English in first year in secondary schools.

R: great and do you think that your choice of language on Facebook differ from your language choice on offline communication or face to face communication.

S: when I speak face to face I usually use Kabyle my dialect with French because as I told you

Abir Bensefita

French and English Status

Abir Bensefita

Written form of Tamazight

Abir Bensefita

French language in Education

Abir Bensefita

Kabyle and French offline

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R: so the main reason is only for academic purposes.

S: yes this is the main reason.

R: okay. When you post or comment on Facebook, do you take into consideration your cultural and social values. I mean do you transmit your culture through language to show that you belong to a particular group?

S: yes I use Kabyle and French a lot while communicating. But when I know that a person does not use Kabyle, I use French and English. I cannot use Arabic, I'm too bad at using it. I cannot use it to comment or to share something.

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R: how?

S: *For example in Algeria when you see someone speaks in French it means he is intellectual ... someone who is intelligent, who has a lot of knowledge. So I am in between I am always saying that learning any language would be great, because in the future you may use it. I am not the kind of people who perceive that if for example I speak French means I am intellectual, quelqu'un qui a un certain grade de connaissance et tout.* I only see French as a language as the other language. A normal language that we can use daily

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Abir Bensefita

Facebook as an educational platform (academic purposes)

Abir Bensefita

Language and identity
Kabyle / French

Abir Bensefita

French and English to communicate with non-Kabyle speakers

Abir Bensefita

Arabic deficiency

Abir Bensefita

Perception of CS

Abir Bensefita

Attitudes towards CS

Abir Bensefita

Language superiority

Abir Bensefita

CS

March 11, 2022

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CS

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Language attitudes

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Perception of Cs

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Links

A B
E~~mo~~is (laughing face+ Humour)

A B
A French word: Voila, followed by English words

A B
An Internet meme that shows how the course are accumulated for students

